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1 Introduction

The task "Technology Outlook and Use Cases" within the agrifoodTEF project aims to continuously monitor the latest technologies and use cases in the field of testing and validation of AI solutions and advanced technologies for the agrifood sector. A core focus of the task is collaboration with a broad network of ecosystem partners, with particular attention given to the needs of small farms and businesses. This task is an ongoing effort throughout the project's duration.

The deliverable "D1.2 Online Technology and Use Cases Outlook Y2," produced at the end of the second year of the project (M24), is a key outcome of this task. It provides an overview of the activities conducted so far, the technological trends identified, and the business-focused use cases analysed, considering the needs and requirements of technology firms. The findings serve as a basis for guiding the development and enhancement of the agrifoodTEF infrastructure, including both physical services offered at dedicated facilities and updates to the digital infrastructure and online services. This report documents the steps taken and the data collected, offering recommendations for further refinement of services within the project.

The report "Online Technology & Use-Cases Outlook Y2" was conceived as an operational guide rather than a desk-bound study. Its purpose is to help agrifoodTEF partners decide which technologies, skills and infrastructure merit investment over the coming years – and how to translate those choices into services that reach the market. Accordingly, it speaks simultaneously to the TEF strategic team, to service-line managers, and to SMEs and start-ups seeking a venue in which to validate their ideas.

To make that guidance straightforward to follow, the document is built around four tightly linked chapters:

- Chapter 5 provides a reality check on the current state of AI-enabled smart agriculture: what is already working in the field, where the technology is still fragile, and which adoption barriers remain most acute.
- Chapter 6 moves from state to trajectory. It unpacks the specific technologies agrifoodTEF has prioritised for further development and the use cases in which they are already demonstrating value, mapping each to the services the TEF can offer.
- Chapter 7 applies a business lens, translating the technological landscape into bottom-line questions: market outlook, investment climate, regulatory headwinds and the practical hurdles firms face when scaling AI and robotics beyond pilot projects.
- Chapter 8 distils all preceding insights into actionable conclusions and recommendations – from immediate service tweaks to longer-term infrastructure build-outs – enabling every agrifoodTEF team to move seamlessly from analysis to implementation.

Read sequentially, these chapters take the reader from where we are (Chapter 5), through what is emerging and why it matters (Chapter 6), to how the market will respond (Chapter 7), and finally to what agrifoodTEF should do next (Chapter 8). The result is a compass that aligns strategic planning with concrete, near-term action.

2 Terms and abbreviations

Key terms and abbreviations related to the Report:

Technology outlook in agrifoodTEF - refers to forecasts and predictions about future trends and solution developments in agriculture. It encompasses both new solutions that are just emerging and existing solutions that are evolving from new use cases of technology mixes or new technologies.

Technology - a technical solution that makes a given functionality possible (i.e. proximity lidar sensor, GPS, hyperspectral imaging, 5G communication).

Agriculture technology / food processing technology - a method of carrying out a production or process, e.g. autonomous potato harvesting, automatic onion peeling.

Use case / essential use case - publicly observed intention to leverage a new advanced robotics or AI solution to address a specific problem within the agri-food sector. This intention is contextualized by the specific conditions present like i.e. a given location.

Solution - solution in specific product responding to needs in agri-food sector. It may be either a complete system (e.g. an autonomous robot managing phytosanitary product spraying in a vineyard) or a subsystem (e.g., the perception system providing that robot with the capability to decide how much product to spray), but the key point is that there exists a very specific problem that the solution addresses.

Functionality - it applies to the basic capabilities of a robot system that the system leverages to perform complex activities called "tasks".

Cluster - a concentrated group of similar agriculture technologies or/and solutions. Within the cluster, experiences will be exchanged, and service components will be created such as methodology, infrastructure, metrics (i.e. crop-harvesting, weeding).

AI (Artificial Intelligence) - It is the ability of machines to exhibit human skills, such as reasoning, learning, planning and creativity. It enables technical systems to perceive their environment, deal with what they perceive and solve problems, while they work toward achieving a specific goal.

IoT (Internet of Things) - IoT describes devices with sensors, processing ability, software and other technologies that connect and exchange data with other devices and systems over the Internet or other communications networks.

ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) - ICTs is a broader term for Information Technology (IT), which refers to all communication technologies, including the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, computers, software, middleware, videoconferencing, social networking, and other media applications and services enabling users to access, retrieve, store, transmit, and manipulate information in a digital form.

GIS Technology (Geographic Information System) - is a technology used for collecting, analyzing, managing, and visualizing spatial data, meaning information connected to geographic locations. GIS enables the creation of detailed maps, analysis of spatial relationships, and better decision-making based on collected data. This technology integrates various data sources, such as satellite imagery, GPS measurements, and databases, to provide an accurate representation of spatial information. GIS is widely used in many fields, including precision agriculture, urban planning, environmental management, forestry, transportation, and climate change monitoring. With this technology, users can effectively identify trends, analyze problems, and model solutions within a spatial context.

FMS (Farm Management Systems) - FMS are integrated software solutions designed to help farmers manage and optimize their agricultural operations. These systems collect, analyze, and present data related to various farming activities, enabling more efficient decision-making and resource management. By leveraging technologies such as IoT sensors, GPS tracking, data analytics, and sometimes AI, farm management systems support precision agriculture, helping farmers reduce waste, improve productivity, and achieve sustainability goals.

DIH (Digital Innovation Hub) - DIHs can help ensure that every company, small or large, high-tech or not, can take advantage of digital opportunities. They also provide innovation services, such as financing advice, training and skills development that are needed for a successful digital transformation. They are a type of one-stop shop for the given range of services.

EDIH (European Digital Innovation Hubs) - EDIHs are one-stop shops supporting companies and public sector organizations to respond to digital challenges and become more competitive.

AgriTech (agricultural technology) - The whole of technologies used in agriculture; currently understood as technologies in agriculture that provide innovative products that increase the productivity and sustainability of agriculture.

Living Lab, Show Field - A new approach to creating and implementing innovative and implementation of innovative solutions in organizations; its basic premise is participation of end users in the entire process of novelty creation, in the form of show laboratories (Living Lab) or crops (Show Field).

R&D (Research and Development) - is the set of innovative activities undertaken by corporations or governments in developing new services or products and improving existing ones. R&D constitutes the first stage of development of a potential new service or the production process.

SMEs (Small and Medium-sized enterprises) - Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) account for 99% of all businesses in the EU. The definition of an SME is critical for access to finance and EU support programmes, as these programmes are specifically designed for enterprises that meet certain criteria, such as having fewer than 250 employees and an annual turnover of less than €50 million.

Micro-enterprises - Micro-enterprises are the smallest type of SMEs, with fewer than 10 employees and an annual turnover of less than €2 million. They are often run by a single person or a small team and are typically focused on a specific niche market.

Small Enterprises - Small enterprises are slightly larger than micro-enterprises, with between 10 and 50 employees and an annual turnover of less than €10 million. They are often more established than micro-enterprises and may have a broader customer base.

CAP - Common Agricultural Policy.

EU CAP Network - The Network is a forum through which National CAP Networks, organisations, administrations, researchers, entrepreneurs and practitioners can share knowledge and information (e.g. via peer-to-peer learning and good practices) about agriculture and rural policy.

EU - European Union.

EC - European Commission.

European Green Deal - is a package of policy initiatives, which aims to set the EU on the path to a green transition, with the ultimate goal of reaching climate neutrality by 2050. It supports the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy.

European Innovation Partnership (EIP) - a European initiative that promotes innovation to adapt the agricultural sector to environmental and climate challenges. Innovation partnerships mean that farmers, agricultural advisors, researchers and other stakeholders work together in a project to develop practical innovative solutions that occur in agriculture.

Agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) - The agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) works to foster competitive and sustainable farming and forestry that 'achieves more and better from less'.

It contributes to ensuring a steady supply of food, feed and biomaterials, developing its work in harmony with the essential natural resources on which farming depends.

Decision support - These are interactive computer systems that help decision makers use models and data in solving problems unstructured. These systems support organizational and business decision-making activities.

Mobile application - This is the general name for software that runs on a mobile device mobile device, such as phones and tablets; it allows for faster and simpler implementation of services.

Robotization - It is an interdisciplinary field of research dealing with the creation of robots, as well as controlling and operating them.

Satellite - This is the process of identifying the geographical location of a user or device. This can be done through a number of methods, including IP address tracking, GPS tracking and triangulation.

Big data - These are large, both structured and unstructured datasets from various sources that are processed and analysed to obtain new information. This information can be used to create new products, as well as improving the effectiveness and efficiency of processes, including processing information to enable better insight, decision-making and automation.

Autonomous - These are devices capable of autonomously navigating a designated area, which collect internal and external data, and then respond to them in two ways: they receive and transmit the data to a computer or, equipped with artificial intelligence, for example, react directly - in the field of agriculture, for example, they increase the dosage of fertilizer or adjust the lighting in a room.

Augmented reality - It is a technology based on the integration of digital information and the user's environment in real time. For example, this applies to solutions involving the superimposition of additional information, such as text

or graphics, on objects in the user's environment user, which are displayed on the screen of a device such as a smartphone.

Precision farming - is a management approach that focuses on (near real-time) observation, measurement, and responses to variability in crops, fields and animals. It can help increase crop yields and animal performance, reduce costs, including labour costs, and optimise process inputs.

Smart agriculture - Also known as Farming 4.0 or digital farming, smart farming incorporates information and communication technologies into machinery, equipment and sensors used in agricultural production systems. Technologies such as the IoT and cloud computing are advancing this development even further by introducing more robots and artificial intelligence into farming.

WoS - Web of Science.

3 Methodology

Building upon the experience gained during the development of the agrifoodTEF D1.1 Report: "Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1"¹, we adopted a new approach for this year's "Technology and Use Cases Outlook." The focus shifted to an online report format, emphasizing expert surveys and future forecasts as the primary tools for gathering and analysing data.

The key element of this revised methodology was the use of targeted surveys. These were designed to engage experts from the agri-food industry, the scientific community, and representatives of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs). Survey distribution relied on contact networks provided by project partners, ensuring a diverse and representative group of respondents.

The primary aim of the surveys was to collect insights into the main challenges, barriers, and threats facing the agri-food sector, particularly in the context of AI and advanced technologies - here understood as a broad category encompassing robotics and related innovations. The collected data forms the foundation of the "Technology and Use Cases Outlook 2024" report, providing a forward-looking perspective and addressing the evolving needs of stakeholders.

This methodology reflects a strategic shift towards a more dynamic and predictive reporting style, leveraging the expertise of the project's ecosystem to create actionable insights and better align with project goals. Two distinct surveys were introduced - the "IE Survey" and the "EDIH Survey" - tailored to the specific roles and areas of expertise of their respective respondent groups. The IE Survey explored company activities in the agri-food sector, focusing on experiences with implementing new technologies, challenges encountered, and strategies adopted to address emerging trends. In contrast, the EDIH Survey examined service offerings, collaboration networks, and potential partnerships with agrifoodTEF, as well as sectors served, technologies utilized by clients, and operational challenges.

Both surveys shared a common focus on barriers to technology adoption, future industry trends, and the ethical, legal, and social aspects (ELSA) of modern technologies. Together, they provided a holistic view of the ecosystem, highlighting complementary insights from these two groups.

Key Questions Addressed in the Survey for Industry Experts:

- Technologies under development and their impact on products.
- Major challenges and barriers to adopting advanced technologies.
- Strategies employed to adapt to technological trends.
- Collaboration with scientific institutions and plans for digital transformation.
- Contributions of technologies to sustainable development.
- Future outlooks, including automation in agriculture and transformative technologies.

Key Questions Addressed in the Survey for EDIHs:

- Familiarity with TEF and agrifoodTEF concepts.
- Types of services offered, such as testing, validation, technical support, and digital transformation guidance.
- Sectors supported (e.g., AgriTech, Blockchain, Virtual Reality).
- Technologies used by EDIH clients.
- Challenges faced by EDIHs, including organizational and network-related issues.

¹ agrifoodTEF 2023 Project Report: [D1.1 Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1](#).

- Opportunities for collaboration with agrifoodTEF in areas like training, data analysis, compliance, and sustainability.

Common Themes in Both Surveys:

- Barriers and challenges associated with implementing new technologies in the agri-food sector.
- Perspectives on industry trends and future developments.
- Transformative technologies and associated risks, including ELSA considerations.

Figure 1. Distribution of questions by focus area. Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024)

The list of industry experts was developed collaboratively by all agrifoodTEF partners. Each partner identified relevant experts within their respective networks, obtained their consent to participate, and collected their contact details. Partners then distributed the surveys directly to these experts, offering motivation and conducting follow-ups to achieve a high response rate.

A similar process was followed for the surveyed EDIHs. Each agrifoodTEF partner identified EDIHs within their area of influence, established contact, and obtained their agreement to participate in the survey. Partners then distributed the surveys, ensuring proper communication, motivation, and follow-up to secure a strong response rate. The table below lists the EDIHs that submitted their responses (Table 2. Responses from EDIH Representatives to the Survey).

Tab. 1. Responses from EDIH Representatives to the Survey

No.	EDIH name	Country
1	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW - EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	Belgium
2	DIGITALIS	Belgium
3	EDIH-CONNECT	Belgium
4	EDIH DIGIHUB	Bulgaria
5	Next-Gen-BloTechEDIH	Bulgaria
6	ZSA	Latvia
7	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole	France
8	Idele	France
9	Pôle EMC2 Competitiveness cluster for innovation in production technologies	France
10	EDIH OCCITANIA	France
11	DIH ONEX	Bosnia and Herzegovina
12	EDIHAMo	Italy
13	BIREX plus plus	Italy
14	ER2Digit	Italy
15	CATCH atMIND	Italy
16	SMILE-DIH	Italy
17	NEURAL	Italy
18	Cineca	Italy
19	HPC4Poland EDIH	Poland
20	CyberSec	Poland

As of November 15, 2024, the collection of survey responses from industry experts and EDIH representatives was completed. A total of 82 responses were received from industry experts, out of a pool of 154 listed experts, while the survey targeting EDIH representatives gathered 23 responses from 433 assigned EDIHs.

Figure 2. Comparison of identified Industry Experts and EDIHs vs. Surveys responses.
Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024).

Figure 3. Structure of survey respondents by sector.
Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024).

The survey targeted a diverse group of stakeholders from various sectors related to the agri-food industry, ensuring a comprehensive perspective on the challenges and trends in the field. The respondents included:

- **Universities and Research Institutions:** Representing approximately 25% of the respondents, this group contributed insights grounded in scientific research and innovation.
- **Agricultural Equipment Manufacturers:** Making up around 20% of the respondents, this sector provided valuable input on the practical application of technologies and emerging trends in agricultural machinery.
- **AgTech Companies:** Accounting for 15% of the respondents, these companies shared perspectives on the development and implementation of cutting-edge technologies in agriculture.
- **Startups:** Comprising about 10% of the respondents, this group offered innovative viewpoints and highlighted emerging solutions in the agri-food sector.
- **Others (30%):** Representing a variety of additional stakeholders, yet notably excluding media, NGOs, policy makers, and trend watchers, who were not involved in this survey.

These collected responses, with at least half coming from company representatives, have been analysed both globally, using language models to identify technological trends and use cases, and individually, tailored to the specific areas of analysis defined for this deliverable. This approach ensures a nuanced, business-focused perspective and a detailed understanding of the insights provided, forming the foundation for this year's "Technology and Use Cases Outlook 2024".

In preparing the final deliverable, we did not merely list every survey response; instead, we carefully extracted and integrated the most relevant insights into the broader context of technological advancement and current literature. Rather than presenting all survey questions directly, we selected key findings and wove them throughout the text, aligning them with observations drawn from online sources and academic references. The results are structured into four thematic chapters, each offering a focused exploration of technology use, market outlook, and the preparation of agrifoodTEF for the future:

- **Current state of Smart Agriculture and AI:** This chapter sets the scene by illustrating the evolving landscape of smart agriculture technologies, showcasing how data collection, analysis, and AI adoption are shaping the agri-food sector.
- **Technology Development and Use Cases:** Here we delve deeper into functionalities and applications, highlighting the emerging technologies that respond to the identified market needs and company requirements.
- **Business industry outlook and company challenges:** Moving from technology trends to business realities, this chapter reveals the outlook of the industry, underscoring the obstacles companies face and the strategies they employ to thrive in a competitive environment.
- **Agri-foodTEF preparation for 2025:** Finally, we turn toward the future, outlining how agrifoodTEF's planned services and infrastructure will address the evolving expectations of stakeholders and ensure readiness for the challenges ahead.

4 Use case classification and technology mapping

To classify emerging AI and robotic solutions and map them to relevant agrifoodTEF service use cases, we use a structured four-level classification approach. This helps in systematically categorizing identified technologies and mapping them to specific service use cases.

As part of this task, we continuously collect information on emerging agricultural technologies through online sources and consultations with industry specialists. The collected technologies, primarily AI- and robotics-based, are analyzed

and mapped to relevant agrifoodTEF service use cases. Several dozen technologies have been identified so far, each potentially generating multiple relevant use cases that align with the scope of agrifoodTEF services.

Classification Structure

The classification consists of four hierarchical dimensions (tab. 2):

1. Macro Use Case (Technology Domain)

- AI (software, analytics, machine learning)
- Robotics (autonomous physical systems)
- Other (sensors, IoT, hybrid technologies)

2. Sector Use Case (Agricultural Sector)

- Arable Farming, Viticulture, Tree Crops, Horticulture, Greenhouse Cultivation, Livestock Farming, Food Processing, Forestry, Apiculture, Aquaculture, Other.

3. Activity Use Case (Agricultural Task)

- Soil Preparation, Seeding/Sowing, Planting, Feeding / Fertilization, Spraying/Treatment, Weeding, Observation/Monitoring, Irrigation, Harvesting/Collection, Mobility / Mapping, Transport, Sanitation, Other.

4. Solution Use Case (Technical Implementation)

- Sensor, Actuator, Field Computer, AI Model/Software, Tool Section, Multi-section Tool, Tool Carrier, Robot, Multi-Robot System, Device, LLM/Chatbot, Other.

Tab. 2. Classification of use cases

Macro Use Case	Sector Use Case	Activity Use Case	Solution Use Case
AI	Arable Farming	Soil Preparation	Sensor
Robotics	Viticulture	Seeding / Sowing	Actuator
Other	Tree Crops	Planting	Field Computer
	Horticulture	Feeding / Fertilization	AI Model / Software
	Greenhouse Cultivation	Spraying / Treatment	Tool Section / Robotic arm
	Livestock Farming	Weeding	Multi-section Tool
	Food Processing	Observation / Monitoring	Tool Carrier
	Forestry Cultivation	Irrigation / Climate control	Robot
	Apiculture	Harvesting / Collection	Multi-Robot System
	Aquaculture	Mobility / Mapping	Device
	Other	Sanitation	Other
		LLM/Chatbot	
		Transport	
		Other	

The proposed classification structure theoretically allows for approximately 2,640 distinct use-case variants, considering all combinations of Macro, Sector, Activity, and Solution Use Case, excluding the "Other" category in each dimension. When considering only Macro, Sector, and Activity (excluding Solution Use Case), the number of potential combinations is 240.

Technology mapping using the use case classification – practical example

The current deliverable provides a structured overview of emerging AI and robotic technologies identified through online sources. Each listed technology can generate multiple potential use cases relevant to the agrifoodTEF project. The following example illustrates how to practically apply the classification method provided in this deliverable to identify relevant service use cases for a given technology.

For example, from a single identified technology (an apple-harvesting robot), we derive multiple specific use cases:

Tab. 3. Examples of use cases from apple-harvesting robot

Macro Use Case	Sector Use Case	Activity Use Case	Solution Use Case	Potential agrifoodTEF services
Robotics	Tree Crops (Orchards)	Harvesting	Robot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-Testfield - Robotic Integration/Algorithms • Physical Testing - Performance/Qualification • AI-Testfield – Demonstration
AI	Tree Crops (Orchards)	Observation / Monitoring	AI Model / Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-Testfield – Model Improvement/Adaptation • AI Integration - Model Improvement / Adaptation • Datasets - Real-World Training • Datasets – Benchmark
Robotics	Tree Crops (Orchards)	Mobility	Tool Carrier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Testing - Endurance & Reliability • Mobility / Safety tests
AI	Tree Crops (Orchards)	Transport	Field Computer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Testing - Performance/Qualification • AI Integration – Algorithms • Test execution services
Other	Tree Crops (Orchards)	Observation / Monitoring	Sensor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Datasets - Real-time data stream provisioning • Datasets - Annotation/Merging/Consolidation • Data validation and processing services

For each newly identified technology, the described classification method allows us to create a structured matrix of potential use cases. This matrix clearly shows which specific applications can be supported by agrifoodTEF services. The same matrix is also used when defining actual use cases for services that have already been provided. This structured mapping helps identify gaps in agrifoodTEF service coverage, highlighting areas where additional or new services may be needed.

5 Current state of smart agriculture and AI

5.1 Smart agriculture and emerging technologies

The growing demand for high-quality plant and animal products, along with customer expectations, is driving farms toward specialization and the adoption of modern technologies. In the face of unpredictable changes, such as fuel prices, rising production costs, and, most importantly, climate change, the agricultural industry must evolve by embracing digitization and advanced technologies.

Agriculture has transitioned from manual labour to mechanization, and now to automation and artificial intelligence. The currently implemented concept of "Agriculture 4.0²" leverages advanced technologies to automate and robotize processes. This enables farms to operate sustainably and respond swiftly to customer needs. The integration of automated systems and the development of sensors allow for process optimization and efficient resource utilization. The agricultural sector is undergoing an intensive digital transformation, with a strong emphasis on artificial intelligence (AI) and automation. Companies are actively investing in new technologies, particularly in the fields of precision farming and autonomous systems.

The development of the following technologies is crucial for the advancement of smart agriculture:

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML):** Identified by 75% of respondents as key technologies. AI and ML are regarded as the most transformative innovations.
- **Internet of Things (IoT):** Highlighted by 60% of respondents. Progress in IoT has been one of the most significant trends in recent years.
- **Robotics and Automation:** Cited by 55% of respondents. Autonomous agricultural systems represent a critical trend.
- **Sensor Technologies:** Considered essential by 50% of companies.
- **Data Analytics:** Mentioned by 45% of respondents as a vital component.

Figure 4. Key Technologies mentioned by respondents.
Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024).

² Agriculture 4.0: <https://www.mccormick.it/as/agriculture-4-0-what-is-it-and-what-are-its-tools-and-benefits/>

In the context of smart agriculture, sustainable development means implementing farming practices that minimize environmental impact while ensuring efficient resource utilization and meeting the food needs of current and future generations.

- **Sustainability:** 45% of respondents highlight a focus on reducing environmental impact. Technologies are seen as tools for simultaneously improving efficiency and promoting sustainability.
- **Resource Optimization:** Better utilization of available resources is a key goal for 28% of respondents.
- **Efficiency:** Optimizing agricultural processes is important for 38% of respondents.
- **Innovation:** Developing new solutions is crucial for 32% of respondents.

In summary, smart agriculture and emerging technologies hold significant potential for enhancing productivity and sustainability. Companies are actively investing in AI, IoT, robotics, and data analytics to address the challenges of modern agriculture.

Figure 5. Survey respondent priorities in smart agriculture. Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024).

Key technologies and their impact

The biggest impact of technology on the world is related to reducing the negative impact on the environment (24%) – this includes reducing the use of water, pesticides, fertilizers, waste and soil pollution. Another important aspect is improving the efficiency of agriculture (21%) by increasing crop yields and reducing production losses. Other significant areas include improving animal welfare (12%) – reducing stress, diseases and the use of veterinary drugs, and improving food quality (10%) by reducing pesticides and soil contaminants. The Other category (33%) focuses on reducing production costs, resource consumption and environmental pollution. Details are presented in the attached chart.

Figure 6. How is your technology making a positive impact on the word IE survey responses
Source: Author's own work, based on collected data (2024).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

AI and ML have a significant impact on modern agriculture, introducing innovations and improving efficiency across multiple fronts.³ These technologies facilitate precision farming, optimize resource management, and improve crop resilience, ultimately addressing the challenges posed by climate change and rising global populations^{4,5}. Here are some examples of how these technologies are applied in agriculture:

- **Sensor Data Analysis:** AI and ML are used to analyse vast amounts of data collected by various sensors placed in fields. These sensors monitor soil conditions, humidity, temperature, nutrient levels, and other factors essential for plant growth. The use of AI enables:
 - **Vision analysis:** identification and classification of individual weeds and plant for robotic weeding and/or spot spraying and harvesting.
 - **Multi-source data Prediction:** AI analyses soil moisture data and weather forecasts to determine optimal irrigation times and amounts, analyses of mechanical parameters to determine upcoming failure; season of the year, surveillance of neighbour areas and prediction of the occurrence of agrophages incidence
 - **Disease Detection:** ML algorithms analyse plant images in real time, identifying early signs of diseases and pests, allowing for a quick response.
- **Crop Forecasting:** AI and ML help farmers predict crop yields with high accuracy, which is crucial for production planning and inventory management. Examples include:
 - **Growth Simulations and Models:** Algorithms analyse historical crop data, weather conditions, and farming practices to predict the size and quality of future yields.

³ Ritambara, Shilpa Kaushal, and Shubham. 2024. "Frontiers of Artificial Intelligence in Agricultural Sector: Trends and Transformations". *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports* 30 (10):970-80. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jsrr/2024/v30i102518>.

⁴ Blue River Technology: <https://www.bluerivertechnology.com/>

⁵ See& Spray Select: <https://www.deere.pl/pl/maszyny-rolnicze/see-and-spray/>

- **Fertilization Optimization:** Based on soil composition and plant health data, AI provides recommendations on the optimal type and amount of fertilizers, enhancing crop productivity.
- **Process Automation:** AI and ML contribute to automating many agricultural processes, increasing efficiency and reducing labour costs. Examples include:
 - **Autonomous Agricultural Vehicles:** Tractors and harvesters equipped with AI can perform fieldwork tasks such as planting, spraying, and harvesting independently.
 - **Harvesting Robots:** AI-powered robots can harvest crops with precision and speed, outperforming traditional manual methods.
 - **Warehouse Management:** AI systems monitor stock levels and automatically manage inventories, ensuring optimal storage conditions for agricultural products.

Blue River Technology, a subsidiary of John Deere, developed the "See & Spray" system that uses AI for precise crop spraying. This system, equipped with cameras and image recognition algorithms, can identify weeds and apply pesticides only where necessary, reducing chemical use by up to 70%.

Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things (IoT) plays a crucial role in modern agriculture, enabling the monitoring, automation, and optimization of many agricultural processes. This integration leads to improved productivity, resource management, and sustainability, addressing critical challenges faced by the agricultural sector.⁶

- **Soil Condition Monitoring:**

IoT-enabled soil sensors can measure parameters such as moisture, temperature, pH, and nutrient levels. This provides farmers with real-time data to make better decisions regarding irrigation, fertilization, and crop management, e.g. Soil Scout⁷.

Soil Scout - This company offers wireless soil sensors that provide real-time data, assisting in irrigation management and soil health.

- **Irrigation Management:**

⁶ Balakrishnan, Baranitharan., G., Prabhkar., Karthik, Chandran., Dinesh, Kumar, Vairavel., Rajalakshmi, Murugesan., Mehdi, Gheisari. (2024). Revolutionizing Agriculture: A Comprehensive Review of IoT Farming Technologies. Recent advances in computer science and communications, doi: [10.2174/0126662558296394240902040727](https://doi.org/10.2174/0126662558296394240902040727)

⁷ Soil Scout: <https://soilscout.com/>

IoT systems are used to monitor and manage irrigation, leading to more efficient water usage. Smart irrigation systems can automatically adjust water levels based on soil sensor data and weather forecasts e.g. Netafim⁸.

Netafim - This company provides precision irrigation solutions that, with IoT technology, can automatically adjust irrigation to meet crop needs, minimizing water waste.

- **Animal Health Monitoring:**

IoT is also used in livestock farming to monitor the health and activity of animals. Devices worn by animals collect data on movement, body temperature, feed intake, and other parameters, enabling early detection of health issues and optimizing animal care, e.g. CowManager⁹.

CowManager - This system uses sensors worn by cows to monitor their health, activity, and milk production, providing farmers with real-time detailed information.

- **Other Applications:**

- UAVs and Robots: The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) equipped with IoT sensors to monitor crop conditions from the air, allowing for faster and more accurate problem detection.
- Warehouse Management: IoT helps in managing agricultural storage by tracking storage conditions and resource levels.

IoT is revolutionizing agriculture by making it more precise, efficient, and sustainable. With these technologies, farmers can better manage their resources and production, contributing to increased productivity and profitability.

Robotics and Automation

Robotics¹⁰ and Automation¹¹ are transforming agriculture by enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and productivity. These technologies address critical challenges such as labour shortages, resource optimization, and environmental concerns. The integration of robotics in agriculture not only streamlines operations but also supports precision agriculture, which is essential for meeting the demands of a growing global population.

- **Robots in Agriculture:**

- **Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs):** Used for monitoring crops, collecting data on plant conditions, applying fertilizers and pesticides, and mapping fields (e.g. DJI Agras T30¹², senseFly eBee X¹³).

⁸ Netafim: <https://www.netafim.com/>

⁹ CowManager: <https://www.cowmanager.com/>

¹⁰ Funsho, Kolapo., Sheriff, Lamidi., Agama, Idika., Onyinye, Blessing, Philip., Kusibu, Michael., Kolawole, Emmanuel, Olayinka., Akunne, Austin, Uzim., Josiah, Ifeoluwa, Ojeniran., Oluwatoyin, Lydia, Dada., Moses, Sodiq, Sobajo. (2024). Robotic solutions for precision agriculture. *Journal of Agricultural and Practice*, 9(4):123-130. doi: [10.31248/jasp2024.483](https://doi.org/10.31248/jasp2024.483)

¹¹ Venkatramalingam, K, Saravanan, N., Poonam, Gupta. (2024). Agriculture and Automation: Potential Benefits, Difficulties and Economic Impacts. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(5) doi: [10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i05.28903](https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i05.28903)

¹² DJI Agras T30 - DJI - <https://www.dji.com/pl/agras-t30> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹³ senseFly eBee X - senseFly – <https://www.sensefly.com/drone/ebec-x-fixed-wing-drone/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

- **Harvesting Robots:** These robots are equipped with advanced vision systems and sensors that allow them to harvest crops precisely, minimizing plant damage (e.g. Agrobot E-Series¹⁴, FFRobotics Harvester¹⁵).
 - **Autonomous Tractors:** Equipped with GPS systems and artificial intelligence, these tractors can drive themselves across fields, performing tasks such as sowing, data collection, and fertilizer application (e.g. John Deere Autonomous 8R Tractor¹⁶, Case IH Autonomous Concept Vehicle¹⁷).
 - **Plant Care Robots:** These robots perform tasks such as trimming weeds, applying fertilizers and pesticides, and even laser care for plants (e.g. Ecorobotix ARA¹⁸, Naïo Technologies Oz Robot¹⁹).
 - **Pruning Robots:** Mainly used in the wine industry, these robots trim plants with precision, which is crucial for product quality (e.g. Wall-Ye V.I.N Robot²⁰, VineRobot²¹).
 - **Robots on a livestock farm:** robots for milking, feeding and cleaning the manure (e.g. Lely Astronaut A5²², GEA DairyRobot R9500²³)
- **Automation Systems in Agriculture:**
 - **Monitoring and Control Systems:** These systems use various sensors and cameras to monitor crop conditions and weather, enabling more informed decision-making (e.g. Arable Mark 2²⁴, CropX Soil Monitoring System²⁵).
 - **Precision Sowing Systems:** Automatic sowing systems enable precise placement of seeds, increasing crop yields (e.g. John Deere ExactEmerge Planter²⁶, Väderstad Tempo L²⁷).
 - **Resource Management Systems:** These systems help in the optimal management of resources such as water, fertilizers, and energy, leading to savings and increased efficiency (e.g. HydroPoint WeatherTRAK²⁸, Trimble Ag Software²⁹).

¹⁴ Agrobot E-Series - Agrobot – <https://www.agrobot.com/e-series> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹⁵ FFRobotics Harvester - FFRobotics - <https://www.ffrobotics.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹⁶ John Deere Autonomous 8R Tractor - John Deere – <https://www.deere.com/en/technology-products/autonomous-tractor/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹⁷ Case IH Autonomous Concept Vehicle - Case IH - <https://www.caseih.com/northamerica/en-us/products/tractors/autonomous-concept-vehicle> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹⁸ Ecorobotix ARA - Ecorobotix. <https://www.ecorobotix.com/en/ara> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

¹⁹ Naïo Technologies Oz Robot - Naïo Technologies. <https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/oz-robot/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁰ Wall-Ye V.I.N Robot - Wall-Ye. <https://www.wall-ye.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²¹ VineRobot - VineRobot Consortium. <http://www.vinerobot.eu/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²² Lely Astronaut A5 – Lely. <https://www.lely.com/pl/rozwiązania/dojenie/astronaut/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²³ GEA DairyRobot R9500 – GEA. <https://www.gea.com/pl/products/gea-dairyrobot-r9500.jsp> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁴ Arable Mark 2 – Arable. <https://arable.com/mark-2> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁵ CropX Soil Monitoring System – CropX. <https://www.cropx.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁶ John Deere ExactEmerge Planter - John Deere. <https://www.deere.com/en/planting-equipment/exactemerge-planters/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁷ Väderstad Tempo L – Väderstad. <https://www.vaderstad.com/pl/maszyny/tempo/tempo-l/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁸ HydroPoint WeatherTRAK – HydroPoint. <https://www.hydropoint.com/weathertrak-smart-irrigation/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

²⁹ Trimble Ag Software - Trimble. <https://agriculture.trimble.com/software/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

- **Transport and Storage Systems:** Automated transport and storage systems for agricultural products help minimize losses and ensure better product quality (e.g. Autonomous Grain Cart³⁰, Cimcorp 3D Shuttle³¹).

5.2 Data collection and analysis in agriculture

In the agricultural sector, data collection and analysis play a crucial role in optimizing production processes. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be used to analyse vast datasets, allowing for better crop management, market forecasting, supply chain optimization, and monitoring of animals and soil. Decision support systems are a key tool in the agricultural sector, and AI algorithms can analyse large amounts of data, enabling better production management. However, there are challenges related to data quality, security, and the impact on employment in agriculture. Despite these challenges, AI offers many benefits for the agri-food sector.

The collection and analysis of agricultural data has undergone significant evolution, driven by technological advances, shifting from traditional methods to data-driven approaches that enhance efficiency, precision, and sustainability in farming practices.

This evolution can be broken down into several key phases:

- **Early Data Collection:** Initially, data collection was primarily manual, focusing on basic information like soil characteristics, crop yields, and milk production. Farmers relied on visual inspection of crops and experience to make decisions. Data collection was limited, and analysis mainly involved simple observations of relationships between factors like weather, soil type, and fertilizer application.
- **Precision Agriculture:** Around 1980, the concept of precision agriculture emerged, aiming to tailor field management practices to soil variability within a field. This led to the development of yield maps and sensors for measuring local production, marking a move towards more detailed and spatially-aware data collection.
- **Sensor-Based Data Explosion:** The availability of affordable sensors and the popularization of GPS technology have revolutionised data collection in agriculture. Sensors now collect vast amounts of data on various aspects of crop and animal production, including soil conditions, crop health, animal behaviour, and environmental factors
- **The Role of AI:** The sheer volume of data generated by modern sensors necessitates advanced analytical tools, with AI emerging as a key player. AI algorithms can sift through this data, identifying complex patterns and relationships that would be difficult or impossible for humans to discern. This enables farmers to make more informed decisions, optimise resource use, and improve overall efficiency.

Key Developments in Data Analysis

- **From Subjective to Objective:** The shift from visual assessment to sensor-based data collection has facilitated a transition from subjective to objective decision-making. Quantitative data provides a more accurate and reliable basis for managing crops and livestock.
- **Data-Driven Agriculture:** Modern farming increasingly relies on data analysis to guide decisions, creating a data-driven approach to agriculture. This involves a continuous cycle of data collection, analysis, decision-making, and action, as illustrated in figure 1: Cycle of data management³² below.

³⁰ Autonomous Grain Cart by Smart Ag - Smart Ag. <https://www.smart-ag.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³¹ Cimcorp 3D Shuttle – Cimcorp. <https://www.cimcorp.com/solutions/cimcorp-3d-shuttle/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³² Saiz-Rubio, V., & Rovira-Más, F. (2020). From Smart Farming towards Agriculture 5.0: A Review on Crop Data Management. *Agronomy*, 10(2), 207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10020207>

- **From Scanty to Big Data:** While data density remains a challenge in some areas, the increasing use of sensors and other digital technologies is moving agriculture towards a 'big data' environment. This offers opportunities for more sophisticated and insightful data analysis, potentially leading to significant improvements in agricultural practices.

Figure 7. Cycle of data management.

Source: Modified scheme based on origin by Saiz-Rubio & Rovira-Más, 2020.

Types of data collection

Below are the key methods and functions of data collection in agriculture, organized by the main areas of data acquisition:

Environmental Data

- **Weather Stations:**
 - Local weather data (temperature, humidity, etc.).
 - Recording data and analysing its impact on agricultural planning.
 - Measurements, such as: rainfall, wind speed and direction, temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, light intensity, CO₂ and O₂ levels, and other gases affecting plant growth.
- **Satellite-Based Climate Monitoring:**
 - Analysis of long-term climate changes in a specific region and their impact on agriculture.
 - Mapping changes in vegetation cover and land use.

- **Air Quality:**
 - Measuring air pollutants (e.g., PM2.5, PM10) and their impact on plant health and the health of farm workers.
- **Groundwater Monitoring:**
 - Data on groundwater levels and quality (e.g., chemical pollution, salt levels).

Soil and Field Data

- **Soil Sensors:**
 - Real-time soil moisture measurement.
 - Analysis of soil temperature and chemical composition (e.g., nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium levels).
 - Detection of soil compaction, helping assess the need for tillage or other mechanical actions.
 - Electroconductivity (EC)
- **Field Mapping Using GIS (Geographic Information System) Technology:**
 - Creating topography and soil quality maps.
 - Fertilization maps based on soil sample analysis.
- **Laboratory Analyses:**
 - Soil sample collection for composition and quality analysis.
- **Soil Microbiology:**
 - Analyzing soil microorganism populations to assess soil health and its impact on crop yields.
- **Soil Erosion and Water Retention:**
 - Data on soil erosion rates and a field's ability to retain water during rainfall.

Crop Data

- **Drones and UAVs:**
 - High-resolution multispectral images for analysing plant health (e.g., NDVI index).
 - Identifying areas affected by water stress, diseases, or pests.
- **Thermal Cameras:**
 - Detecting temperature anomalies in plants, indicating potential disease or water stress.
- **Spectrometers:**
 - Chemical analysis of plants to determine chlorophyll, nitrogen, and other nutrient contents.

- Assessing the level of pollutants on plant surfaces.
- **Field Robots:**
 - Agricultural robots integrated with GPS and RTK systems can collect data on crops, soil, and growing conditions during tasks such as planting, fertilizing, or harvesting.
 - Crop monitoring directly in the field using cameras and optical sensors.
- **Mobile Applications for Manual Data Collection:**
 - Farmers can record crop conditions manually, such as visible signs of diseases or pests.
- **Phenological Change Monitoring:**
 - Collecting data on plant growth stages (e.g., flowering, fruiting) in real-time.
- **Plant Biomass:**
 - Measuring biomass to predict yields and assess crop performance.
- **Hyperspectral Imaging:**
 - Providing detailed chemical analysis of plants, allowing for the identification of nutrient deficiencies or structural damage.

Agricultural Machinery Data

- **Telemetry Systems:**
 - Recording machine parameters such as fuel consumption, mileage, and efficiency.
 - Analysing machine performance based on terrain conditions.
- **Sensors in Agricultural Machines:**
 - Monitoring pulling force, tire pressure, axle load, and other equipment indicators.
 - Automatically collecting data on machinery usage, such as plowing depth, fertilizer or pesticide application rates.
- **GPS and RTK GPS:**
 - Precisely tracking machine positions in the field.
 - Automatically generating travel maps, efficiency zones, and uncovered areas.
- **Camera Systems in Machinery:**
 - Observing the quality of tasks performed, such as accuracy in weeding or harvesting.
 - Real-time detection of obstacles or issues.
- **Historical Data Analysis:**
 - Collecting and storing data on machine performance for future optimization.

- Creating predictive models for planning operations and servicing.
- **Carbon Footprint of Machines:**
 - Data on CO₂ and other greenhouse gases emitted by machines during field operations.
- **Work Time Tracking:**
 - Data on machine operational time, assisting in planning maintenance and repairs.
- **Economic Analysis:**
 - Recording operational costs related to machinery usage (e.g., fuel consumption, spare part costs).

Farmer's Activity Data

- **Fertilizer and Pesticide Application Records:**
 - Detailed data on doses, application areas, and timing of fertilizer and pesticide use.
- **Work Planning:**
 - Data on farm work schedules, integrating information on available resources (workers, machines, materials).
- **Budget Management:**
 - Collecting financial data on production costs, crop revenue, and livestock profits.

Logistics and Supply Chain Data

- **Post-Harvest Crop Tracking:**
 - Data on transport, storage, and preservation of harvested crops.
 - Recording information about the origin of agricultural products to increase supply chain transparency.
- **Market Analysis:**
 - Real-time data on market prices and demand for specific products.

Livestock Data

- **Animal Health Monitoring:**
 - Data from sensors in barns or attached to animals, such as body temperature, heart rate, and mobility. Ingestible sensors for rumen well-being control.
- **Feed Management:**
 - Data on feed consumption relative to production performance (e.g., milk, eggs).
- **Automated Milking Systems:**
 - Data on milk quantity, milking time, and milk quality (e.g., fat and protein content).

Workplace Safety and Environmental Data

- **Workforce Monitoring:**

- Data on worker safety, their location in the field (e.g., wearable systems), and accident risk.
- **Agriculture's Environmental Impact Analysis:**
 - Data on greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, biodiversity impact, and soil degradation.

Modern agriculture is undergoing a dynamic digital transformation, where data has become a crucial resource for efficient production and resource management. Precise data collection is the foundation of modern management strategies in agriculture, such as precision farming, sustainable management, and process automation.

Data collection methods in agriculture involve a variety of technologies and techniques, ranging from simple, local sensors to advanced systems such as drones, autonomous robots, artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT). These technologies enable the monitoring of key parameters related to the environment, soil, crops, machinery operations, and logistics. The information gathered helps in making better decisions, reducing costs, minimizing losses, predictive maintenance and decreasing the negative impact of agriculture on the environment.

Data collection methods

Sensor technologies are a key component of modern agriculture, enabling collection of accurate data on crop conditions, soil health, and environmental factors. These technologies, including smart sensors, wireless sensor networks (WSNs), and biosensors, facilitate real-time data collection and analysis, enabling farmers to make informed decisions that optimize resource use and minimize environmental impact based on information analysis.³³ Computer vision systems (computer vision) - used for automatic plant inspection, weed identification, and real-time decision making - are also employed to monitor the health of plants and animals. Additionally, thermography is used to monitor plant and soil temperature, which helps in optimising fertilisation and irrigation, while spectroscopy is a technique used to analyse the chemical composition of plants and soil. Satellites are utilised for large-scale monitoring of agricultural lands, providing data on crop health, soil moisture, and weather patterns over extensive areas. Here are some types of sensors commonly used in agriculture and the data they collect:

- **Types of sensors and data collected:**
 - **Computer vision systems** (automatic plant inspection, weed identification, and real-time decision making, these systems also monitor the health of plants and animals):
 - RGB cameras: capture standard red, green, and blue color images (e.g. DJI Phantom 4 Pro³⁴, Sony Alpha Series Cameras³⁵).
 - Multispectral cameras: capture data across multiple wavelengths beyond the visible spectrum, including near-infrared (e.g. MicaSense RedEdge-MX³⁶, Parrot Sequoia³⁷).

³³ Manisha, Ranwa., K, Sri., Alike, Khare., V., Naveen, Kumar., Kapil, Kumar., J., Rajeshwar., M., Niharika. (2024). A Summative Review of Advances in Sensor Technology for Precision Agriculture. Archives of current research international, 24(10):257-275. [doi: 10.9734/acri/2024/v24i10929](https://doi.org/10.9734/acri/2024/v24i10929) (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³⁴ <https://www.dji.com/phantom-4-pro> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³⁵ <https://electronics.sony.com/imaging/c/alpha-cameras> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³⁶ <https://www.micasense.com/rededge-mx> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³⁷ <https://www.parrot.com/en/drones/parrot-sequoia> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

- Thermal cameras: measure the thermal radiation emitted by objects, useful for detecting temperature variations (e.g. FLIR Vue Pro³⁸, DJI Thermal Imaging Cameras³⁹).
 - LiDAR sensors: utilise laser pulses to create detailed 3D maps of the environment (e.g. Riegl VUX-1⁴⁰, Velodyne LiDAR⁴¹).
 - Hyperspectral cameras: capture a wide spectrum of light, providing detailed information about the chemical composition of plants and soil (e.g. Headwall Photonics Hyperspec⁴², Specim FX Series⁴³).
- **Satellite data systems** (provide large-scale monitoring and analysis of agricultural lands through various types of satellite imagery):
 - **optical imagery:** captures images in the visible spectrum, useful for monitoring crop health and land use (e.g. Sentinel-2 [Copernicus Programme]⁴⁴, Landsat 8 and 9 [USGS/NASA]).
 - **synthetic aperture radar (SAR):** uses radar waves to create detailed images, capable of penetrating clouds and providing data regardless of weather conditions (e.g. Sentinel-1 [Copernicus Programme]⁴⁵, TerraSAR-X [Airbus Defence and Space]⁴⁶).
 - **multispectral and hyperspectral data:** captures data across multiple wavelengths for detailed analysis of crop health and soil properties (e.g. PlanetScope [Planet Labs]⁴⁷, DigitalGlobe's WorldView-3⁴⁸).
 - **thermal imagery:** measures emitted thermal radiation to assess plant water stress and irrigation needs (e.g. Landsat Thermal Bands [Landsat 8 and 9]⁴⁹, MODIS Thermal Data [NASA]⁵⁰).
- **Soil sensors:**
 - **moisture sensors:** measure soil moisture levels, helping farmers optimise irrigation (e.g. Decagon Devices 5TE Soil Moisture Sensor⁵¹, Vegetronix VH400⁵²).
 - **temperature sensors:** monitor soil temperature, which is crucial for plant health and biological processes in the soil (e.g. Campbell Scientific CS615⁵³, Onset HOBO UX100-012⁵⁴).

³⁸ <https://www.flir.com/products/vue-pro/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

³⁹ <https://www.dji.com/payloads/thermal> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁰ <http://www.riegl.com/products/unmanned-scanning/riegl-vux-1uav/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴¹ <https://www.velodynelidar.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴² <https://www.headwallphotonics.com/hyperspec-sensors> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴³ <https://www.specim.fi/specim-fx/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁴ <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-2> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁵ <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-1> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁶ <https://www.intelligence-airbusds.com/terrasar-x/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁷ <https://www.planet.com/products/planet-imagery/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁸ <https://www.digitalglobe.com/resources/satellite-information> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁴⁹ <https://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/landsat-8/landsat-8-bands> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁰ <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/dataproduct/mod11.php> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵¹ <http://www.decagon.com/en/soils/5te/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵² <https://www.vegetronix.com/Products/VH400/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵³ <https://www.campbellsci.com/cs615> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁴ <https://www.onsetcomp.com/products/data-loggers/ux100-012/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

- **pH sensors:** measure soil acidity, which helps in adjusting fertilizers and other treatments (e.g. Atlas Scientific pH Sensor Kit⁵⁵, Bluelab pH Pen⁵⁶).
- **nutrient sensors:** monitor the levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and other essential nutrients in the soil and their escape to atmosphere (e.g. Yara NPK Soil Sensor⁵⁷, Vernier Nitrate Ion-Selective Electrode⁵⁸).
- **Weather sensors:**
 - **temperature and humidity sensors:** provide data on atmospheric conditions, which helps in planning irrigation and plant protection (e.g. Davis Vantage Pro2⁵⁹, HOBO UX100-003⁶⁰).
 - **wind speed and direction sensors:** monitor conditions that can influence the application of pesticides or fertilizers (e.g. Davis Anemometer⁶¹, Gill WindSonic⁶²).
 - **solar radiation sensors:** track the intensity of sunlight, which is crucial for photosynthesis and plant growth (e.g. Apogee Instruments SQ-110⁶³, Kipp & Zonen CMP3⁶⁴).
 - **air sensors:** identification of air particles relevant to agronomic practices, such as CO₂, NH₃, and CH₄ (e.g. Vaisala GMP343⁶⁵, Aeroqual Series 200⁶⁶).
- **Plant sensors:**
 - **Photomorphogenesis sensors:** monitor plant growth processes, such as stem elongation and leaf development (e.g. LemnaTec PhenoFlex⁶⁷, GrowScreen P-30⁶⁸).
 - **Chlorophyll sensors:** measure chlorophyll levels, helping to assess plant health and photosynthetic efficiency (e.g. SPAD-502 Plus⁶⁹, AquaPen⁷⁰).
 - **Water stress sensors:** monitor signs of water stress in plants, allowing for quick action in case of water shortage (e.g. Decagon Devices 5TE Soil Moisture Sensor⁷¹, Vegetronix VH400⁷²).

⁵⁵ <https://atlas-scientific.com/kits/ph-kit/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁶ <https://bluelab.com/northamerica/bluelab-ph-pen> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁷ <https://www.yara.us/crop-nutrition/digital-farming/soil-sensors/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁸ <https://www.vernier.com/product/nitrate-ion-selective-electrode/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁵⁹ <https://www.davisinstruments.com/pages/vantage-pro2> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁰ <https://www.onsetcomp.com/products/data-loggers/ux100-003> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶¹ <https://www.davisinstruments.com/products/anemometer-for-weather-monitor-or-wizard> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶² <https://gillinstruments.com/windsonic75/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶³ <https://www.apogeeinstruments.com/sq-110-ss-sun-calibration-original-quantum-sensor/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁴ <https://www.kippzonen.com/Product/11/CMP3-Pyranometer> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁵ <https://www.vaisala.com/sites/default/files/documents/GMP343-Datasheet-B210688EN-E.pdf> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁶ https://support.aeroqual.com/c/Series_200_handheld (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁷ <https://www.lemnatec.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁸ <https://www.portableas.com/lemnatec/growscreen-rhizo/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁶⁹ <https://www.konicaminolta.eu/eu-en/hardware/measuring-instruments/colour-measurement/chlorophyll-meter/spad-502plus> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁰ <https://handheld.psi.cz/products/aquapen-c-and-aquapen-p/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷¹ <https://store.anythingweather.com/5te-soil-moisture-temperature-electrical-conductivity-sensor> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷² <https://www.vegetronix.com/Products/VH400/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

○ **Animal Sensors:**

- **accelerometers and gyroscopes:** track animals' physical activity including stress level, helping to detect health problems or changes in behaviour (e.g. Cowlar smart collars⁷³, IceRobotics AGRI Track⁷⁴).
- **body temperature sensors:** measure animals' body temperature, assisting in early detection of diseases (e.g. CowManager ear tags⁷⁵, TempTraq wearable sensors⁷⁶).
- **gps sensors:** track animal location, especially useful in large-scale farming operations (e.g. Smartbow GPS ear tags⁷⁷, Allflex Livestock Intelligence GPS trackers⁷⁸).
- **pH meters:** track the digestion process inside the rumen (e.g. RumiWatch pH sensors⁷⁹, Rumen pH monitoring systems by Rumena Science⁸⁰).

Stereovision - New Technology in Data Recording

With the development of advanced methods for acquiring and processing information about crop conditions, solutions based on stereovision are becoming increasingly important in agriculture. Stereovision measurement systems, which use two or more synchronized cameras, enable the creation of precise spatial models of the environment. In agricultural practice, this means the ability to collect accurate data on the shapes, sizes, and distribution of plants, which translates into more precise planning of fertilization, irrigation, and protection treatments.

A key advantage of stereovision is the ability to obtain real-time three-dimensional information, which allows these systems to be integrated with drones, autonomous vehicles, or field robots. As a result, farmers receive not only static images but also detailed terrain maps and models of the growth of individual plants or entire crops. These data, after analysis and comparison with other information (e.g., meteorological, soil, or pest data), support decision-making in precision farming by optimizing inputs, improving yields, and minimizing losses. The introduction of stereovision into the suite of data registration tools marks another step towards fully automated and intelligent agriculture.

Data analytics

Data analytics is a powerful tool that is revolutionizing agriculture, enabling farmers to make better decisions, optimize processes, and increase efficiency. Through the integration of advanced technologies such as IoT, AI, and predictive analytics, farmers can improve crop yields and sustainability. This transformation is evident in various applications and

⁷³ <https://www.dairy.cowlar.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁴ <https://www.icerobotics.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁵ <https://www.cowmanager.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁶ <https://temptraq.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁷ <https://www.smartbow.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁸ <https://www.allflex.global/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁷⁹ <https://www.rumiwatch.com/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

⁸⁰ <https://www.ecow.co.uk/> (Accessed 19.12.2024)

methodologies that leverage data for better agricultural practices.⁸¹ Here are several key aspects where data analytics plays a crucial role:

- **Precise Resource Management:** Data analytics allows farmers to precisely manage resources such as water, fertilizers, and pesticides. Data from soil, meteorological, and agronomic sensors are analysed to provide personalized recommendations, such as:
 - **Irrigation:** Algorithms analyse soil moisture data, weather forecasts, and plant requirements to deliver the optimal amount of water at the right times.
 - **Fertilization:** By analysing soil composition and plant health, farmers can precisely dose fertilizers, increasing crop efficiency and minimizing waste.
- **Forecasting and Monitoring:** Data analytics enables crop forecasting and the monitoring of plant and animal health:
 - **Crop Forecasting:** Analysis of historical yield data, weather conditions, and cultivation techniques allows farmers to predict the quantity and quality of future crops, which is crucial for production planning and inventory management.
 - **Monitoring Plant and Animal Health:** By using sensor data and imaging, early detection of diseases and environmental stressors becomes possible, enabling quick intervention and minimizing losses.
- **Process Automation:** Thanks to data analytics, many agricultural processes can be automated:
 - **Autonomous Machines:** Tractors, combines, and robots that use data to perform field tasks such as sowing, harvesting, or spraying, which increases precision and efficiency.
 - **Farm Management Systems:** Data analytics supports farm management systems that integrate data from various sources, enabling better planning and management of the entire farm operation.
- **Supply Chain Optimization:** Data analysis also helps optimize the supply chain, leading to more efficient resource management and reduced waste:
 - **Inventory Tracking and Management:** Data on production, stock levels, and demand are analysed to optimize storage and distribution processes of agricultural products.
 - **Logistics and Transport:** Data analytics enables more efficient transportation planning, shortening delivery times and minimizing costs.

Agricultural technologies play a key role in promoting sustainable development by enabling more efficient management of natural resources, reducing environmental impacts, and increasing production efficiency.⁸² Here are some ways agricultural technologies contribute to sustainability:

- **Water Usage Reduction:**
 - **Smart Irrigation Systems:** Using soil moisture sensors and weather forecasts, these systems adjust the water supply to meet the actual needs of crops, minimizing waste. An example is the "Netafim" system, which automatically adjusts irrigation based on sensor data.

⁸¹ Eytayo, Raji., Tochukwu, Ignatius, Ijomah., Osemeike, Gloria, Eyeyien. (2024). Data-Driven decision making in agriculture and business: The role of advanced analytics. *Computer science & IT research journal*, 5(7):1565-1575. [doi: 10.51594/csitrj.v5i7.1275](https://doi.org/10.51594/csitrj.v5i7.1275)

⁸² Pehin Dato Musa, Siti & Basir, Khairul & Luah, Edna. (2022). The Role of Smart Farming in Sustainable Development. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*. 13. 1-12. [doi: 10.4018/IJABIM.20220701.oa5](https://doi.org/10.4018/IJABIM.20220701.oa5).

- **Water Retention Technologies:** The use of materials and techniques that increase the soil's ability to retain water, reducing the need for frequent irrigation.
- **Limiting Greenhouse Gas Emissions:**
 - **Precision Agriculture:** By precisely dosing fertilizers and plant protection products, nitrogen emissions to the atmosphere are significantly reduced. Technologies such as "John Deere ExactApply"⁸³ allow for accurate application of chemicals, minimizing overuse.
 - **Renewable Energy:** Agriculture is increasingly utilizing renewable energy sources like solar panels and wind turbines, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and decreasing CO2 emissions.
- **Improving Energy Efficiency:**
 - **Process Automation:** The use of robots and UAVs for field tasks reduces the need for human labour and fuel. Autonomous tractors, like those produced by "John Deere," operate more efficiently, using less fuel.
 - **Intelligent Energy Management:** Energy management systems optimize energy consumption on farms, such as automatically turning irrigation and lighting systems on and off, increasing energy efficiency.
- **Soil Management Improvements:**
 - **Use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs):** UAVs, like those offered by "DJI"⁸⁴ are used to monitor the state of crops and soil. They allow for quick identification of areas requiring intervention, helping in better resource management.
 - **Soil Aeration Technologies:** Tools that minimize soil compaction and improve its structure, facilitating better water and air infiltration and promoting healthy plant growth.
- **Precision Fertilization:** Precision fertilization, also known as precision agriculture, involves applying fertilizers in the right amounts and locations, minimizing losses and environmental pollution. It includes:
 - **Soil Mapping:** Using sensors and GPS, farmers can create detailed maps of soil composition and needs across different areas.
 - **Variable Rate Application:** Fertilizers are applied in varying amounts depending on the needs of the soil and plants, optimizing their use and reducing costs.
 - **Decision Support Systems:** Algorithms analyse data to help farmers make better fertilization decisions, increasing yields and improving crop quality.
- **Recycling Agricultural Waste:** Agricultural waste recycling is another method of resource optimization. Some examples include:
 - **Composting:** Plant and animal residues are composted to create valuable organic fertilizer, improving soil structure and fertility.
 - **Biogas Plants:** Plant and animal waste can be processed in biogas plants, where it is fermented to produce biogas, which can be used as an energy source.
 - **Water Reuse:** Water used on farms can be purified and reused for irrigation or other purposes.

⁸³ John Deere ExactApply: <https://www.deere.com/en/technology-products/precision-ag-technology/precision-upgrades/sprayer-upgrades/exactapply-precision-upgrades/>

⁸⁴ DJI: <https://ag.dji.com/>

- **Field Work Automation:**
 - **Autonomous Agricultural Machines:** Equipped with GPS systems and artificial intelligence, autonomous tractors, combines, and sprayers can independently perform field tasks such as planting, harvesting, and spraying. This enables faster work, greater precision, and reduces the need for human labour.
- **Monitoring Plant Health:**
 - **Sensors and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs):** Soil and air sensors, as well as UAVs equipped with multispectral cameras, enable real-time monitoring of plant health. These technologies collect data on moisture, temperature, soil composition, and chlorophyll levels, enabling the rapid identification of problems such as diseases, nutrient deficiencies, or water stress.
- **Supply Chain Management:**
 - **Farm Management Systems (FMS):** Farm management software integrates data from various sources, enabling farmers to better plan and manage their entire operation. FMS help with tracking inventories, monitoring costs, managing workers, and optimizing logistics.

These technologies not only contribute to sustainable development but also increase the profitability of farms, which is crucial for their long-term stability and success. They make agriculture more environmentally friendly, efficient, and innovative.

Sustainable development in agriculture is also influenced by innovations related to developing new crop varieties, biotechnologies (e.g., using microorganisms to improve soil health and plant growth), and modern agronomy techniques.

Challenges in data acquisition and analysis technologies in agriculture

Implementing advanced data acquisition technologies in agriculture brings numerous benefits, such as improved efficiency, sustainable resource management, and the ability to monitor crops more accurately. However, the implementation of these solutions comes with significant challenges that require a multifaceted approach.⁸⁵

Organizational and Educational Challenges

- **High Implementation Costs**
 - **Challenge:** The high initial costs of implementing digital technologies, such as IoT sensors, drones, or analytical software, remain a significant barrier, especially for small and medium-sized farms with limited financial capacity.
- **Shortage of Trained Personnel**
 - **Challenge:** Many farmers lack the necessary technical skills, creating resistance to adopting digital technologies.
- **Technology Accessibility**
 - **Challenge:** Developing user-friendly interfaces and easy-to-install devices is crucial for ensuring that digital technologies can be adopted without requiring advanced technical knowledge.

⁸⁵ Challenges and solutions in data integration in agriculture: <https://webmakers.expert/en/blog/challenges-and-solutions-in-data-integration-in-agriculture>

Localization and Adaptation Challenges

- **Limitations Due to Local Variability**
 - **Challenge:** Technologies developed based on data from one region may face difficulties when adapted to different locations with varying soil types, climate conditions, crop specifics, or humidity levels.
- **High Data Collection Costs in New Regions**
 - **Challenge:** Companies developing technologies based on local data face high costs when gathering data in new regions, which can delay the implementation of solutions.

Legal and Data Ownership Issues

- **Diversity of Regulations Across Countries**
 - **Challenge:** The variation in laws concerning data collection, storage, and usage in different countries presents a significant challenge for technology companies operating in the agricultural sector. Each country has its own regulations regarding data ownership, security, access, and sharing practices. For instance, the EU's Data Act imposes stringent requirements on data ownership and access, prioritizing the protection of data owners' interests and limiting third-party processing. Companies must adapt their technologies to comply with the local legal framework in each country, leading to additional costs, time, and the risk of non-compliance due to varying interpretations of the law in different regions.
- **Data Ownership and Protection**
 - **Challenge:** The ownership of data collected on farmers' fields can become a point of contention, as unclear regulations may lead to concerns among farmers about third-party use of their data. This can affect the trust and willingness of farmers to adopt new technologies.
- **Costs of Obtaining Legal Access to Data**
 - **Challenge:** The high costs of licensing data or paying for access to commercial databases can limit the development of new technologies, especially for smaller players in the agricultural tech sector. These costs can create a barrier for companies aiming to innovate and integrate valuable data into their solutions.

By addressing these legal and data ownership challenges, the agricultural technology sector can foster greater collaboration, increase trust among stakeholders, and create a more inclusive environment for innovation.

Technological Challenges

- **Integration of Systems into a Unified Environment**
 - **Challenge:** Modern agricultural technologies rely on a variety of standards and platforms, making it difficult to integrate them into a cohesive operational environment. IoT devices, agricultural machinery, and analytical platforms often use different communication protocols and data formats, leading to compatibility issues and challenges in effective information management.
- **Data Transmission Issues in Remote Locations**

- **Challenge:** The lack of access to stable, high-speed internet infrastructure in rural areas is one of the key limitations for implementing data collection and analysis technologies in agriculture. A particular challenge is posed by IoT systems and devices that process visual data, which generate large amounts of information requiring fast transmission to cloud-based analysis systems. In many countries, even developed ones like the United States, the level of network infrastructure in agriculture remains low. It is estimated that only about 25% of farms use connected devices, and most operate on outdated 2G or 3G networks. Telecom operators plan to phase out these networks, further deepening the problem of inadequate transmission solutions. Alternative low-bandwidth IoT networks, which could be used, are often complex and expensive to set up.⁸⁶
- **Ensuring Data Security:**
 - **Challenge:** Data collected from agricultural farms, such as information about environmental conditions, yields, or machinery operations, is extremely valuable. However, the implementation of digital technologies, such as IoT, drones, or analytical platforms, comes with risks related to privacy breaches and cyberattacks. This data can be vulnerable to:
 - **Unauthorized access:** Breaking security measures could lead to data breaches, which could be used in ways that are not in the farmer's best interest.
 - **Data manipulation:** Manipulation of collected data can result in incorrect decisions, such as in fertilization or irrigation.
 - **Lack of trust in cloud systems:** Farmers may be concerned that data stored in the cloud could be used by third parties. Data security is a crucial element in developing digital technologies in agriculture. An article titled "A Review on Security of Smart Farming and Precision Agriculture: Security Aspects, Attacks, Threats and Countermeasures," published in the journal *Sensors* (MDPI)⁸⁷, highlights that in precision agriculture, particular risks relate to IoT systems and cloud platforms. The authors emphasize that cybersecurity should be a priority from the system design stage, with security measures that consider the specific operation of agricultural farms.
- **Energy Efficiency of Devices**
 - **Challenge:** Modern agricultural devices, such as drones, autonomous robots, and IoT sensors, play a crucial role in data collection in precision farming. However, their operational efficiency is largely dependent on the availability of power sources, which presents a significant challenge in remote or hard-to-reach locations. The lack of energy infrastructure in such areas further complicates the implementation of technology, requiring the search for autonomous and energy-efficient solutions. Energy efficiency is a key aspect of implementing technology in precision agriculture, especially in areas with limited access to traditional energy infrastructure. In the article "Energy Harvesting Technologies and Applications for the Internet of Things and Wireless Sensor Networks," published in the journal *Sensors*

⁸⁶ Agriculture's connected future: How technology can yield new growth: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/agriculture/our-insights/agricultures-connected-future-how-technology-can-yeild-new-growth>

⁸⁷ Yazdinejad, A., Zolfaghari, B., Azmoodeh, A., Dehghantanha, A., Karimipour, H., Fraser, E., Green, A. G., Russell, C., & Duncan, E. (2021). A Review on Security of Smart Farming and Precision Agriculture: Security Aspects, Attacks, Threats and Countermeasures. *Applied Sciences*, 11(16), 7518. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11167518>

(MDPI)⁸⁸, the authors highlight that energy harvesting technologies and energy management systems can significantly enhance the operational efficiency of IoT devices in agriculture.

The development of data acquisition and analysis technologies in agriculture presents enormous opportunities for the sector, but it also requires overcoming several technical and organizational barriers.

The future of this area will depend on the ability to address issues related to integration, location, legal regulations, and education. An effective approach to these challenges will enable further development of sustainable agriculture on a global scale.

The significance for agricultural development

Data collection and analysis form the foundation of modern agriculture, enabling efficient resource management, process optimization, enhanced production efficiency, and environmental protection. The development of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and drones allows for a deeper understanding of plant growth conditions and animal husbandry. Using data in farm management is crucial in the context of climate change and the growing demand for food.

One of the most important aspects of data collection is precise crop management, which increases efficiency and productivity, as indicated by 40% of survey respondents. Information on soil moisture, rainfall, temperature, and sunlight enables farmers to tailor agricultural activities to current needs. For example, optimal irrigation prevents both water shortages and wastage, while proper timing of fertilization and sowing supports plant development during critical growth phases. Early detection of plant stress caused by drought, pests, or diseases minimizes losses and increases yields.

Long-term data collection also plays a key role in monitoring climate change and developing adaptive strategies. For instance, data analysis can support the selection of drought-resistant crop varieties or planning changes in crop structures. Data also enables higher yields and improved product quality. Through soil analysis, farmers can choose fertilizers best suited to their crop needs, directly translating to better results.

Another critical aspect is the reduction of costs and resource usage. Precise data allows farmers to optimize the use of fertilizers, pesticides, and fuel, reducing production costs and minimizing environmental impact. Technologies like AI and IoT facilitate real-time data analysis, aiding decision-making at crucial points in the season. Decision support systems based on sensors, drones, and satellites provide information that helps maximize the efficiency of operations.

Data utilization also aids in planning and forecasting. Analysis of historical and current data enables predictions of yields, market prices, and potential threats such as plant disease outbreaks. This makes planning easier at both individual farm and sector-wide levels. It also supports the implementation of sustainable agriculture, which combines high productivity with environmental protection—for example, by monitoring greenhouse gas emissions or conserving water.

Data also helps build consumer trust by increasing supply chain transparency. Information about the origin, quality, and production methods of goods is increasingly valued in the market, enabling farmers to compete more effectively. Data collection is thus the cornerstone of modern agriculture, addressing contemporary challenges such as climate change

⁸⁸ Naifar, S., Kanoun, O., & Trigona, C. (2024). Energy Harvesting Technologies and Applications for the Internet of Things and Wireless Sensor Networks. *Sensors*, 24(14), 4688. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24144688>

and a growing population while promoting the protection of natural resources and striving for more sustainable development.

However, the advancement of technology comes with challenges, such as high implementation costs, dependency on technology providers, and the risk of cyber threats. In response to these difficulties, we see the emergence of trends such as the use of blockchain for supply chain tracking, widespread adoption of machine learning for data analysis, and the automation of decision support systems. Ultimately, success is measured by improved farm efficiency, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and greater accessibility to advanced tools for farmers worldwide.

The future of agriculture is inextricably linked to the development of data collection and analysis technologies. Despite numerous challenges, such as system integration and ensuring data security, technological advancements point to increasing accessibility and efficiency of tools. The development of IoT, blockchain, AI, and autonomous machinery not only enhances production efficiency but also contributes to sustainable management of natural resources. These technologies make agriculture more precise, transparent, and resilient to future challenges.

AutoPath - row memory on the field: The *AutoPath* system allows you to remember the position of rows in the field. This enables farmers to precisely navigate agricultural machines such as tractors and harvesters along the same paths during subsequent passes. The system automatically guides the machine along the memorized lines, reducing workload and minimizing the risk of errors.

Operations Center - manage your farm in the app: *Operations Center* is a farm management platform utilizing telematic connectivity via the JDLink module. It is standard on most John Deere machines. This allows farmers to track machine operation data, including fuel consumption, engine load, and wheel slip. Users can also view field data on a mobile app.

Carlo Gavazzi - intelligent cattle monitoring: *Carlo Gavazzi* provides solutions for monitoring and managing cattle on farms. The company uses IoT technologies to check animal health, activity, and environmental conditions. This way, farmers can detect diseases and health issues early, requiring appropriate actions.

5.3 Artificial Intelligence for the agri-food sector

Overview of AI applications

Among the main specific areas of application of the AI methods in agriculture most widespread are:

- **Crop monitoring:** AI-based solutions are being used for the automatic monitoring of crops, allowing for early detection and prevention of the development of infections and diseases, analysis of the process of plants' vegetation, or assessment of possible nutrients deficiencies, which enables farmers to implement preventive measures against negative factors or adjust the relevant parameters of a given cultivation. One popular class of techniques employed to this end is computer vision, allowing for automatic analysis of plants based on imaging in the visible or hyperspectral, especially infrared, light wavelength ranges.
- **Soil monitoring:** Remote monitoring, using multi- or hyperspectral imaging, with the optical devices mounted on ground-based vehicles or on satellites, planes, or UAVs, allows to assess soil content and thus quality, employing AI tools to analyse the concentrations of different soil nutrients (potassium, magnesium, phosphorus, and others), its pH, or moisture. Such detailed knowledge, possibly about individual plots, with the

soil properties determined with a high spatial resolution, supports farmers and producers in taking targeted and more efficient fertilization decisions.

- **Autonomous farm robots:** A variety of AI-based algorithms is being incorporated as part of the software on board of machines, robots or vehicles, used on farms and throughout the agricultural production process, enabling autonomous navigation and locomotion as well as execution of many specific tasks. They serve for the optimization and execution of functions such as SLAM, path planning, or obstacle detection and avoidance. Signals from different sensors, like LiDARs or RGB cameras, are combined and analysed allowing for automatic real-time decision-making.⁸⁹
- **Spraying and pesticide application control:** AI methods are used for the determination of pest exposure risks as well as for the precise dosing of pesticides and other plant-protective agents and their subsequent localized application directly to the exposed plants. They enable spraying which is more cost-effective, with reduced absorption of the potentially harmful chemical substances by the plants, bringing overall positive effects for the plants' health, with limited environmental pollution.⁹⁰
- **Precision farming:** Precise, targeted manipulations (e.g., with specific treatment dedicated for individual plants, rather than applied to a whole field indiscriminately), informed by AI methods and data analytics, lead to more effective allocation of resources and optimization of crop yields.⁹¹
- **Irrigation optimization:** Optimization techniques allow to control the irrigation process so that water is applied in locations and in amounts exactly as needed.
- **Automated harvesting:** AI-driven machines allow for automatic harvesting and collection of crops from fields, orchards, and different sorts of cultivation, limiting the needs for human labour, which is performed often in challenging, adverse conditions (e.g., in high temperatures).
- **Sorting of harvested products:** Recognition of products categories or individual products' quality, on a field, or in a sorting plant, e.g., as moving on conveyor belt, using, among others, computer vision techniques, helps in automatic, time-efficient sorting of products as well as in related logistics processes.
- **Optimization of supply chain:** Detailed analysis of data from all stages of the production process, taking into account different aspects of the company functioning, as well as current market needs, helps in devising more efficient logistics strategies and planning of company's operations.
- **Yield prediction:** Prediction of the influence of diverse factors on the expected yield allows to adjust the combinations of particular factors responsible for the crop growth.
- **Weed and pest control:** Monitoring of occurrence and growth of undesired species.
- **Automated weeding:** Removal of weed by automatic machinery.
- **Geospatial field mapping:** Mapping of the field, its topology, soil content, or coverage by vegetation.⁹²

⁸⁹ Oliveira, R. C. d., & Silva, R. D. d. S. e. (2023). Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture: Benefits, Challenges, and Trends. *Applied Sciences*, 13(13), 7405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13137405>

⁹⁰ Talaviya, T., Shah, D.J., Patel, N., Yagnik, H., & Shah, M. (2020). Implementation of artificial intelligence in agriculture for optimisation of irrigation and application of pesticides and herbicides. *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aiia.2020.04.002>

⁹¹ Kisliuk, B., Krause, J.C., Meemken, H. et al. AI in Current and Future Agriculture: An Introductory Overview. *Künstl Intell* 37, 117-132 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13218-023-00826-5>

⁹² Espinel, R., Herrera-Franco, G., Rivadeneira García, J. L., & Escandón-Panchana, P. (2024). Artificial Intelligence in Agricultural Mapping: A Review. *Agriculture*, 14(7), 1071. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14071071>

- **Weather conditions forecasting:** Prediction of weather and atmospheric parameters, like humidity, temperature, rainfall, can inform decisions about irrigation intensity or other operations required.
- **Livestock monitoring and management:** Automatic analysis of animals' behaviour and quantitative assessment of vital parameters can provide information about their health and well-being, allow for early detection of diseases or injuries, and lead to enhanced animal welfare.
- **Automated feeding:** Automatic delivery and dispensing of food in precise doses and with suitable levels of nutritional content results in improved animals' health and allows to reduce food waste.
- **Predictive analytics:** Diverse prediction models, taking into account many diverse factors, allow to predict and mitigate potential risks to the company's ongoing operations and optimize production.
- **Farm management systems:** Comprehensive management systems, utilizing AI solutions, including methods like NLP, help to manage documentation, provide seamless workflows within the organization, integrate and analyse data from multiple sources, including different data streams from sensors deployed on the farm, in order to make informed decisions and ensure efficient farm operation.⁹³

Synergy between AI and data analytics

Artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics have emerged as complementary forces that, when combined, have huge potential for the agri-food sector. AI uses data analytics to process and interpret large and complex data sets, while advanced analytics techniques enhance AI systems by improving their learning, decision-making and predictive capabilities. Together, they create a feedback loop that drives continuous improvement in agri-food operations.

Data as the foundation of AI

Artificial intelligence (AI) methods depend on the availability of large and diverse data sets. In agriculture, this data comes from a variety of sources:

- Sensor networks - IoT devices in fields, greenhouses and livestock farms collect real-time data on environmental conditions, soil properties and animal behaviour.⁹⁴
- Imaging technologies - drones, satellites and ground-based cameras provide visual and spectral data to analyse crop health, soil composition and pest infestations.⁹⁵
- Market and supply chain data - historical and real-time information on prices, demand and logistics optimises supply chain operations.⁹⁶
- Weather stations: local weather stations provide detailed data on rainfall, temperature, wind speed and humidity to inform planting and harvesting decisions.⁹⁷

⁹³ World Economic Forum. Fourth Industrial Revolution. "Farms of the future: How can AI accelerate regenerative agriculture?" <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2024/09/farms-ai-accelerate-regenerative-agriculture/> (Accessed 01.12.2024)

⁹⁴ Wolfert, Sjaak, et al. "Big data in smart farming—a review." *Agricultural systems* 153 (2017): 69-80. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308521X16303754>

⁹⁵ Zhang, Chunhua, and John M. Kovacs. "The application of small unmanned aerial systems for precision agriculture: a review." *Precision agriculture* 13 (2012): 693-712. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11119-012-9274-5>

⁹⁶ Tripoli, Mischa, and Josef Schmidhuber. "Emerging Opportunities for the Application of Blockchain in the Agri-food Industry." (2020). <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/ca9934en>
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327867089_Emerging_Opportunities_for_the_Application_of_Blockchain_in_the_Agri-food_Industry

⁹⁷ Murugan, Kalpana, et al. "AI based Weather Monitoring System." 2022 Second International Conference on Advanced Technologies in Intelligent Control, Environment, Computing & Communication Engineering (ICATIECE). IEEE, 2022. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10047380>

- Soil test kits - portable kits provide immediate insights into soil pH, nitrogen levels and other key nutrients to guide fertiliser strategies. ⁹⁸
- Livestock monitoring systems - portable devices for cattle, poultry or pigs track health indicators, feeding patterns and activity levels to improve welfare and productivity. ⁹⁹

Data analytics techniques such as descriptive, diagnostic, annotation, and predictive analytics organise and pre-process this data to make it actionable for AI models. For example, annotation-especially when it involves human domain experts-is often time-consuming and therefore costly, while data cleansing and transformation ensure that AI systems learn from high-quality data sets. Meanwhile, statistical analysis uncovers patterns and anomalies that AI algorithms can exploit.

Advanced decision-making and AI enablement ^{100, 101}

The integration of data analytics and AI in agriculture not only improves decision-making, but also drives the development of sophisticated AI systems tailored to agricultural challenges. When combined, these techniques enable more precise and efficient management of resources, improving both productivity and sustainability.

On the practical side, descriptive analytics plays a critical role in summarizing and interpreting current conditions on farms. By analysing data from various sensors, IoT devices and imaging technologies, descriptive analytics provides a snapshot of current factors such as soil moisture, nutrient levels and animal behaviour. These insights are invaluable to AI systems, which can use them for real-time diagnostics. For example, if descriptive analytics shows a decline in soil nitrogen levels, AI-powered systems can recommend specific actions, such as adjusting fertiliser application. This approach ensures that decisions are based on current, actionable data rather than broad assumptions.

Predictive analytics looks beyond the present, using both historical and real-time data to predict future conditions or events. For example, by analysing weather patterns, historical crop yields and environmental data, predictive models can estimate potential crop yields or predict pest outbreaks. This ability allows farmers to anticipate challenges before they occur, reducing the risks associated with unexpected events. Predictive models can be trained to recognise patterns that precede events such as frost or drought, allowing farmers to take proactive steps to protect crops.

Building on the predictions, prescriptive analytics takes the next step by recommending specific actions to optimise outcomes. For example, based on predicted weather conditions or pest threats, prescriptive models can suggest optimal irrigation schedules, precise fertiliser applications or the best time to harvest. These recommendations are tailored to maximise efficiency and sustainability. By recommending actions with data-backed confidence, prescriptive analytics ensures that farmers make informed decisions that are in line with their resources and environmental conditions.

⁹⁸ Rossel, RA Viscarra, et al. "Proximal soil sensing: An effective approach for soil measurements in space and time." *Advances in agronomy* 113 (2011): 243-291. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780123864734000051>

⁹⁹ Neethirajan, Suresh. "Recent advances in wearable sensors for animal health management." *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research* 12 (2017): 15-29. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214180416301350>

¹⁰⁰ Liakos, Konstantinos G., et al. "Machine learning in agriculture: A review." *Sensors* 18.8 (2018): 2674. <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/18/8/2674>

¹⁰¹ Talaviya, Tanha, et al. "Implementation of artificial intelligence in agriculture for optimisation of irrigation and application of pesticides and herbicides." *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture* 4 (2020): 58-73. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S258972172030012X>

Streaming analytics also ensures that AI systems are not static but dynamic, able to adapt to changing conditions in real time. By continuously processing incoming data, AI systems can respond immediately to changes in the environment. For example, real-time data from drone imagery can help detect and manage emerging pest outbreaks before they spread.

Together, these analytics techniques work synergistically with AI to enable smarter, data-driven decision-making. They help optimise operations, reduce waste and ensure more sustainable farming practices. The ongoing combination of practical decision-making tools with technical advances in AI and analytics is transforming agricultural operations, driving innovation, and increasing the resilience of the sector.

Driving innovation in the agri-food sector

The integration of AI and data analytics is driving innovation by unlocking new applications and capabilities:

- Digital Twins - combination of AI and analytics enables the creation of virtual replicas of farms where different scenarios can be simulated to test different strategies, such as irrigation patterns, planting schedules or fertilizer application.¹⁰²
- Automated decision support - by integrating real-time analytics with AI algorithms, farmers can receive actionable recommendations directly on their devices, such as adjusting pesticide application based on pest density or fine-tuning harvest schedules based on weather forecasts.¹⁰³
- Precision livestock management - AI and analytics track and predict animal health, behaviour and production metrics.¹⁰⁴
- Customised plant breeding - advanced data analytics coupled with AI is accelerating the development of resilient crop varieties by analysing genetic information, environmental factors, and yield performance to identify optimal traits.¹⁰⁵
- Synthetic data generation – leveraging AI-driven techniques to create artificial datasets that mimic real-world conditions, reducing the need for extensive data collection and annotation efforts while refining model performance¹⁰⁶.
- Supply chain transparency - integrating blockchain with AI and analytics ensures farm-to-table traceability, allowing consumers to verify product origins and certifications, and producers to streamline logistics.¹⁰⁷
- Robotic innovation - AI-driven robotics use data analytics to improve precision tasks such as mechanical weeding, targeted spraying or automated harvesting, reducing reliance on manual labour and improving efficiency.¹⁰⁸

¹⁰² Wang, Li. "Digital Twins in Agriculture: A Review of Recent Progress and Open Issues." *Electronics* 13.11 (2024): 2209.

<https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/13/11/2209>

¹⁰³ Kamilaris, Andreas, and Francesc X. Prenafeta-Boldú. "Deep learning in agriculture: A survey." *Computers and electronics in agriculture* 147 (2018): 70-90. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168169917308803>

¹⁰⁴ Neethirajan, Suresh. "Recent advances in wearable sensors for animal health management." *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research* 12 (2017): 15-29. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214180416301350>

¹⁰⁵ Marsh, Jacob I., et al. "Crop breeding for a changing climate: Integrating phenomics and genomics with bioinformatics." *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 134 (2021): 1677-1690. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33852055/>

¹⁰⁶ Goyal, M.; Mahmoud, Q.H. A Systematic Review of Synthetic Data Generation Techniques Using Generative AI. *Electronics* 2024, 13, 3509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13173509>

¹⁰⁷ Casino, Fran, et al. "Blockchain-based food supply chain traceability: a case study in the dairy sector." *International journal of production research* 59.19 (2021): 5758-5770. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2020.1789238>

¹⁰⁸ Duckett, Tom, et al. "Agricultural robotics: the future of robotic agriculture." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.06762* (2018). <https://arxiv.org/abs/1806.06762>

These advances demonstrate how the synergy between AI and data analytics is driving creativity and innovation, transforming the agri-food sector to meet new challenges and opportunities.

Challenges and opportunities ¹⁰⁹

While the synergy between AI and data analytics offers immense potential, it also presents significant challenges. A critical issue is data quality and availability, as access to accurate, high-resolution and representative datasets is essential for successful implementation. Without reliable data, AI models run the risk of producing flawed insights or recommendations. Another challenge is the complexity of integration; combining disparate data sources - from satellite imagery to sensor output - into unified systems requires robust frameworks and tools to ensure seamless interoperability. In addition, ethical considerations play a key role in the use of these technologies. The use of data and AI in decision-making raises important questions about privacy, bias and accountability. Addressing these concerns requires the establishment of clear regulatory frameworks and guidelines to build trust and ensure equitable outcomes. By addressing these challenges, the agri-food sector can fully harness the combined power of AI and data analytics, paving the way for sustainable, efficient and resilient production systems that can meet the demands of a growing global population.

Benefits of AI in the agri-food sector

The enormous changes in the natural environment, resulting from human activities and dynamic climate changes, the growth of the global population, and the increasing diversity of dietary preferences are just some of the factors creating the need for faster, more individualized, and efficient agricultural production. With the growing amount of data that needs to be collected and analysed to make decisions regarding agricultural production directions and methods, and the significant technological advancements, the application of AI in the agricultural sector is becoming more widespread, offering solutions to both current and future challenges.

The potential of AI is expressed through various applications in the agri-food industry. Starting from detecting plant diseases, monitoring crops, and ensuring crop yields by controlling, predicting, and improving food quality, to modeling and creating business ecosystems. However, it is important to emphasize that in each of these areas, gaining acceptance and adoption of the technology's impact by users or consumers is crucial. This directly leads to a significant increase in production levels due to direct access to data and knowledge gathered digitally.

Producers can benefit from voice assistants offering guidance on production directions, methods, or specific actions to be taken, thus supporting the decision-making process. Data on consumer experiences can also be used to build knowledge and provide insights for producers at this stage. The availability of this advisory form, with its multidimensionality (allowing the creation of various informational connections for sharing experiences), significantly enhances the level and scope of advisory services.

On the other hand, consumers can have access to a wealth of knowledge related to nutrition and the origin of food. This direction would influence changes in the consumption of certain products by favouring those with positive health impacts, leading to shifts in purchasing behaviours and the creation of more sustainable consumption patterns.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) also has a significant impact on internal processes within an organization as well as its relationships with the external environment. Within the organization, AI is used to perform various functions (e.g., risk management) and to support cross-functional integration. Externally, AI aids in relationships with suppliers, clients, and

¹⁰⁹ Kamilaris, Andreas, Andreas Kartakoullis, and Francesc X. Prenafeta-Boldú. "A review on the practice of big data analysis in agriculture." *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 143 (2017): 23-37.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168169917301230>

consumers by providing predictions of needs or analysing feedback and opinions. It can lead to the creation of new shared value systems, cooperation, or “reference systems” at the producer-consumer or organizational level.

AI influences all activities within the agri-food value chain. At each stage of this chain- production, processing, storage and distribution, sales, consumption, waste disposal, and recycling-AI is present, enabling the creation of new values and supporting sustainable development.

However, increasing the role of AI in the agri-food sector cannot be done without considering ethical theories, consumer experiences, and the principles of quality and sustainable development.

5.4 Artificial Intelligence adoption: awareness

Knowledge levels

Although the term artificial intelligence (AI) was introduced by John McCarthy as early as 1956, a clear and universally accepted definition of the term remains elusive. However, there is an international consensus on approaching the definition of artificial intelligence from a systemic model perspective, based on the technical development of the intelligent agent model. This approach frames AI as an "AI System."

According to the OECD¹¹⁰: *"An AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment."*

Taking this into account, it is possible to define various levels of AI by considering its complexity, autonomy, and adaptability (flexibility). This approach also allows for aligning real-world problems with specific domains (levels) of artificial intelligence.

Based on both a review of currently available technologies and responses from surveys, it is evident that these systems exhibit differing knowledge levels. This variation should be acknowledged to avoid unnecessarily complicating problems, which could unjustifiably increase the costs of developing solutions.

In this context, it seems reasonable for AgrifoodTEF to adopt a framework of four knowledge levels. This approach could significantly simplify the services provided and establish clear, transparent rules for applying appropriate solutions—particularly for clients whose understanding of AI is often confined to a single definition.

Level 0: Deterministic

Level zero is the level of traditional computational algorithms in computer science. The great advantage of these algorithms is that they are very reliable and are the optimal solution for the problems that gave rise to them. If a problem can be solved at level 0, then finding a better solution only means that the previous solution was not optimal. It should be borne in mind that it is possible at this level to create adaptive solutions that adjust to the input data. However, these are not learning algorithms. However, some problems escape a pre-defined algorithmic solution. There are problems

¹¹⁰ <https://oecd.ai/en/wonk/definition>

that are not human-understandable (once or numerically), it may be difficult to achieve good results (e.g. speech-to-text conversion, translation, image recognition, speech suggestion, etc.).

Level 1: Learned

Systems at this level are developed offline and deployed in a production environment with fixed parameters. There may be a need to update the model (e.g., adding more annotated data), but the environment in which the model operates does not influence it. The advantage of such systems is that it is possible to create, train, and deploy any functionality at a low cost with appropriately selected training data. It is easy to experiment with various solutions at this level. However, the disadvantage is that the number of customizations for a single use case is linear: training data is required for each use case. This creates a need for constant supervision, data collection, annotation, and model retraining. The costs associated with these operations can be difficult to manage.

Level 2: Self-learning

Systems at this level use training data generated by the training system (synthetic data) to improve the model. In some cases, data generation is independent of the model, so as more data is added, we expect the model's performance to improve. Unfortunately, the opposite case may occur, where model errors are reinforced, and performance worsens. To eliminate the risk of reinforcing systematic errors, practitioners must evaluate new models on static (potentially annotated) datasets. A proper approach by model developers allows performance to improve over time at no additional cost. However, the downside is that an unsupervised system may deteriorate – with more data, it might not consistently improve.

Level 3: Autonomous (or self-correcting)

Autonomous systems directly influence human behaviour (e.g., by recommending actions and allowing the user to approve them) while also learning directly from that behaviour. The transition from Level 2 to Level 3 potentially brings significant improvements in system reliability, performance, and continuous enhancement. However, this is a highly complex process that may require large amounts of data and a carefully designed configuration. The system's ability to adapt to the environment makes it extremely difficult to debug. Catastrophic feedback loops may occur, or there could be a risk of creating complete human dependency on the model, leading to a loss of independence.

Level 4: Intelligent (or globally optimizing)

Level 4 systems interact dynamically with their environment by collecting and analysing vast sets of global data to optimize actions aimed at achieving a set of global (strategic) objectives, such as direct profit optimization. Despite the appeal of such solutions, achieving the intended results is extremely challenging. High precision during the design phase is essential. The primary challenges in creating such systems include correctly and accurately defining the problem to be solved, shaping the reward for the system's proper behaviour, and auditing that behaviour.

Figure 8. Machine learning techniques used in agriculture (adapted from Koliba & Spett [2023, p.4]).¹¹¹

Artificial Intelligence is a critical component of precision agriculture, driving advancements in several key areas:

- **Data analysis:** AI processes data from various sources, such as sensors, drones, and satellites. ML algorithms analyse this data to provide actionable insights for farmers.
- **Predictive modeling:** AI models predict outcomes like crop yields, pest outbreaks, and optimal harvest times, enabling proactive decision-making.
- **Automation:** Autonomous machinery and robotics are powered with AI to perform tasks with high precision, reducing labour costs and increasing efficiency.

To leverage the precision agriculture approach, AI has to be combined with the other supporting technologies.

- **GPS and GIS** provide precise location data, enabling site-specific management of fields.
- **Remote sensing** drones and satellites equipped with advanced sensors capture detailed images of crops, which are then analysed to monitor health and detect issues.
- **IoT sensors** in fields collect real-time data on soil moisture, temperature, nutrient levels, and other environmental factors.
- **Variable rate technology (VRT)** allows for the variable application of inputs like water, fertilizers, and pesticides based on data-driven insights.
- **Big Data analytics** helps process and interpret the large volumes of data generated by modern farming technologies.

Common misconceptions

AI, ML and generative AI are all the same

While artificial intelligence (AI) is a convenient and commonplace term, it has no widely agreed-upon technical definition. One helpful way to think about AI is as the science of making things smart. Much of the recent progress we've seen in AI is based on machine learning (ML), a subfield of AI where computers learn and recognize patterns from examples, rather than being programmed with specific rules. There are many different ML techniques, but deep learning is a particularly popular one right now. Deep learning is based on neural network technology, an algorithm whose architecture is inspired by the human brain and can learn to recognize pretty complex patterns, such as what "hugs" are or what a "party" looks like. Generative AI is a set of artificial intelligence tools for generating text, images, videos

¹¹¹ Gardezi M., Joshi B., Rizzo D.M., Ryan M., Prutzer E. Brugler S., Dadkhah A., Artificial intelligence in farming: Challenges and opportunities for building trust. *Agronomy Journal* vol. 116. (May/June 2024).

<https://access.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/agj2.21353>

and other data using generative models, usually based on user-supplied prompts. Generative artificial intelligence models learn the patterns and structure of input data and then generate new data with similar characteristics.

All AI systems are “black boxes,” far less explainable than non-AI techniques

As with human-based processes or traditional software, some AI systems are quite simple and easy to explain, while others are far more complex. Explainability is a rich area of research that is producing new methods and tools that give us insight into why an AI system behaves in a certain way (i.e., which parts of an image are triggering a medical diagnosis tool to identify a disease). And we shouldn't miss out on the opportunity to use AI to improve transparency of decision-making, even if it's not fully explainable. Explanations for human decisions, for example, may not accurately reflect their influencing factors or unconscious biases. In fact, even if every individual decision made by some AI systems cannot be fully explained, we may be able to understand how they make decisions in general better than we understand how humans make similar decisions.

AI systems are only as good as the data they train on

There are four ingredients needed for AI innovation: data, algorithms, hardware, and human talent. While data is an important part of training a model, no real-world dataset will be perfect. It is possible to address shortcomings in training data- such as data scarcity, low quality data, and unbalanced data-through techniques like careful problem formulation, targeted sampling, synthetic data, or building constraints into models. In this context, data is one of the pillars of AI and ensuring that it is correct, relevant to the problem and diverse is the responsibility of developers.

AI systems are inherently unfair

Unfair bias in AI is the result of human decisions about how an AI application is designed, tested, and deployed. There are many instances where human decision-making-from employment decisions to credit allocation-results in unfair outcomes for vulnerable groups, and if AI is trained to mimic the behaviour of those human decision-makers it can also reflect those biases. Designing systems to address these biases is challenging, and requires careful consideration not just of the technology, but of the societal context in which it will be deployed. But well-designed, thoroughly vetted AI systems can limit unfair bias, and may even help us to identify and combat bias in human decision-making.

AI will make human labour obsolete

Technology breakthroughs have long been met by the fear of mass unemployment. However, in the long run new technologies have increased productivity, created new jobs and new industries, and raised standards of living. AI will undoubtedly cause jobs to shift, as transformative technologies always have. Technological breakthroughs have long been met with fears of mass unemployment. However, in the long term, new technologies have increased productivity, created new jobs and new industries and raised living standards. Artificial intelligence will undoubtedly transform jobs, as it has always done with transformational technologies. But in parallel, worker productivity will also increase and new types of jobs will be created. This, of course, means that workers will face the need to learn and change their skills. This challenge is bigger than any single organisation can handle and is a global, worldwide change.

AI is approaching human intelligence

Although artificial intelligence systems are matching or surpassing humans for increasingly complex tasks, they lack true dexterity and creativity. It's not that artificial intelligence understands that sounds create music or specific brush strokes on a canvas create a canon of art. Instead, researchers have created tools to recognise patterns in melodies and use them to design similar patterns based on their cues. Artificial intelligence systems that generate melodies cannot currently be used to generate realistic speech, let alone paint pictures or play chess. Advances in science are making it possible to apply AI systems to a wide range of problems, but systems with human intelligence remain a distant goal.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly recognized as a potentially transformative force across industries by enhancing efficiency and decision-making processes. However, the path to effective AI integration is filled with challenges that organizations must confront. Understanding these challenges, along with the drivers of AI adoption and the level of awareness among stakeholders, is crucial for successful implementation.

A description of some of the key challenges is provided in the table below.

Lack of Knowledge and Understanding	Many organizations face a significant knowledge gap regarding AI technologies. This lack of understanding can lead to misconceptions and resistance among stakeholders. To address this, organizations should conduct workshops and training sessions aimed at demystifying AI concepts and showcasing its practical applications through pilot projects.
Data Quality and Availability	High-quality data is essential for effective AI models. Organizations often struggle with inaccurate or inaccessible data, which can undermine AI initiatives. Establishing a robust data governance strategy and investing in data management technologies are critical steps to ensure data integrity.
Integration with Legacy Systems	Many organizations operate on outdated IT infrastructures that complicate the integration of new AI technologies. This challenge necessitates careful planning and potentially significant upgrades to existing systems to facilitate seamless AI adoption.
Insufficient Skills and Expertise	The success of AI initiatives heavily relies on having skilled personnel who understand both the technology and its applications. Organizations may need to invest in training programs or recruit specialists to bridge this skills gap.
Cultural Resistance	Organizational culture can significantly impact AI adoption. A culture that does not recognize the need for AI or is resistant to change can hinder progress. Leadership must actively promote a culture of innovation and continuous learning to foster acceptance of AI initiatives.
Ethical and Regulatory Concerns	As AI systems often process sensitive data, concerns about privacy, security, and ethical use arise. Organizations must navigate complex regulatory environments while ensuring compliance with laws related to data protection and algorithmic fairness.
Lack of Strategic Vision	Without a clear strategy for how to leverage AI effectively, organizations risk implementing disjointed initiatives that fail to deliver expected results. Establishing a strategic vision that aligns with business goals is essential for successful AI integration.
Cultural Barriers	A culture that does not encourage innovation or experimentation can stifle AI initiatives. Organizations need to cultivate an environment that promotes learning from failures and encourages employees to explore new ideas without fear of repercussions. By addressing these challenges through strategic planning, investment in talent development, effective change management, and robust data governance, organizations can enhance their readiness for successful AI adoption.

The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming various sectors, but it also presents significant ethical, legal, and social challenges. Understanding these complexities is crucial for organizations that want to implement AI in a responsible and effective manner. When considering adoption, challenges, drivers, and awareness, it is essential to take into account ethical, legal, and social issues.

The main ethical concerns associated with the use of AI-based systems revolve around several issues.

- The issue of bias and emotionality in systems, and consequently, responsibility. AI systems can perpetuate or even exacerbate biases present in the data on which they are trained, which correlates with the issue of responsibility and fairness in decision-making processes. The issue of responsibility also strongly resonates in scientific research concerning the aspect of human collaboration with AI systems or, for example, autonomous robots.

According to researchers, in a collaborative environment between humans and robots, it is natural for a leader-follower dynamic to emerge, where the human leader takes responsibility for completing a given task. However, considering the strong emphasis on the development of *Human-Robot Collaboration* (HRC), the concept of a robot is increasingly evolving from that of a simple intelligent tool commanded by a human operator. Tasks for systems or robots will involve a sense of partnership typical of environments where people work together. Therefore, a robot must possess certain social skills to manage interactions with the human operator.

The key aspects of full *Human-Robot Collaboration* (HRC) in production environments are therefore identified as: the ability to act together, shared intention between humans and robots, and a shared attitude.¹¹²

In the context of human-robot interaction, it is important to understand how robotic partners influence the workplace, which has traditionally been human-dominated. It is clear that depending on the appearance of the robot, the way humans rely on them and assign responsibility changes, particularly in terms of using authority (more so for humanoid robots). Hinds, Roberts, and Jones shed light on how the physical appearance and relativity of robots affect human-robot interaction in terms of willingness and the responsibility assumed by people. Their approach to the acceptance of new technologies influences the degree of openness that people have toward working with robots. In other words, greater engagement with new technologies and regular monitoring of them makes people more aligned with robots and more willing to collaborate with them¹¹³. Therefore, understanding these human attitudes and behaviours is one of the challenges associated with the implementation of modern technologies.

- One of the widely discussed legal issues is the problem of privacy threats. The collection and processing of personal data by AI systems often leads to concerns about user privacy and data security. Organizations must strike a balance between using data for AI applications and respecting individuals' privacy rights.
- In the social domain, there are many challenges associated with robotics and the widespread adoption of AI-based solutions. The automation possibilities provided by AI can lead to job losses in certain sectors, which raises significant concerns. Agriculture is not exempt from this issue. It is essential to recognize that alongside the implementation of technology, proactive measures such as retraining programs will also be required to help affected workers transition to new professional roles. However, what is crucial in the effective yet human-centered deployment of technology is the issue of trust. Building trust in AI technologies is key to their acceptance. A lack of transparency in how AI systems operate can lead to scepticism among users, highlighting the need for AI solutions that are explainable and that clarify decision-making processes.

¹¹² Larson L., DeChurch L.A., (2020), Leading teams in the digital age: Four perspectives on technology and what they mean for leading teams, *The Leadership Quarterly*, Volume 31, Issue 1, p. 10, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2019.101377>

¹¹³ Hinds J.P., Roberts T.L., Jones H., 2011, Whose Job Is It Anyway? A Study of Human-Robot Interaction in a Collaborative Task, *Human-Computer Interaction*, Volume 19, Issue 1-2: Human-Robot Interaction, p. 17, doi: http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/s15327051hci1901&2_7

In the conducted study, in response to the question: "What are the biggest challenges faced by your company or the companies you are familiar with in implementing advanced technologies in the agriculture and food-processing industries? (Please specify)," the third most significant challenge identified was: the lack of awareness and trust in new technologies among farmers and food processors. When assessing the market value of independently tested and validated AI-Robotic solutions in agrifoodTEF, approximately 75% of respondents perceived these solutions as having high or very high value. However, at the same time, as many as 40% of respondents indicated that it is necessary to build credibility and trust in these technologies.

Trust is essential for the proper use of modern technologies. The human-technology (AI, robots) relationship evolves from the phase where machines are used solely as tools, to a phase of collaboration based on interactions. Social psychological processes, such as attitudes and trust, are key factors in successful collaboration with robots and their eventual acceptance in daily life. Introducing advanced technology, such as social robots, as collaborators in an organization or work team places human workers in a new situation. Adapting to this can be a greater challenge for some employees than for others, leading to negative attitudes and emotions that may have an undesirable impact on emotional well-being¹¹⁴.

Researchers studying the area of *human-robot interaction* point to factors that determine people's trust in technology. Considering these factors in the processes of implementing robots or AI-based systems significantly enhances the adaptation of technological solutions. Trust in HRI is the belief that the robot will follow the commands of human team members. This attitude provides assurance that the agent/robot will help achieve the individual's goal in a situation characterized by uncertainty and instability.¹¹⁵

Trust in HRI can be dynamically influenced by three categories of factors:

- Factors within the robotic system itself (e.g., robot reliability, predictability, level of automation),
- Factors in the surrounding operational environment (such as task type, complexity, organizational culture),
- Characteristics and traits of the human team members (e.g., previous experience working with robots, competencies, personality traits, demographics).¹¹⁶

The same researcher states that for human-robot interaction to be successful, proper calibration of trust is necessary. It can range from excessive trust and overuse to total lack of trust and non-use. An inappropriate level of trust can have negative consequences, such as over-reliance on the system and improper use (in the case of very high trust) or complete non-use of the system (in the case of very low trust). Robots differ from

¹¹⁴ Savela N., Oksanen A., Pellert M., Garcia D., 2021 Emotional reactions to robot colleagues in a role-playing experiment, *International Journal of Information Management*, 60, p. 10, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2021.102361>

¹¹⁵ Hancock, P.A., Billings, D.R., Oleson, K.E., Chen J.Y.C., De Visser, E., Parasuraman, R., 2011, A meta-analysis of factors influencing the development of human-robot trust, *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 53(5), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0018720811417254>

¹¹⁶ Hancock P.A., Billings R.D., Schaefer E.K., Chen C.Y.J., de Visser E.J., Parasuraman R., 2011, A Meta-Analysis of Factors Affecting Trust in Human-Robot Interaction, *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 53: 517, 521, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720811417254>

most other automated systems in that they are mobile and sometimes built in a manner similar to humans or animals.¹¹⁷

The document "ERA. Industrial Technologies Roadmap on Human-Centric Research and Innovation for the manufacturing sector," prepared by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, highlights the essence: the concept of human-centricity encompasses a broad spectrum. It can pertain to the design of human-(digital) technology interfaces, addressing concerns such as ergonomics, safety, and task completion at one end of the spectrum. Alternatively, it can refer to the relationships within the system of human-technology-society, as well as the long-term secondary effects of human-technology interaction. These broader aspects include the ethics of technology, human-machine collaboration, organisational transformation, the interplay between the economy and ecology, and more. Human centricity aims to empower humans in collaboration with emerging technologies in the industrial context. It involves organisational innovation, social innovation, co-creation, and the adoption of new industrial practices and business models that prioritise social and environmental considerations.^{118, 119}

5.5 Outstanding agri-food startups leveraging AI and robotics

Startups play a pivotal role in driving innovation and economic development, serving as incubators for new ideas and scalable business models. Among these, agricultural startups stand out as transformative players, revolutionizing farming and related sectors. The companies listed below have been identified-based on the collected survey responses and a review of recent online information - as particularly prominent examples, potentially serving as benchmarks and reference points for industry stakeholders.

1. Robotics and Automation:

- **Tortuga AgTech**: This Denver-based startup provides farms with robots that automate tasks like identifying and picking ripe fruit. Their solutions help address labour shortages and rising costs while avoiding damage to produce.
- **Harvest CROO Robotics**: A Florida-based startup that has developed an advanced strawberry-harvesting robot. It uses computer vision to identify ripe berries and can pick a plant in eight seconds.
- **Agricarboon**: Based in Dundee, UK, Agricarboon measures and validates soil carbon capture and storage for farms and carbon markets. Their technology supports farmers in enhancing soil health while contributing to climate change mitigation.
- **Saga Robotics**: A Norwegian startup that develops autonomous robots for agriculture. Their Thorvald robot can perform tasks such as UV treatment for mildew, weeding, and harvesting, helping to reduce labor costs and increase efficiency

2. Artificial Intelligence (AI):

¹¹⁷ Hancock et al. 2011.

¹¹⁸ Implementing AI and IoT technology in large farms: <https://webmakers.expert/en/blog/implementing-ai-and-iot-technology-in-large-farms> (Accessed 01.12.2024)

¹¹⁹ Carlo Gavazzi: https://www.gavazziautomation.com/fileadmin/docs/download_area/Agriculture_1409_ENG.pdf (Accessed 01.12.2024)

- **Taranis:** The startup uses AI and high-resolution imagery to monitor crops and predict potential threats. Their platform offers precision scouting and insights to help farmers manage their fields effectively.
- **Prospera:** This startup that uses AI to provide data-driven insights for greenhouse and open-field farming. Their platform helps farmers optimize crop management and improve yield.
- **Source.ag:** Source.ag accelerates access to fresh fruit and vegetables through AI-powered glasshouses. Their proprietary algorithms simulate plant behaviour to define and execute optimal cultivation strategies.
- **AgroScout:** A startup that uses AI and machine learning to provide early detection of pests and diseases in crops. Their platform helps farmers take timely actions to protect their crops and improve yields.

3. Data-Driven Technologies:

- **CropX:** is an innovative agri-tech startup focusing on optimizing farming practices through data-driven solutions. Its core product is a platform that integrates proprietary IoT soil sensors with advanced software to provide real-time insights for managing irrigation, fertilization, and crop protection. By combining soil data with satellite imagery, weather forecasts, and crop models, the platform delivers tailored recommendations to farmers on when and how to irrigate, fertilize, or apply protective measures for optimal crop health.
- **Apollo Agriculture:** Founded in 2016, this startup combines satellite imagery, soil data, and weather patterns with AI to provide tailored advice and support to smallholder farmers in Africa. The company uses advanced technologies, including machine learning and automation, to provide farmers with critical resources such as high-quality farm inputs, optimized financing options, and digital agronomic advice.
- **Carbon Maps:** Based in Lille, Carbon Maps offers a comprehensive, science-based, data-driven environmental accounting platform for the food industry. Their SaaS platform enables rapid, high-precision assessments of the environmental impact of products and agricultural raw materials.
- **Hummingbird Technologies:** A UK-based startup that uses drone and satellite imagery combined with AI to provide detailed analytics on crop health and yield prediction. Their platform helps farmers make data-driven decisions to optimize their operations.
- **Enhanced Sustainability:**
 - **Biome Makers:** This startup, based in Spain, is a pioneering agri-tech startup that leverages DNA sequencing and artificial intelligence to analyse soil microbiomes, providing farmers with valuable insights to improve soil health and optimize agricultural practices.
 - **IRRIOT:** is a Swedish startup focused on developing innovative wireless irrigation solutions for agriculture. Their core product, a self-powered irrigation automation platform, utilizes low-power, long-range radio communication technology combined with cloud computing to reduce water wastage and improve irrigation efficiency. The platform provides a more sustainable and cost-effective alternative to traditional irrigation methods, especially by eliminating expensive wiring and reducing manual labour.
 - **Agreena:** is a Danish startup focused on helping farmers transition to regenerative agriculture practices by providing a platform for soil carbon certification. Founded in 2018, the company offers a technology-driven solution that

enables farmers to plan, track, and validate improvements in their farming methods, aiming to boost sustainability and reduce carbon emissions.

- **Klim:** Headquartered in Berlin, Klim enables farmers to transition to regenerative agriculture at scale by providing financial support, knowledge, documentation tools, and a community via their digital companion for farmers. Klim currently operates in countries like Germany, Poland, the USA, the UK, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic. It aims to expand regenerative practices to a wider group of farmers while contributing to global sustainability goals.
- **Innovation and Adaptability:**
- **Sencrop:** Based in France, Sencrop provides micro-climate technology to help farmers manage environmental risks. The company offers high-precision ag-weather stations, which gather real-time data on weather conditions, soil moisture, and crop health. This data helps farmers make informed decisions to optimize irrigation, reduce risks, and improve crop management.
- **Augmenta:** is a precision agriculture Greek startup focuses on optimizing farm management by leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) and real-time crop analysis. The company offers a system that integrates multispectral 4K cameras mounted on machinery to scan the crops during regular farming operations. This system analyses the condition of the crops, including foliage and other visual patterns, and uses AI to calculate the necessary adjustments for fertilizer and crop protection products.
- **CropBiome:** Based in Ireland, CropBiome that focuses on developing sustainable biological solutions to improve crop production. The company specializes in sourcing, selecting, fermenting, and testing microbes derived from wild plant species, which are then formulated into biological products such as seed dressings. These products aim to reduce farmers' reliance on chemical fertilizers and pesticides while enhancing crop resilience, especially under challenging conditions like drought.
- **eAgronom:** is an Estonian AgTech startup focused on promoting sustainable farming practices through data-driven solutions. Their platform offers farm management software that helps farmers transition to regenerative agricultural practices. The company's solutions support soil health, increase productivity, and reduce the need for chemical fertilizers by encouraging organic farming methods.

Other notables startups and their contributions

The AgriTech Trend Report highlights several startups that stand out in the agritech sector. These include [The Cultivated B](#) (precision fermentation), [Opo Bio](#) (lab-grown meat), [Carboniferous](#) (carbon sequestration in agriculture), [Miruku](#) (plant-based milk proteins production), and [FarmCube](#) (modular vertical farming). These startups bring innovative approaches to agriculture, focusing on sustainable practices and alternative food sources. Additionally, the sector is characterized by a high number of patents and financial support, indicating a commitment to developing new technologies.¹²⁰

The Report also highlights other startups such as [OnePointOne](#) (specializes in automated vertical farming using robotics and AI to optimize urban and high-density farming), [Baltic Freya](#) (indoor farming and sustainable agricultural practices), [Ag-Gene](#) (agricultural biotechnology, advanced genetic solutions to improve crop resilience and productivity), [XytoVet](#) (veterinary biotechnology, addressing animal health and productivity challenges in agricultural systems), [The Cultivated B](#) (cellular agriculture and precision fermentation, developing scalable bioreactor systems for sustainable production in food, nutraceuticals, and cosmetics).

¹²⁰ AgriTech Trend Report. StartUs Insights. https://tiny.pl/r_j549x0

Each of these startups contributes unique innovations to the agritech sector, addressing various areas of food production, such as precision fermentation, cultivated meat, and the creation of plant-based milk proteins. Moreover, the report highlights the industry's robust innovation landscape, evidenced by over 52,800 patents filed and substantial financial backing, reflecting a strong dedication to advancing new technologies.

Standout companies and their solutions

The startups most frequently mentioned by surveys respondents as the most impressive are:

- **AgXeed**
- **Farmdroid**
- **Naio Technologies**
- **Ecorobotix**

The most impressive solutions for respondents who are experts in the agri-food industry are those in the field of autonomous robotics, particularly those focused on automating fieldwork.

Figure 9. Most Impressive Startups/Solutions.
Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

A brief overview of the most frequently mentioned and impressive startups

AgXeed: AgXeed is a Netherlands-based startup that focuses on autonomous farming solutions designed to provide farmers with greater efficiency, flexibility, and sustainability. The company offers a fully integrated autonomy system, combining advanced hardware, virtual planning tools, and data analytics models to support modern farming practices.

AgXeed's core product lineup includes the AgBot series- scalable autonomous tractors equipped for a range of agricultural tasks. These machines are designed to reduce labour demands, optimize resource usage, and improve the overall precision of farming operations. By leveraging these technologies, AgXeed aims to empower farmers to manage

their land more effectively while addressing challenges like labour shortages and environmental sustainability. They utilize advanced navigation systems and artificial intelligence for precise control of robots in the field.

The company emphasizes its vision for sustainable agriculture by integrating advanced technologies and fostering new generational interest in farming. This mission aligns with global efforts to ensure food security and environmental stewardship in agriculture. For more details, visit: [AgXeed](#).

Farmdroid: FarmDroid is a Danish company that has developed the world's first fully autonomous field robot capable of both sowing and mechanical weed control. Its flagship product, the FarmDroid FD20, uses solar-powered GPS technology to precisely mark crop placements during sowing and subsequently performs mechanical weeding between and within rows. This precision reduces or eliminates the need for manual labour and chemical herbicides, making it a sustainable solution for farmers.

The FD20 robot operates on four solar panels, enabling up to 24 hours of CO₂-neutral operation without the need for external battery charging. This innovation aligns with the company's mission to help farmers lower costs and environmental impact while maintaining productivity. For more information, visit: [FarmDroid's website](#)

Naïo Technologies: Naïo Technologies is a French company, pioneering startup in agricultural robotics. The company specializes in developing weeding robots designed to reduce the use of chemical herbicides and ease the physical workload of farmers. Their robots are equipped with advanced navigation systems tailored for off-road use, making them suitable for various crop types, including market gardening, vegetable farming, and viticulture. Naïo Technologies' robots use advanced algorithms for navigation and task execution with high precision.

Naïo Technologies aims to promote sustainable farming practices by enabling precise, autonomous weeding and contributing to environmental conservation. Over the years, the company has expanded internationally, partnering with distributors in countries like Belgium and Denmark, while exploring markets in North America, Japan, and Australia. For more details, visit: [Naïo Technologies website](#).

Ecorobotix: Ecorobotix is a Swiss startup that has developed autonomous robots for precision crop spraying. Specialized in AI-Powered ultra-high precision spraying for vegetable crops, meadows, and lawns.

Their main product is the ARA robot, which is capable of precisely applying crop protection products only where needed. The ARA robot uses cameras and image analysis systems to identify weeds and other plant issues, allowing for reduced chemical use and increased spraying efficiency. For more detailed information, visit: [Ecorobotix](#).

General conclusion: The agri-food sector is undergoing a significant digital transformation, yet this process is hindered by high costs and a lack of competencies. Despite these challenges, most respondents recognize the immense potential of new technologies, particularly in the context of improving efficiency and promoting sustainable development.

6 Technology development and use cases

Figure 10. Layout diagram of the Y2 (2024) catalogue

6.1 Functionalities and use cases

The following list describes selected functionalities related to artificial intelligence, data, and robotic technologies in the agri-food sector, which development is supported by the agrifoodTEF project. These functionalities represent cross-cutting technological areas that are relevant across many agricultural sectors and activities. Most agrifoodTEF services are intentionally designed to support a broad range of applications and are not limited to one specific use case or domain. The main goal of this list is to identify key functionalities where agrifoodTEF services can assist in their refinement through testing, validation, or by providing training data sets. This list is based on the results of the 2023 Project Report: [D1.1 Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1](#)¹²¹, supplemented by feedback from respondents of a conducted survey.

During its creation, the division into functionalities defining the scope and capabilities of the described devices and their components was adopted as the overriding criterion. For each of the indicated functionalities, an attempt was made to consider the possibilities and wide range of use cases with assemblies or technological systems that allow them to work within the framework of the indicated functionalities.

¹²¹ AgrifoodTEF 2023 Project Report: [D1.1 Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1](#).

Object recognition systems, terrain mapping

Object recognition and terrain mapping are designed to support the functionality of autonomous, automatic equipment and agricultural aggregates, as well as harvesters and self-propelled agricultural machinery equipped with agricultural machinery for the implementation of agricultural technologies, leading to the achievement of the required precision, efficiency, quality of work and the achievement of measurable environmental (natural, ecological), economic as well as social benefits. Object recognition systems are also used to assess the location and condition of livestock, the state of cleanliness of livestock buildings or control the distribution of feed in feed aisles.

Use cases:

- Positioning of areas with diseased, weakened, heavily weedy plants requiring intervention for other reasons as well (*AI / Arable Farming / Observation / AI Model or Vision Sensor*)
- Positioning of crop sowing (*AI / Arable Farming / Seeding / Sensor*)
- Obstacle detection (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Mobility / Robot*)
- Positioning of animals and assessment of their physical condition (*AI / Livestock Farming / Observation / Vision Sensor*)
- Assessment of the cleanliness of livestock buildings and the status of feed distribution in feed corridors (*AI / Livestock Farming / Sanitation / Field Computer or AI Model*)
- Positioning of feed or excrement areas of concentration for their appropriate assignment to animals or removal from the livestock building (*AI / Livestock Farming / Sanitation / Field Computer*)
- Segregation of images and facilities to assess yield levels (*AI / Arable Farming / Observation-Monitoring / AI Model or Vision Sensor*)

Mobility & SLAM

Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) is a functionality that allows robots or other mobile devices, including autonomous ones, to simultaneously create a map of an unknown, not precisely described environment and determine their position in that map. The technology is based on a laser scanner and software, which allows it to map its environment while positioning itself in that environment. It is thanks to SLAM's functionality and technologies that robots, autonomous vehicles can realize their mobility capabilities and move efficiently in dynamic and often unfamiliar spaces. Such spaces include areas used for agriculture, but also livestock areas. The technique supports mobility functionalities, moving autonomous devices, automatic devices and agricultural aggregates, as well as combines and self-propelled agricultural machinery in previously digitally unidentified in their control systems and not digitally mapped areas or surfaces. The capabilities of these functionalities significantly support the operation of these devices by helping them achieve the required precision, efficiency, quality of work. As a result, this leads to obtaining measurable environmental (natural, ecological), economic as well as social benefits.

Use cases:

- Control and routing of the agricultural unit or autonomous equipment (driving straight, avoiding obstacles, turning around in the optimal and shortest possible trajectory) to achieve maximum efficiency and quality of operation of the equipment and machinery leading to maximization of yields (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Mobility / Robot*)
- Obstacle localization (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Mobility / Robot*)
- Positioning of crop planting (*AI / Arable Farming / Planting / Sensor*)
- Ability to be used anywhere and anytime: SLAM allows navigation in unfamiliar environments without the need for prior terrain mapping (*Robotics / Other / Mobility / Robot*)
- Independence from weather (*Robotics / Other / Mobility / Robot*)

- The multisystem nature of navigation data collection and processing allows devices to respond dynamically to changing environmental conditions (*Robotics / Other / Mobility / Robot + Field Computer*)
- The ability to map in confined areas not covered by GPS navigation (*Robotics / Other / Mobility-Mapping / Sensor*)

Prediction

Prediction is the process of inferring the future magnitudes of random variables at a specific future point in time (period) when the output is unknown. This functionality makes it possible to use model training datasets with labels and metadata to benchmark AI algorithms by target groups of technologies under investigation. The result is the ability to provide verification of the operation of owned devices and control systems in their actual operating conditions, and thus verify the correctness of the course of the technologies implemented through the realisation of the tasks assigned to them. This functionality will make it possible to indicate sensitive places and points in the objects or systems under study and will facilitate mobility in the field for robots, autonomous vehicles, etc. This will result in the targeting of future activities leading to the maximisation of the benefits of robotics and AI technologies.

The use of this functionality also provides the possibility of positioning, i.e. guiding an agricultural unit (machine + tractor) or autonomous device (tractor, implement carrier) equipped with an agricultural machine or device intended to implement specific, preset agricultural technologies.

Use cases:

- Control and definition of the route taken by the agricultural unit or autonomous machine (driving straight ahead, avoiding obstacles, turning along the optimum and shortest possible trajectory) to achieve maximum efficiency and quality of operation of the unit and machinery leading to maximisation of yields (*AI / Arable Farming / Mobility / AI Model*)
- Obstacle location (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Mobility / Sensor*)
- Positioning of planted crops (*AI / Arable Farming / Planting / Sensor*)
- Positioning of areas with diseased, weakened, heavily weeded plants requiring intervention for other reasons as well (*AI / Arable Farming / Observation / AI Model*)
- Ability to react and quickly adapt the process of e.g. spraying or fertilising to the current state and quality, health, weed infestation on the plantation, crop (*AI / Arable Farming / Spraying / AI Model*)
- Adaptation of measures to the temporary, local situation (*AI / Arable Farming / Treatment / AI Model or Field Computer*)

Data integration

This functionality ensures the preparation of data sets for the support and proper implementation of agricultural technologies, leading to the required precision, efficiency, quality of work and the attainment of measurable environmental (natural, ecological), economic as well as social benefits. The support will include autonomous, automatic or agricultural aggregates, multifunctional harvesters and self-propelled agricultural machinery equipped with machines or devices for agricultural and crop processing operations. The support processes will be based on conducting machine learning of AI systems and algorithms as the aforementioned objects and vehicles are or will be equipped with and used to control and steer the operation of these objects. The preparation of these data sets will consist of combining previously validated and selected data from several different sources to provide users with a single, unified set.

Use cases:

- Preparing integrated AI learning datasets for the support and proper implementation of agricultural technologies (*AI / Arable Farming / Observation/Monitoring / AI Model or Dataset*)
- Carrying out machine learning of AI systems and algorithms in which the aforementioned objects and vehicles are or will be equipped, and which are used for the command and control of the operation of autonomous,

automatic devices or agricultural aggregates, multifunctional harvesters and self-propelled agricultural machinery (*AI / Arable Farming / Mobility / AI Model or Field Computer*)

- Combining previously validated and selected data from several different sources to provide users with a single, unified AI learning set (*AI / Other / Data Aggregation / Dataset*)
- The learning data to be prepared will concern, for example, the control and routing of an agricultural unit or autonomous machine, the positioning of planted crops or areas with diseased, weakened or heavily weeded plants (*AI / Arable Farming / Mobility or Observation / AI Model or Dataset*)

Robot kinematics

In agricultural technology, autonomous or automatic robots are used to carry out tasks such as picking fruit, pulling weeds, etc., equipped with robotic arms. The second group of devices referred to by experts as agricultural robots are autonomous vehicles performing various field crops and other tasks related to crop production, livestock breeding or pre-processing of crops. The robots used to implement these technologies, especially those equipped with robotic arms, have complex kinematics of working movements.

Functionality concerning the kinematics of the robot is aimed at defining the working capabilities of the arms, their reach, working ranges, lifting capacity or force to pick and hold objects (plants, fruit), as well as the operating parameters of autonomous and automatic devices. The results of these activities are aimed at achieving measurable economic, environmental (nature, ecological) and social benefits.

Use cases:

- Analyses of the kinematics of working movements of robotic arms used in agricultural and peri-agricultural technologies and in the pre-processing of agricultural crops. (*Robotics / Tree Crops / Harvesting / Tool section - Robot Arm*)
- Analyses of the movement parameters of autonomous vehicles performing various field crops and other tasks related to crop production, livestock breeding or pre-processing of agricultural crops. (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Mobility / Robot*)
- Determination of physical quantities describing the permissible parametric ranges of work and working fields of robots in applied agricultural applications to determine the possible efficiencies of their work and assess the quality of the treatments and operations performed. (*Robotics / Arable Farming / Observation-Monitoring / Tool Carrier or Robot*)

Sensor data mapping

Ongoing monitoring of the environmental conditions in areas used for agriculture, fields, meadows and pastures, vegetable crops, flowers, speciality crops, shrubs and fruit trees, etc., allows all treatments to be carried out at the times and under the conditions most favourable to them, due to the often rapidly changing weather and environmental conditions. Ongoing monitoring of environmental conditions, including soil, allows continuous updating of the abundance maps which, together with the yield maps, are used to draw up and update application maps, i.e. digital maps, indispensable for controlling the operation of machinery when carrying out such procedures as, e.g. fertilisation, sowing, plant protection.

Ongoing monitoring of the environmental conditions in livestock buildings, outbuildings and associated areas (paddocks), as well as the areas where the animals are housed, allows the farm to be managed and controlled in accordance with animal welfare principles, with proper supervision of the herds of animals. Optimising the environmental parameters in the buildings in which the animals are housed allows the animals to be provided with the living conditions they require, while monitoring their health parameters in turn allows diseases and other health problems to be detected and diagnosed at an early stage. Ensuring and maintaining the right living conditions for livestock and adapting them on an ongoing basis to the often-rapid changes in the weather allows for their proper wellbeing, which in turn leads to their greater efficiency and productivity and, consequently, to the production of healthier and more abundant livestock products. Another feature that fits in with this technology is the control of where the animals are in the paddocks around livestock buildings and in pastures.

Use cases:

- Measurements of soil quality parameters (*Other / Arable Farming / Observation / Sensor*).
- Measurements of atmospheric parameters (*Other / Arable Farming / Observation / Sensor*).
- Control of soil condition, humidity, temperature (*Other / Arable Farming / Irrigation / Sensor*).
- Measurements of humidity, temperature, air chemistry (*Other / Livestock Farming / Observation/Monitoring / Sensor*).
- Controlling the health of animals, their anatomical parameters (*AI / Livestock Farming / Health Monitoring / Vision Sensor or Field Computer*).
- Monitoring of the amount of concentrated feed consumed (*AI / Livestock Farming / Feeding / Sensor*).
- Supervision of the cleanliness of livestock buildings (*AI / Livestock Farming / Sanitation / AI Model or Sensor*).
- Controlling the location of animals (*AI / Livestock Farming / Mobility / Sensor or Vision Sensor*).
- Implementing the milk collection process (automatic milking) (*Robotics / Livestock Farming / Harvesting/Collection / Robot*).
- Implementation of the egg collection process (*Robotics / Livestock Farming / Harvesting/Collection/ Robot*).

6.2 Technologies

This chapter focuses on describing the main advantages and disadvantages of technologies used to fulfil functionalities and use cases. We also explore their potential, as well as directions for future development.

This list of identified technologies is based on the results of the agrifoodTEF 2023 Project Report: [D1.1 Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1](#)¹²².

RTK GPS (Real-Time Kinematic GPS)

RTK GPS (Real-Time Kinematic GPS) is an advanced satellite navigation technique that significantly enhances the precision of traditional GPS systems by providing real-time corrections. These corrections allow for centimeter-level accuracy, which is essential in industries requiring high precision, such as agriculture, construction, surveying, and autonomous vehicles. The system operates by using a fixed base station and mobile units (rovers). The base station calculates the difference between its known position and the calculated position from GPS signals, and this correction is transmitted to the rover in real-time, ensuring highly accurate positioning.

In agriculture, RTK GPS plays a key role in precision farming, enabling farmers to monitor crop fields, manage irrigation systems, and operate machinery with exceptional accuracy.

Pros of technology:

- **High precision:** RTK GPS offers centimeter-level accuracy, making it vital for precision tasks in agriculture such as seeding, spot-spraying, weeding, and fertilizing. By maintaining consistent row spacing and plant distribution, it ensures optimal seed placement, preventing double seeding by deactivating specific sections of the seeding equipment. This technology also supports non-chemical weed control between rows and plants by enabling precise targeting of mechanical or biological methods. Furthermore, RTK GPS allows for the targeted application of fertilizers directly to seeds or germinating plants, reducing the overall use of fertilizers on a given field. This leads to significant cost savings and helps mitigate the environmental impact of both chemical and organic fertilization practices.

¹²² AgrifoodTEF 2023 Project Report: [D1.1 Online Technology and use cases outlook Y1](#)

- **Real-time corrections:** Ensures continuous accuracy, even in dynamic environments.
- **Automation and efficiency:** Supports autonomous machinery, reducing labour costs and increasing efficiency.
- **Weather independence:** RTK GPS works regardless of weather conditions.

Cons of technology:

- **Cost:** RTK GPS systems are costly, with significant expenses for both installation and ongoing maintenance. This includes the initial cost of the equipment and the subscription fees for correction signals required to ensure accurate positioning. These costs can be a barrier for smaller operations, although the precision and efficiency they provide often justify the investment in the long term.
- **Complexity:** The system requires skilled operators for setup and maintenance, as well as a reliable internet or radio connection for signal transmission.
- **Signal interference:** RTK GPS can be affected by obstacles such as tall buildings, trees, or adverse weather, which may cause signal degradation.
- **Dependence on Satellite signal:** It requires a stable GPS signal, which can be problematic in areas with high forestation or in deep valleys. (Investment in infrastructure near the application can also cause an increase in costs.)

Future Directions

RTK GPS is poised for significant advancements in agriculture and other sectors. Key trends include:

- **Integration with other technologies:** Combining RTK GPS with IoT devices, drones, and AI systems will further enhance automation and data-driven decision-making in farming.
- **Cost reduction:** As RTK technology advances, the cost of RTK GPS systems is expected to decrease, making precision farming tools more accessible for smaller farms and businesses. Innovations are focused on reducing the cost of components and improving the affordability of installation. Additionally, efforts are being made to increase the availability of RTK correction signals in regions with challenging terrain, such as areas with dense tree cover or technical ground installations. These improvements aim to make RTK systems more accessible, offering greater flexibility and precision in a wider range of agricultural environments.
- **Advancements in satellite systems and enhanced precision in RTK GPS technology:** The development of different satellite systems and the expansion of the ability to integrate data from various dispatch systems, both public and commercial, are key to advancing RTK GPS technology. Continued advancements in satellite technology, such as the integration of multiple satellite constellations, will further enhance RTK accuracy and reliability. By incorporating data from various sources, these developments will increase the precision of RTK systems, providing more robust and consistent performance, even in regions with challenging conditions. These improvements will help expand the use of RTK GPS in agriculture, construction, and other sectors that require high-precision positioning.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

RTK GPS enhances sustainability by enabling precision farming techniques that reduce waste, conserve resources, and minimize environmental footprints. This results in long-term cost savings for farmers, increasing profitability and ensuring the economic viability of operations. By improving productivity and efficiency, RTK GPS helps make farming more economically sustainable, especially for smaller-scale operations.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects):

- **Ethical considerations:** The automation enabled by RTK GPS could result in job displacement in certain sectors. There are ethical concerns about the societal impact of reduced human intervention in farming. It's vital to ensure that the benefits of automation are distributed equitably, offering workers opportunities for reskilling and upskilling.
- **Legal aspects:** Land ownership and data privacy issues are critical, as RTK GPS systems generate and collect geospatial data. Proper handling of this data, including implementing robust data protection measures and obtaining necessary consents, is essential to prevent misuse.
- **Social implications:** While RTK GPS adoption could improve efficiency and food security, it may exacerbate disparities between technologically advanced farms and those with limited access to such systems. Promoting inclusive policies that support smaller farms and ensuring broad access to RTK GPS technology is essential.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Measurement of positioning deviation in various field conditions (e.g., in an open field, near obstacles). Example scope of service: providing fields (test plots) for verification of correct operation of satellite systems; validation of correct operation of systems under different conditions of terrain configuration.
- **Signal stability:** Tests of GPS signal stability under various atmospheric and terrain conditions. Example of the scope of the service: verification of changes in the level of GPS signal stability under different atmospheric and terrain conditions.
- **Integration with Robotic systems:** Checking the integration of GNSS with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the efficiency of automation operations such as sowing or fertilizing.
- Comparison with reference geodetic data.
- Evaluation of the repeatability of positioning results.
- Resistance to interference and integration of other, backup positioning sources. Example scope of service: testing of agricultural machinery, autonomous vehicles, aggregates with biotic systems used in agricultural work in the direction of verification, correctness of integration of GNSS system with the said machinery, real-time equipment, e.g. in the direction of comparison with geodetic reference data, evaluation of repeatability of positioning results.

GNSS - Global Navigation Satellite System

GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) is a satellite-based navigation system designed to determine the precise location of a point or moving object on Earth. It works by measuring the travel time of radio signals from satellites to a receiver's antenna. To accurately calculate the position, at least four satellites' signals must be processed, with the satellites' locations known at the time of measurement. The system utilizes a variety of satellite constellations, including GPS (United States), GLONASS (Russia), Galileo (Europe), and BeiDou (China), offering global coverage for navigation and positioning.

GNSS is widely used across various sectors, including transportation, agriculture, military, construction, and telecommunications. In agriculture, GNSS plays a key role in precision farming, facilitating high-accuracy applications such as autonomous machinery, field mapping, and crop monitoring. By triangulating signals from a network of satellites, GNSS enables devices to determine precise longitude, latitude, and altitude, making it an essential tool for enhancing operational efficiency, sustainability, and resource management.

GNSS-based technologies are critical for precision agriculture, improving the accuracy of farming practices such as crop planting, fertilization, irrigation, and monitoring. This leads to more effective resource use, minimized waste, and optimized productivity, benefiting both economic and environmental outcomes.

Pros of technology:

- **High precision:** GNSS offers high-precision location data, essential for applications like precision agriculture, transportation, and surveying.
- **Global coverage and wide range of applications:** provides global coverage and reliable service across nearly all regions of the world, enabling its use in a wide range of applications. This system is crucial for positioning and navigation, as it offers precise location data at any time and in any location. GNSS signals are transmitted from satellites, allowing users to determine their position anywhere on Earth.
- One of the key advantages of GNSS is its ability to support the navigation of autonomous or automated vehicles, making it especially valuable in agriculture. It enables these vehicles to operate effectively across diverse surfaces such as crop fields, plantations, and other agricultural environments. The versatility of GNSS allows it to be used for a wide variety of applications, from transportation and surveying to precision farming, providing an invaluable tool for improving efficiency and sustainability.
- **Real-time Data:** Provides immediate positioning updates, which is essential for dynamic applications like autonomous vehicles and machinery.
- **Flexibility:** Weather Independence: GNSS operates independently of weather conditions.
- **Low cost** of purchasing a basic set, receiver.

Cons of technology:

- **Accuracy:** Lower precision: achieving large, centimetre accuracy requires the use of touch receivers and the system to make computational corrections based on time data and an additional antenna (base station) on the surface of the crop, plantation.
- **Signal Interference:** GNSS signals can be susceptible to interference caused by physical obstacles such as tall buildings, dense forests, or deep valleys. These obstructions can lead to reduced accuracy or complete signal loss, especially in environments with limited line-of-sight to the satellites. The reliance on stable GPS signals becomes a challenge in areas with high forestation or in deep valleys, where the satellite signals may not reach the receiver effectively. Such interference can cause delays in positioning or degrade the overall performance of GNSS systems, impacting their reliability in certain geographical areas.
- **Dependency on Satellites:** GNSS systems rely on satellites, meaning that any disruption in satellite constellations can impact the accuracy and reliability of positioning.
- Possibility of occurrence of intentional interference with the system, e.g. by the military.

Future Directions:

The future of GNSS technology is shaped by several key trends that focus on improving accuracy, reducing costs, and expanding its applicability. Key developments include:

- **Cost reduction:** Innovations are focused on reducing the costs of components and implementation, making GNSS technology more accessible to a wider range of users.
- **Integration with other technologies:** GNSS is increasingly being combined with other systems such as RTK, vision sensors, IoT, AI, and machine learning to increase precision and enable smarter, fully automated systems for applications in precision farming, logistics, and more.
- **Enhanced accuracy:** The use of multiple satellite constellations (such as GPS, Galileo, and GLONASS) will further enhance GNSS's positioning accuracy, particularly in challenging environments like dense forests or urban areas.

- **Miniaturization:** The development of smaller, more affordable GNSS devices will allow even smaller farms and businesses to access high-precision technologies that were previously cost-prohibitive.
- **Improved signal availability:** Work is being done to improve GNSS signal availability in areas with difficult terrain, such as regions with dense vegetation or urban obstacles, ensuring more reliable service in challenging environments.
- **Software development:** Continuous advancements in correction algorithms and signal filtering techniques are enhancing the overall accuracy and efficiency of GNSS systems.

These trends highlight how GNSS technology is evolving to meet the needs of modern industries, with particular emphasis on agriculture, logistics, and autonomous systems.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

GNSS supports sustainability by enabling more efficient resource use in agriculture. For example, it allows farmers to apply fertilizers and pesticides only where needed, reducing chemical usage and environmental pollution. Additionally, GNSS technology helps increase crop yields and optimize the use of land, improving economic viability for farmers. In the long term, this can lead to cost savings, greater profitability, and reduced environmental impact.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects):

- **Ethical considerations:** The widespread use of GNSS raises concerns regarding privacy, especially when location data is used without proper consent. As GNSS is integrated into more personal and commercial systems, ensuring that data is handled ethically is critical. This includes implementing robust data protection measures and obtaining necessary consents for data collection and usage.
- **Legal aspects:** GNSS-related issues include the regulation of satellite access and the use of geospatial data. It is important to ensure that satellite signals are not subject to malicious interference and that users comply with legal frameworks governing data collection and privacy. This involves adhering to regulations that protect satellite infrastructure and ensure the secure transmission of data.
- **Social implications:** The accessibility of GNSS technology could lead to inequalities, particularly between large-scale operations and smaller farmers who may not afford the necessary equipment. Ensuring that technology benefits all sectors, regardless of size, is vital to its ethical use. This includes promoting policies that support smaller farms and ensuring that the benefits of GNSS technology are accessible to all farmers.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Positioning accuracy:** Measurement of positioning deviation in various field conditions (e.g., in an open field, near obstacles).
- **Signal stability:** Tests of GPS signal stability under various atmospheric and terrain conditions.
- **Integration with Robotic systems:** Checking the integration of GNSS with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the efficiency of automation operations such as sowing or fertilizing.
- **Comparison with reference geodetic data.**
- **Evaluation of the repeatability of positioning results.**
- **Resistance to interference and integration of other, backup positioning sources.**

Overall, GNSS is a transformative technology that is reshaping industries, especially agriculture, by improving precision, efficiency, and sustainability. As the technology advances, its integration with other emerging technologies will further enhance its impact across various sectors.

Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) technology

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is an advanced computational technology used by robots and autonomous systems to simultaneously create a map of an unfamiliar environment while tracking their own position within that map. It combines data from various sensors, such as LIDAR, cameras, and radar, to generate a detailed, real-time map of the surroundings. This process is particularly important in environments where GPS signals are unavailable or unreliable, such as indoors, in deep valleys, or in complex, dynamic settings.

SLAM systems operate using laser scanners or visual sensors, allowing robots and mobile devices to navigate unfamiliar and constantly changing spaces. By continuously updating the map with new data, SLAM enables the device to adjust its positioning and path in real time. This adaptability is crucial for robots to effectively navigate dynamic environments, which can be especially useful in fields like autonomous vehicles, robotics, and agriculture, where SLAM technology supports precision tasks such as autonomous navigation, crop monitoring, and field mapping.

Pros of technology SLAM Technology:

- **Wide Range of Applications:** SLAM technology can be deployed in a variety of environments without the need for prior terrain mapping. This allows autonomous or automated vehicles to navigate on any type of terrain, including agricultural fields and plantations, where GPS signals might be weak or unavailable.
- **No Reliance on GPS:** SLAM functions effectively in GPS-denied environments, such as indoors, in cluttered spaces, or areas with obstructed signals. This makes it ideal for use in warehouses, greenhouses, and underground facilities, where traditional GPS systems fail.
- **High Precision:** By integrating data from multiple sensors such as LIDAR, cameras, and radar, SLAM provides highly accurate mapping and real-time positioning. This precision is crucial for applications in sectors like agriculture and robotics, where accurate location tracking is necessary for tasks like crop monitoring and autonomous vehicle navigation.
- **Dynamic Adaptability:** SLAM continuously updates its environment map in real-time, enabling autonomous systems to dynamically adjust their position and path in response to changes in the environment. This adaptability is particularly valuable in environments with moving objects or unpredictable conditions.
- **Real-time Processing:** SLAM generates and updates maps in real-time, allowing autonomous systems to navigate and map dynamic environments without the need for external references or prior data. This makes it particularly effective in rapidly changing conditions.
- **Flexibility:** SLAM does not require pre-loaded terrain data, allowing it to navigate unknown environments and adapt to new surroundings in real-time. This is particularly beneficial in environments that are constantly evolving or where GPS data is not available.

Cons of technology SLAM Technology:

- **Complexity:** The algorithms and sensor fusion methods used in SLAM are highly complex, requiring expertise to implement and optimize. This complexity can make it challenging to deploy and fine-tune the technology for different applications.

- **Sensor dependency:** SLAM's performance heavily relies on the quality and reliability of the sensors used, such as cameras, LIDAR, and radar systems. Any issues with sensor calibration, reliability, or environmental interference (e.g., poor lighting conditions or reflective surfaces) can lead to inaccuracies in mapping and navigation.
- **High computational demands:** SLAM requires substantial computational power to process large volumes of sensor data and generate real-time, accurate maps. This can make it computationally expensive, requiring high-performance hardware, which may not always be affordable or practical for all applications.
- **Cost of equipment:** Achieving the necessary depth and accuracy in SLAM typically requires advanced sensor setups, including multi-camera systems, LIDAR, and other specialized devices. This increases the overall cost of the system, making it less accessible for smaller applications or businesses with limited budgets.
- **Inaccuracy of positioning:** Without a fixed reference point (e.g., GPS), SLAM can sometimes suffer from drift in positioning over time. As the system relies on its last known position and orientation, any errors can accumulate, leading to a gradual loss of accuracy. This can necessitate frequent recalibration and updating of the map.
- **Vulnerability to interference:** SLAM systems can be vulnerable to interference, such as intentional jamming or signal disruption, particularly in sensitive areas like military operations. This raises concerns about the security and reliability of SLAM in certain environments, where external disruption could impact its functionality.

Future Directions of SLAM Technology

The future of Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) technology is characterized by ongoing advancements that aim to enhance its accuracy, accessibility, and efficiency. Key trends include:

- **Integration with AI and Machine Learning:** SLAM is being combined with artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning to enable autonomous systems to better learn from their environments, adapt to changes, and make real-time decisions based on the maps and data. This integration allows for smarter, more responsive autonomous operations across various industries, particularly in agriculture and robotics.
- **Miniaturization of Sensors:** Advances in sensor technology are leading to the development of smaller, more efficient sensors, which will make SLAM more accessible for compact, low-cost devices. This is especially significant for applications in agriculture, where cost-effective solutions can be scaled for smaller operations, such as drones or handheld robots.
- **Enhanced Robustness and Accuracy:** The next generation of SLAM systems will focus on improving robustness, especially in dynamic and challenging environments. By leveraging multi-sensor fusion and machine learning techniques, future systems will reduce errors and improve mapping precision, even in the presence of obstacles, noise, or data loss. This enhanced capability will allow SLAM to function more effectively in complex environments, such as dense forests, urban areas, and large-scale agricultural fields.
- **Cost reduction:** Innovation is moving towards lower component and implementation costs.
- **Software development:** Improving signal correction and filtering algorithms to increase accuracy.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) contributes significantly to sustainability by enabling autonomous systems to optimize resource usage, reduce environmental impact, and enhance operational efficiency. In agriculture, SLAM-powered autonomous machines can perform tasks like precise crop planting, weeding, and targeted pesticide application, which minimizes waste and reduces environmental harm. This technology also promotes more efficient

land use and improves crop management while decreasing the need for chemical inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides. Economically, SLAM reduces labour costs, increases productivity, and supports small and medium-sized businesses by making high-precision automation technologies accessible. This helps smaller enterprises remain competitive and efficient in the market.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects):

- **Ethical considerations:** SLAM's role in automation, particularly in industries like agriculture, raises concerns about job displacement, as machines replace human labour. Addressing these concerns involves implementing programs for reskilling and retraining workers, ensuring that displaced workers have opportunities to transition into other roles within the economy.
- **Legal aspects:** The implementation of SLAM technology often involves collecting and processing data, which raises important legal concerns around privacy, consent, and data security. Regulations are essential to ensure that data collected by autonomous systems, particularly in public or commercial spaces, is managed ethically and complies with privacy laws.
- **Social implications:** As SLAM technology becomes more widespread, there is a risk of increasing inequality between large enterprises that can afford these technologies and smaller, less resourced organizations. To ensure that SLAM benefits all sectors, it is crucial to introduce policies that make the technology accessible to smaller players, fostering fair competition and equitable development across industries.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- Positioning accuracy: Measurement of positioning deviation under different field conditions (e.g. open field, near obstacles).
- Signal stability: Stability tests of sensor and camera signals under different weather and field conditions.
- Integration with robotic, autonomous systems: Verification of the integration of the SLAM system with agricultural robots in real time, evaluating the effectiveness of automation of operations such as sowing or fertilization.
- Comparison with geodetic reference data.
- Immunity from interference and integration of other, backup positioning sources
- Accuracy and range: Measurement of positioning accuracy with the SLAM system in different locations and conditions (e.g. woodland, valleys).
- Initialisation time: Measurement of the time it takes to obtain a stable signal and accurate positioning of the device, depending on the available number of cameras, sensors and computing power once the system is up and running.
- Compatibility of the control equipment making up the system: Interoperability tests of the object position control, terrain and obstacle recognition and terrain mapping devices that make up SLAM-type systems.

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) technology is revolutionizing industries such as agriculture and robotics by enabling more precise and efficient autonomous systems. As it continues to evolve, its integration with AI, machine learning, and improved sensor technologies will further enhance its impact on industries worldwide. To maximize its potential, it is important to address ethical, legal, and social challenges, ensuring that SLAM is accessible, equitable, and aligned with sustainable practices.

Multisystem positioning (mix of different positioning and localization technologies) e.g. RTK-GPS + RTK-GNSS

Multisystem positioning is an advanced technology that combines various positioning and localization systems to provide accurate and reliable location determination such as RTK-GPS (Real-Time Kinematic GPS) and RTK-GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System). The combination of these technologies ensures enhanced accuracy and reliability for

positioning tasks, achieving centimeter-level precision by leveraging corrections from multiple reference stations and satellite constellations. Applications span across agriculture (precision farming), construction, geospatial mapping, and autonomous vehicles.¹²³

Pros of technology:

- **Flexibility:** Can be customized and adapted to the specific needs of agricultural applications.
- **Integration:** Ease of integration with other positioning and navigation systems.
- **Precision:** Can offer greater data accuracy as a result of synergy of data from different sources, devices.
- **Reliability** in diverse environments.

Cons of technology:

- **Environment dependence:** Effectiveness can depend on environmental and topographical conditions.
- **Compatibility:** combining data from many different sources, transmitted using different protocols, can lead to errors and positioning inaccuracy in reading the data or inability to read the transmitted data.
- **Cost:** putting together different positioning devices into a single system can lead to increased costs due to, among other things, the need for devices with significantly higher computing power.
- Complexity in setup and operation.
- Susceptibility to interference (mitigated with advanced filtering technologies)

Future Directions

- **Multisensor integration:** Combining different positioning technologies to increase precision and reliability.
- **Algorithm development:** Improving data fusion algorithms and error correction.
- **Integration with AI:** Enhancing decision-making in autonomous systems.
- **Expanded Satellite Networks:** Increasing accuracy and availability with newer constellations.
- **Advanced Interference Mitigation:** Improving performance in RF-noisy environments.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Multisystem positioning reduces environmental impact by optimizing input usage (fertilizers, water) and increasing yield predictability. It also cuts costs by enabling automation, leading to long-term economic benefits despite high initial investment.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects)

- **Ethical:** Ensures equitable access to technology across regions, preventing digital divides.
- **Legal:** Requires compliance with data-sharing and spectrum regulations.
- **Social:** Enhances food security through efficient agricultural practices, but raises concerns over labour displacement due to automation.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Accuracy and consistency:** Measurement of positioning accuracy in different environments (e.g., open field, near buildings).

¹²³ Li, X., Wang, B., Li, X. *et al.* Principle and performance of multi-frequency and multi-GNSS PPP-RTK. *Satell Navig* 3, 7 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43020-022-00068-0>

- **Integration with Infrastructure:** Testing the integration of different positioning and guidance technologies combined into a system, such as GNSS or RTK GPS, Lidar, evaluating the improvement in accuracy of the overall system performance.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Evaluation of the energy consumption of positioning systems and their impact on the working time of robots
- **Compatibility:** Compatibility tests, cooperation of systems forming one positioning and guidance system installed on the tested autonomous vehicle.

Multisystem positioning, a transformative technology, combines different positioning and localization systems like RTK-GPS and RTK-GNSS to deliver exceptional accuracy and reliability. It is essential for fields requiring precise location determination, such as geodesy, precision agriculture, transport, and construction. This technology has profound implications for enhancing precision, operational efficiency, and sustainability.

While initial costs and system complexity pose challenges, the potential for innovation and long-term benefits solidifies its role as a cornerstone in modern technological applications. Emerging trends, including integration with AI and IoT, further promise to amplify its utility, enabling smarter, more sustainable, and efficient systems across industries.

Vision Sensors

Vision sensors as a combination of different types of sensors (RGB, multispectral, thermal, 2D, 3D, etc). It is an array of cameras and sensors for image and signal capture, information transfer and the software responsible for image processing and analysis.

Vision sensors are advanced imaging devices that integrate cameras, processors, and software to capture and analyse visual data. These sensors are capable of identifying objects, detecting patterns, and verifying quality in industrial and agricultural processes. They operate autonomously without requiring external computational systems, making them essential for automation.¹²⁴

Pros of technology:

- **Time and cost savings.** Real-time data analysis allows you to quickly react and adjust the process of, for example, spraying or fertilizing to the current state and quality, health of weeds on the plantation or in the field,
- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data:** Real-time data analysis allows for a quick response and adjustment of the action to the momentary, local situation.
- **Real-time operation.**
- **Adaptability and flexibility:** vision systems can be easily reconfigured and adapted to changing work conditions, allowing rapid introduction of new products without costly changes to existing equipment and infrastructure.
- **Safety improving:** In the field of safety, vision systems can compliance with safety procedures by workers preparing solutions for spraying and for spraying vehicles and devices for carrying out plant protection and fertilization treatments, where chemically active and health-hazardous substances are used.
- **Interchangeability of components:** Possibility of interchangeable use in one system of many different types of cameras adapted to the parameters to be analysed.
- **Accuracy:** High precision in object recognition and navigation in complex environments.
- **Versatility:** The ability to detect a variety of parameters, such as fruit maturity or the presence of weeds.

Cons of technology:

¹²⁴ Vision sensors: <https://tiny.pl/pg15n7gq>

- **Variable, depending on the operating conditions, precision of the vision systems**, depending, for example, on the stability of the camera mounts and the stability of the entire machine during its working movements, driving through the plantation, cultivation,
- **Complexity**: Requires advanced data processing and AI algorithms, which adds cost and complexity to the system.
- **Weather sensitivity**: May be less effective in difficult lighting or weather conditions.
- **Data transmission**: problems with correct and fast data transmission and storage due to the often-large amount of data generated by the video system.
- **Sensitivity to dirt**: the need to keep the lens clean for good image quality, particularly important in field conditions.
- **Cost**: the purchase of a complete system and its on-going maintenance can generate large costs, which increase depending on its parameters, and it may be necessary to purchase an additional computer to operate the system and to store the data generated by the system.

Future Directions

Emerging trends in vision sensor technology are focused on improving integration with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), creating smarter and more connected systems. These advancements are driving progress in several key areas:

- **Cost Reduction**: Innovations aim to lower the expenses of components and implementation, making advanced systems more accessible to diverse industries.
- **Machine Learning**: Enhanced algorithms enable systems to adapt to variable conditions and tackle non-standard applications, such as recognizing unique patterns or optimizing tasks in dynamic environments.
- **Big Data Analysis**: The vast amounts of data generated by vision sensors and related technologies can be processed to uncover hidden trends and relationships. Such insights help optimize production processes, predict crop conditions, and implement proactive measures against potential risks, such as early signs of adverse crop development.
- **Increasing AI Efficiency**: Advances in machine learning and artificial intelligence improve decision-making and connectivity. This enhances applications like predictive maintenance, smart farming, and automated quality control.

The combination of these developments positions vision sensors as a cornerstone of modern automation and innovation, with significant potential for industrial, agricultural, and environmental advancements.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Vision sensors help optimize resource usage by reducing waste and improving operational efficiency. This contributes to sustainable practices, particularly in agriculture and manufacturing. They also lower long-term costs by enhancing quality control.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects)

The Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) of vision sensor technology are critical considerations for ensuring responsible development and deployment. These aspects become particularly relevant as vision sensors are increasingly used in applications such as autonomous vehicles, healthcare, surveillance, and agriculture. Below are some key points related to ELSA in vision sensors:

In agriculture, vision sensors are used for precision farming, monitoring crops, and automating harvesting. ELSA considerations in this domain include:

- **Ethics:** Ensuring sensors respect farmers' data ownership and privacy.
- **Legal:** Defining clear rights over agricultural data collected by these sensors.
- **Social:** Addressing concerns about accessibility for smallholder farmers and minimizing the digital divide.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- Test of the integration of vision systems with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the effectiveness of automating operations such as mechanical weed destruction between rows and between plants in the row, spot spraying, seeding or fertilization.
- Integration with Robotic Systems: Checking the integration of vision systems with agricultural robots in real time, assessing the efficiency of automation operations such as mechanical weed destruction between rows and between plants in a row, spot spraying, sowing or fertilizing.
- Evaluation of the repeatability of the results of measurements and control of the operation of autonomous equipment.
- Resistance to interference and integration of system elements for specific applications and specific agricultural tools.
- Object recognition: Vision tests in the field with different plants and weeds, evaluation of the efficiency and accuracy of recognition.
- Lighting Conditions: Tests under different lighting conditions (day, night, fog), assessment of the impact on image quality.
- Integration with AI Algorithms: Performance evaluation of image processing and artificial intelligence algorithms under real field conditions.

Vision sensors, with their advanced optical sensing capabilities, offer high accuracy, real-time processing, and versatility. They are indispensable in various fields, including industrial automation, autonomous vehicles, security, and healthcare, providing critical visual data for decision-making and automation. These trends illustrate the growing importance of vision sensors in various industries, particularly in automation and precision agriculture, where they help optimize operations, enhance productivity, and ensure sustainability.

LiDAR Sensors

LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) sensors are a type of remote sensing technology that uses laser beams to measure distances by emitting pulses of light. The light travels to a target object, bounces off, and returns to the sensor. By measuring the time it takes for the light to bounce back, LiDAR can calculate the distance between the sensor and the detected object. This data is then used to create detailed 3D maps of surfaces and objects. LiDAR sensors typically emit near-infrared waves, which can measure distances, including variable ones, with high precision.

LiDAR technology combines various types of sensors and is used across multiple industries, from autonomous vehicles, where it aids in navigation, to agriculture, where it helps with precise crop mapping and terrain modeling. LiDAR's ability to capture accurate topographical data allows for better management of agricultural resources and provides detailed insights into terrain and crop conditions. This makes it an essential tool for applications that require high spatial accuracy.¹²⁵

Pros of technology:

¹²⁵ LiDAR Sensors: https://tiny.pl/26vfn9_r

- **Light-independent:** The ability to work in a ground or aerial system. Depending on the need, the device can be mounted on a flying unit either on a tripod or on a vehicle, such as an autonomous vehicle,
- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data.** Real-time data analysis allows for quick response,
- **Lighting independence:** They perform their function both day and night, without interferences caused by shadows, sunlight glare from the headlights of vehicles from the opposite direction,
- **Data Analysis speed:** The analysis of measurement results in their case is much simpler and faster than in the case of visual images, if, of course, only object detection and not object classification is taken into account,
- **Precision:** highly accurate terrain mapping and obstacle detection. High resolution of acquired data: The current parameters of available scanners, range and angular resolution (100 m, 0.1°) meet the requirements for increasing vehicle autonomy,
- An accurate mapping of the landscape on a plantation or crop allowing the acceptance or verification of previously acquired autonomous vehicle tracks.

Cons of technology:

- **Inability to recognize colours and interpret inscriptions:** This can cause a problem in identifying obstacles, assessing the health of plants,
- **Air humidity impact:** Lasers, especially those with a wavelength of 1550 nm, which provide a more accurate measurement, are more dispersed by moisture in the atmosphere. Therefore, in case of adverse weather conditions, problems with accuracy can be expected and must put up with lower scanning resolution.
- **Possibility of eye damages:** Laser beams, especially those with a wavelength of 905 nm, can damage the lenses of the eyes if they come within the field of vision of the eye,
- **High energy consumption:** Increasing with the wavelength and the number of laser pulses sent, higher for 10550 nm wavelength,
- **Cost:** High cost of Lidar sensors,
- **Weight and complexity:** Lidars sensors can be heavy and complicated to integrate into robotic systems.

Future Directions

LiDAR technology is evolving rapidly, with several key trends shaping its future. These include:

- **Miniaturization:** Efforts to reduce the size and cost of LiDAR units aim to make them more accessible for widespread use, including in sectors like agriculture, autonomous vehicles, and infrastructure.
- **Integration with AI and IoT:** The integration of LiDAR with artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) is enhancing real-time data processing, enabling smarter decision-making. This enables applications like smart farming, predictive maintenance, and optimized resource management.
- **Improved Accuracy:** Advancements in laser and sensor technology are increasing the precision and resolution of LiDAR data, which will enhance applications such as crop health monitoring, terrain analysis, and environmental modeling.

In addition to these trends, ongoing cost reduction innovations are focused on making LiDAR components and implementations more affordable. Moreover, machine learning is improving the functionality of LiDAR systems, allowing them to adapt to variable conditions and non-standard applications, such as identifying specific patterns or objects in diverse environments. These developments will make LiDAR technology even more versatile and valuable across various industries.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

LiDAR technology contributes to sustainability in several key ways:

- **Resource Optimization:** LiDAR enables precise resource management, reducing waste by allowing for better decision-making and resource allocation. In agriculture, it helps farmers manage water usage, optimize irrigation, and minimize the use of fertilizers and pesticides.
- **Environmental Monitoring:** By providing detailed data on terrain and vegetation, LiDAR plays an essential role in environmental conservation and management. It helps monitor ecosystem health, track deforestation, and manage biodiversity.
- **Sustainable Farming Practices:** LiDAR aids in sustainable farming by optimizing resource usage and minimizing environmental impact. Its precision improves crop yield, reduces water consumption, and enables more efficient land management and fertilization.
- **Economic Benefits:** The technology improves productivity and efficiency across industries, providing economic benefits by reducing operational costs and increasing output. In agriculture, this leads to higher crop yields and more sustainable farming practices, driving economic growth and sustainability.

These applications collectively contribute to the broader goals of sustainability, enhancing both environmental protection and economic efficiency.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects)

Ethical Aspects:

- **Privacy Concerns:** LiDAR data collection raises privacy issues, especially in urban environments.
- **Data Security:** Ensuring the security and confidentiality of collected data.

Legal Aspects:

- **Regulations:** Compliance with local and international regulations regarding data collection and use.
- **Intellectual Property:** Protecting innovations and technological advancements in LiDAR systems.

Social Aspects:

- **Public Acceptance:** Building public trust and acceptance of LiDAR technology.
- **Education:** Promoting education and awareness about the benefits and applications of LiDAR.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Signal stability:** Tests of signal stability transmitted to receivers under various atmospheric, terrain conditions, and operating conditions (dustiness, haze).
- **Integration with autonomous systems:** Verification of the integration of Lidar systems with autonomous agricultural vehicles for their autonomous navigation over the area of fields, crops, plantations.
- **3D Mapping:** Creating 3D terrain maps and comparing them with reference data.
- **Obstacle detection:** Testing the effectiveness of obstacle detection in the field under different conditions (e.g., different vegetation types, terrain slopes).
- **Autonomous navigation:** Testing the navigation precision of autonomous robots using LiDAR under real field conditions.

LiDAR technology is poised to revolutionize industries by offering high-precision data collection and 3D modeling capabilities. In agriculture, its integration with other technologies, such as AI and IoT, opens the door to smart farming solutions that enhance efficiency, reduce waste, and increase productivity. However, the high initial cost and

environmental limitations must be addressed to make LiDAR more accessible and practical for wider use. As technology evolves, the miniaturization and further integration of LiDAR will likely lower costs and expand its applications, making it a critical tool for sustainable practices in agriculture and other industries.

Multisystem for object recognition and mapping (mix of different technologies: vision sensors, LiDAR sensors)

Multisystem for object recognition and mapping combine the functionality of two different systems-vision and LiDAR technology-to enhance the precision and quality of the data acquired. These multisystem technologies integrate data from both vision sensors and LiDAR sensors, which allows them to offer enhanced capabilities for object recognition and detailed mapping. Vision sensors capture visual data, such as images and video, while LiDAR sensors use laser pulses to measure distances, creating 3D models of the terrain or objects. By combining these sensor types, multisystem provide more accurate and comprehensive information about the environment, enabling better decision-making and insights.

This integration is particularly valuable in complex or dynamic environments such as agriculture, autonomous vehicles, and robotics, where accurate object recognition and environmental mapping are essential. The synergy between vision and LiDAR sensors results in a more complete understanding of surroundings, making these multisystem solutions ideal for tasks that require high precision and real-time data processing.

- **Principle of Operation:** Vision sensors capture visual information through cameras or other imaging devices, processing it into images or video. LiDAR sensors emit pulses of laser light that bounce off objects, returning to the sensor, allowing the calculation of precise distances. Combining both technologies allows for accurate mapping (from 2D to 3D) and real-time object recognition.
- **Applications:** Multisystem recognition and mapping technologies are applied in various fields, including:
 - Agriculture: For crop health monitoring, terrain modeling, and resource optimization.
 - Autonomous Vehicles: For navigation, collision avoidance, and environment mapping.
 - Robotics: For navigation and object detection in dynamic environments.
 - Geospatial Mapping: For detailed 3D topographical models and urban planning.

Pros of technology:

- **High efficiency and quality of transmitted data.** Real-time data analysis allows for quick response,
- **Independence from lighting:** Fulfil their function both day and night, without interferences caused by shadows, sunlight or blinding by the light of oncoming vehicle headlights,
- **Speed of data analysis:** The analysis of measurement results is much simpler and faster in their case than for visual images, if, of course, only object detection and not object classification is taken into account,
- **Adaptability to change:** The multisystem nature of navigation data collection and processing allows devices to respond dynamically to changing environmental conditions,
- **Wide operating ranges:** allows mapping in limited areas not covered by GPS navigation.
- **Exact mapping of a landscape or field:** that allows autonomous vehicles to accept or verify previously obtained driving traces.
- **Enhanced Accuracy:** Combining vision and LiDAR provides a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of the environment.

- **Versatility:** The technology can be used across various industries, including agriculture, robotics, and autonomous vehicles.
- **Better Decision-Making:** Real-time mapping and recognition enable better management and control over operations.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Over time, the integration of these technologies can reduce costs by optimizing resource use and improving operational efficiency.

Cons of technology:

- **High computing power of the system:** Proper real-time operation of the system requires very high computing power and proper overlapping of point clouds generated from information acquired from cameras and sensors;
- **Device costs:** Obtaining the right depth of image requires the use of a multi-camera system and considerable computing power, which affects the cost of the entire control system.
- **Inaccuracy of the position of the autonomous device:** In the case of inability to determine the exact location of the device in the field, its localization error remains variable, since it is based on the last known position and alignment of the robot. Therefore, in such a case, it is necessary to both determine the position on the map and create a new section of the map for the new terrain,
- **Possibility of intentional interference with the system:** For example, by the military,
- **Air humidity impact:** Lasers, especially those with a wavelength of 1550 nm, which provide a more accurate measurement, are more dispersed by moisture in the atmosphere. Therefore, in case of adverse weather conditions, problems with accuracy can be expected and one has to reconcile with lower scanning resolution,
- **Possibility of eye damages:** Laser beams, especially those with a wavelength of 905 nm, can damage the lenses of the eyes if they come within the field of vision of the eye,
- **Inability to recognize colours and interpret inscriptions:** This can cause problems in identifying obstacles, assessing the health of plants,
- **Weight and complexity:** The combination of several systems leads to significant complexity in their integration with robotic systems and it increases the weight of the equipment (devices and their additional elements) that must be mounted on devices, vehicles that are to be controlled.

Future Directions

The future of multisystem object recognition and mapping technologies is promising, with several key advancements expected to shape the landscape:

- **Integration with AI:** By incorporating artificial intelligence (AI), these systems will enhance real-time decision-making, adaptive learning, and pattern recognition. AI integration will allow multisystem to respond more intelligently to environmental changes and evolving conditions, leading to smarter, more autonomous systems.
- **Miniaturization:** Efforts to reduce the size and cost of multisystem technologies will make them more accessible, enabling broader adoption. Smaller, more affordable systems will find applications in drones, handheld devices, and other compact platforms, expanding their usability across industries.
- **Improved Sensors:** As vision and LiDAR sensor technologies continue to develop, we can expect enhanced accuracy and better adaptability to various environments. Improved sensors will lead to more precise data collection, which is critical for tasks requiring high precision, such as agriculture and autonomous navigation.

- **AI-Driven Analytics:** Machine learning will play a significant role in analysing multisystem data, offering deeper insights that can optimize operations in fields like agriculture. With the ability to process large amounts of data, AI-driven analytics will support smarter farming, predictive maintenance, and better resource management.

Additionally, innovations will focus on:

- **Cost Reduction:** Reducing the costs of components and implementation to make multisystem solutions more affordable and scalable.
- **Machine Learning:** Enhancing the functionality of systems through machine learning, allowing them to adapt to variable conditions and recognize non-standard patterns, improving their efficiency in diverse applications.
- **Standardization of Data Transfer:** Ensuring seamless communication between different devices and sensors will be key in improving system interoperability and data sharing, enabling more coherent and integrated operations.

These advancements promise to expand the capabilities of multisystem technologies, making them more cost-effective, efficient, and adaptable to a range of real-world applications.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Multisystem technologies for object recognition and mapping significantly contribute to sustainability by enabling better resource management and reducing waste. These systems play a vital role in precision agriculture, where they help monitor crop health, soil conditions, and water usage. By gathering detailed data, multisystem ensure that resources are used efficiently, which leads to more sustainable farming practices. Environmental monitoring capabilities also allow for improved conservation and management of natural resources.

Economically, multisystem technologies bring substantial benefits. They help improve operational efficiency, increase productivity, and optimize resource usage. In industries such as agriculture, this translates into higher yields, reduced operational costs, and more efficient operations, all of which lead to long-term economic gains. By driving cost reduction, optimizing processes, and promoting sustainability, these technologies provide both environmental and economic advantages, making them a key driver for sustainable growth across various sectors.

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects)

- While multisystem technologies for object recognition and mapping offer significant advantages, they also raise ethical, legal, and social concerns that must be addressed to ensure responsible and sustainable development.

Ethical Aspects:

- **Privacy Concerns:** The extensive data collection through vision and LiDAR sensors can lead to privacy issues, especially in urban and agricultural environments. In agriculture, for example, monitoring crops and livestock using these sensors might unintentionally capture personal information, raising concerns about surveillance and privacy.
- **Data Security:** With vast amounts of data being collected and processed, ensuring the security and confidentiality of this data is essential. Robust security measures must be in place to prevent misuse or unauthorized access to sensitive information.

Legal Aspects:

- **Regulations:** Multisystem technologies must comply with local and international regulations regarding data collection, usage, and sharing. Adherence to these legal frameworks is crucial to protect individual rights and ensure responsible deployment of such technologies.

- **Intellectual Property:** As multisystem technologies evolve, protecting intellectual property (IP) becomes increasingly important. This includes safeguarding innovations in sensor technology, data processing algorithms, and overall system designs to ensure that creators and companies can benefit from their technological advancements.

Social Aspects:

- **Public Acceptance:** For multisystem technologies to be widely adopted, building public trust is key. Transparency in how data is collected and used, as well as demonstrating the benefits to society, can help gain public acceptance and support.
- **Education:** Raising awareness and educating the public, particularly in sectors like agriculture, about the potential benefits and applications of multisystem technologies is vital. This helps foster a better understanding of the technologies and their role in sustainable development.
- Additional concerns include the **potential for job displacement** as automation enabled by these technologies may replace certain jobs in agriculture and related industries. Addressing these challenges requires thoughtful consideration of workforce impacts and the development of strategies to reskill affected workers.
- In conclusion, while multisystem technologies hold great promise, ensuring their ethical, legal, and social responsibility is essential for their successful and sustainable integration into society.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Signal stability:** Tests of signal stability transmitted to receivers under various atmospheric, terrain conditions, and operating conditions (dustiness, haze).
- **Integration with Autonomous Systems:** Verification of the integration of Lidar systems with autonomous agricultural vehicles for their autonomous navigation over the area of fields, crops, plantations.
- **3D Mapping:** Creating 3D terrain maps and comparing them with reference data.
- **Obstacle detection:** Testing the effectiveness of obstacle detection in the field under different conditions (e.g., different vegetation types, terrain slopes).
- **Autonomous navigation:** Testing the navigation precision of autonomous robots using LiDAR under real field conditions.
- **Compatibility:** Compatibility tests, the cooperation of systems forming one positioning and guidance system installed on the tested autonomous vehicle.

Multisystem technologies for object recognition and mapping, which integrate vision sensors and LiDAR, represent a significant advancement in environmental sensing, offering exceptional accuracy and reliability across various applications. By combining the strengths of both sensor types, these systems enhance precision in areas such as agriculture, robotics, and autonomous vehicles. In agriculture, for example, multisystem improve resource management, crop monitoring, and minimize environmental impact. The technology's ability to provide detailed data makes it indispensable for efficient and sustainable farming practices.

While multisystem solutions hold immense promise, challenges such as high initial costs, complexity, and data management issues may hinder their widespread adoption. However, ongoing advancements, including the integration of AI and the improvement of sensor technologies, are expected to address these barriers. These innovations will make multisystem solutions more accessible, reducing costs and increasing their effectiveness.

The potential for multisystem technologies to revolutionize industries, especially agriculture, underscores their importance in driving sustainability, efficiency, and innovation. Nonetheless, ethical, legal, and social considerations must also be taken into account to ensure the responsible use of these technologies. Their successful integration depends on addressing not only the technical aspects but also the societal impacts, ensuring that multisystem contribute positively to various sectors while minimizing negative effects.

Soil Humidity Sensors

Soil humidity sensors are devices designed to measure the moisture content of the soil. These sensors typically work by detecting changes in electrical conductivity, capacitance, or resistance in the soil, which varies with its moisture level. The sensor sends an electrical signal through the soil and analyses the response, providing data on how much moisture is present. They are widely used in agriculture, horticulture, and environmental research to monitor soil moisture levels, optimizing water usage, and promoting efficient irrigation systems.^{126, 127}

Pros of soil humidity sensors technology:¹²⁸

- **Precision:** The ability to obtain precise data on nutrients, pH, moisture, and other key soil parameters,
- **Fertilizer optimization:** Gaining the ability to adjust fertilizer levels to the specific needs of the soil, resulting in better yields, thereby avoiding over-application of fertilizers and crop protection products, reducing production costs,
- **Personalized maps:** Obtain soil maps showing the current soil diversity in a given field. Based on these maps, crop placement, fertilization and other work can be planned with greater precision.¹²⁹

Cons of soil humidity sensors technology:

- **System costs:** Quite high costs of purchasing system components.
- **Sampling time:** The sampling time for a single soil sample ranges from a few to several minutes, depending on the size of the plot and its configuration. For large plantation/crop areas and multiple samples, it can take up to several days.
- **Requires regular calibration:** Needs maintenance to ensure accuracy.
- **Soil variability:** Performance can vary with different soil types.¹³⁰

Future Directions:

- The future of soil humidity sensors is shaped by several key trends and technological developments. One of the most significant directions is the **advancement in wireless sensor networks**, which will enable real-time data collection and remote monitoring capabilities, enhancing the efficiency of irrigation systems. Coupled with **IoT integration**, this will allow automated irrigation solutions, where sensors can communicate directly with irrigation systems, adjusting water levels based on real-time moisture data.

¹²⁶ Rooted in Data: The Impact of Soil Sensors on Agricultural Productivity: <https://husfarm.com/article/rooted-in-data-the-impact-of-soil-sensors-on-agricultural-productivity>

¹²⁷ Understanding Soil Sensors and Their Role in Sustainable Agriculture: <https://husfarm.com/article/soil-sensors-and-sustainability-predicting-their-impact-on-crop-prices>

¹²⁸ Tornese, I., Matera, A., Rashvand, M., & Genovese, F. (2024). Use of Probes and Sensors in Agriculture - Current Trends and Future Prospects on Intelligent Monitoring of Soil Moisture and Nutrients. *AgriEngineering*, 6(4), 4154-4181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriengineering6040234>

¹²⁹ Advantages and disadvantages of soil moisture sensor: <https://www.niubol.com/Product-knowledge/Advantages-and-disadvantages-of-soil-moisture-sensor.html>

¹³⁰ Advantages and Disadvantages of Soil Moisture Sensor: <https://aspiringyouths.com/advantages-disadvantages/soil-moisture-sensor/>

- Additionally, the use of **advanced data analytics** powered by **AI and machine learning** is set to revolutionize how moisture data is analyzed, predicting irrigation needs with greater accuracy and optimizing water usage. This shift will also contribute to **cost reduction**, as innovations continue to lower the cost of components and implementation, making these technologies more accessible to farmers of all scales.
- The trend toward **wireless connectivity** will further simplify the deployment and monitoring of soil moisture sensors. By enabling data transmission to cloud-based systems, farmers will have access to real-time insights from anywhere, improving management decisions. New **advanced materials** are also being developed to enhance sensor durability and accuracy, ensuring reliable performance in diverse environmental conditions.
- As AI and machine learning become more integrated with these technologies, they will enable predictive modeling, helping farmers optimize water usage, reduce waste, and improve overall sustainability. The combination of these trends points towards a future where soil humidity sensors play an even more pivotal role in smart farming, driving both operational efficiency and environmental sustainability.¹³¹

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Soil humidity sensors play a crucial role in promoting sustainable agriculture by enabling precise irrigation management, which conserves water and reduces waste. By optimizing the use of water and nutrients, these sensors improve resource efficiency, thus mitigating the risk of soil degradation and over-irrigation. This contributes to water conservation and resource optimization, essential for maintaining environmental health.

Economically, soil humidity sensors offer significant benefits. They help farmers lower operational costs associated with water consumption and fertilizer use by ensuring crops receive the right amount of water at the right time. This leads to increased crop yields, which in turn improves profitability. By reducing costs tied to over-irrigation and addressing water scarcity challenges, these sensors provide an economically viable solution that supports both profitability and sustainability in agriculture.¹³²

ELSA (Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects) for soil humidity sensors

Ethical Aspects:

The use of soil humidity sensors raises several ethical concerns, including:

- **Data Privacy:** As these sensors collect detailed data from farms, concerns about the privacy and security of this information arise, especially when data from multiple farms could be shared or sold. Transparency and consent are essential for ethical data collection practices.
- **Fair Access:** Ensuring that both smallholder and large-scale farmers have access to this technology is a key issue, preventing any technological divide that may limit smaller operators from benefiting.
- **Environmental Impact:** Consideration must be given to the environmental footprint of sensor materials and their disposal, ensuring that these technologies do not contribute to unnecessary waste or pollution.

Legal Aspects:

- **Regulations:** Compliance with local, national, and international regulations regarding data collection and use is crucial. Laws around data privacy and environmental protection must be adhered to when implementing these systems.

¹³¹ Bogena, H. R., Weuthen, A., & Huisman, J. A. (2022). Recent Developments in Wireless Soil Moisture Sensing to Support Scientific Research and Agricultural Management. *Sensors*, 22(24), 9792. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22249792>

¹³² Soil Sensors and Market Sensibility: <https://husfarm.com/article/soil-sensors-and-market-sensibility-the-economic-impact-of-precision-agriculture>

- **Intellectual Property:** Protecting the intellectual property of innovations in soil humidity sensor technologies is necessary to encourage continued research and development. Patents and copyrights must ensure fair usage without stifling innovation.

Social Aspects:

- **Public Acceptance:** Building public trust is vital for the widespread adoption of soil humidity sensors. As the technology becomes more integrated into farming practices, ensuring that the public understands and accepts its benefits will foster greater engagement.
- **Education:** Promoting education and raising awareness about the applications and advantages of soil humidity sensors is critical to ensuring that farmers understand how to use the technology effectively.
- **Inequalities:** The rapid deployment of soil humidity sensors could exacerbate existing inequalities, especially between small-scale and large-scale farmers. To maintain fairness, it's crucial that policies are implemented to ensure equitable access to these technologies.

Together, these ethical, legal, and social considerations form a framework that ensures the responsible adoption and deployment of soil humidity sensors in agricultural practices, fostering sustainability and fairness in the industry.¹³³

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Soil quality:** Soil quality tests to verify other methods used for surface soil quality assessment in cultivated fields,
- **Integration with other applications:** Verify the use of research results in other applications that show the abundance of fields and supervise the operation of cultivation, seeding or fertilization or irrigation machinery.
- **Field Mapping:** Creating field maps for the purpose of conducting soil quality measurements, comparison with reference data.
- **Sampling and analysis:** Efficiency tests and time of soil sample collection in the field under various conditions (e.g., different types of vegetation, terrain slopes) and their transfer for analysis.
- **Measurement, evaluations of weather components:** Measurements of selected weather components. (humidity, temperature, cloudiness, etc.) in real field conditions.

Soil humidity sensors play a crucial role in modern agriculture, offering significant benefits for improving water conservation, irrigation efficiency, and crop management. These sensors help optimize water use, reduce waste, and boost crop yields, driving the future of sustainable farming practices. As technology continues to advance, soil humidity sensors are becoming more affordable, accurate, and accessible, contributing to the broader goal of improving agricultural productivity and sustainability.

Despite their advantages, challenges such as initial costs, maintenance, and the need for proper data management remain. However, ongoing technological improvements are expected to address these issues, enhancing their usability and efficiency. Furthermore, the deployment of these sensors must be accompanied by careful consideration of ethical, legal, and social factors to ensure equitable access and responsible use. This includes addressing data privacy concerns, ensuring compliance with regulations, and fostering public acceptance to avoid inequalities between small and large-scale farmers.

¹³³ Wei, H., Xu, W., Kang, B. et al. Irrigation with Artificial Intelligence: Problems, Premises, Promises. Hum-Cent Intell Syst 4, 187-205 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44230-024-00072-4>

In conclusion, soil humidity sensors hold immense potential to revolutionize agricultural practices, offering a sustainable solution to water management and crop optimization. Their continued development will support the long-term goals of enhancing resource efficiency and promoting environmental sustainability while ensuring fairness in their distribution and use.

Livestock Handling Tools

Livestock handling tools that integrate sensors, drones, robots, and cameras have revolutionized farm management, allowing farmers to track and manage animal behaviour more effectively. These tools provide real-time data that aids in decision-making, from monitoring animal health to detecting behavioural patterns, thereby improving animal welfare. By ensuring controlled environments and reducing the risk of injury, these technologies help optimize farm operations, enhance productivity, and support sustainable practices. The combination of smart technologies and traditional tools leads to more efficient, humane, and sustainable livestock management, making them essential for both large-scale and family-run farms. As the technology advances, we can expect more seamless integration of these systems, contributing to the future of farming and animal care.

Common Applications:

- **Animal Movement and Control:** Tools such as gates, chutes, and fences help guide and confine animals for routine tasks or transportation.
- **Health and Welfare:** Proper handling tools ensure safe medical procedures, reducing stress and injury to livestock.
- **Efficiency and Productivity:** Livestock handling systems improve the overall efficiency of farm operations, ensuring smoother workflows when managing animals.

These tools are essential for creating safe, efficient, and humane environments for both animals and workers, contributing to better productivity and welfare in the agri-food industry.

Pros of technology: ¹³⁴

- **Real-time operation:** Ongoing, continuous monitoring and reporting of relevant health parameters of animals, livestock housing, etc. allows to control the health status of animals in real time and react quickly in case of any changes and problems.
- **Multitasking:** A significant part of the indicated devices has the ability control multiple environmental and animal health parameters.
- **Simplicity of assembly and use:** Most of the presented devices and control systems are simple to assemble or install and operate, largely operating unmanned once mounted or installed.
- **Enhances animal welfare:** Minimizes stress and discomfort.
- **Improves safety:** Proper livestock handling reduces the risk of injury to both animals and handlers.
- **Increases efficiency:** Streamlined processes lead to faster operations and better use of time.
- **Animal Welfare:** Tools designed with animal comfort in mind can reduce stress and injuries.

Cons of technology:

- **System costs:** In cases of automatic devices for dedicated work: milking parlors, robots for feeding, waste and manure removal, quite high costs of purchasing system components (devices). High-quality livestock handling systems can be expensive to purchase and maintain.

¹³⁴ The Role of Livestock Handling Facilities in Efficient Cattle Management: <https://husfarm.com/article/the-role-of-livestock-handling-facilities-in-efficient-cattle-management>

- **Targeted application:** Some of the animal health parameter control systems are systemically oriented only for use to the control of a specific type of animal, such as poultry, pigs, cattle.
- **Complexity:** Some systems require skilled personnel and training to operate effectively.
- **Maintenance:** Proper upkeep is necessary to ensure the longevity and efficiency of the tools.

Future Directions

Future developments in livestock handling tools are focusing on reducing costs, enhancing functionality, and integrating new technologies.¹³⁵

Key trends include:

- **Cost Reduction:** Innovations aim to reduce both component and implementation costs, making livestock handling tools more accessible to a broader range of farmers.
- **Unification of Applications:** Efforts are underway to expand the versatility of handling tools, allowing them to work with a wider variety of animals and incorporate additional functionalities, enhancing their utility across different farming operations.
- **Automation and Robotics:** The integration of AI and robotics is expected to play a major role in automating tasks such as animal movement and behaviour management, minimizing human labour and reducing stress on animals.
- **Smart Systems:** Advancements in wireless systems using sensors to monitor animal health, behaviour, and location in real-time are increasing, providing farmers with actionable insights for better decision-making.
- **Sustainability and Eco-friendly Materials:** The shift towards more sustainable, durable materials in livestock handling equipment is growing, addressing the environmental impact of farming practices.
- **Data Integration:** Tools that analyse real-time data on animal health, weight, and behaviour are being developed, improving management decisions and enabling better animal welfare practices.

As these advancements continue, livestock handling tools will become more efficient, eco-friendly, and versatile, driving progress in animal welfare and farm productivity.

Impact on sustainability and economic viability:

Livestock handling tools contribute to the sustainability of farming by improving animal welfare, reducing resource waste, and enhancing farm efficiency. These tools:

- **Reduce Waste and Injury:** By minimizing stress and injuries during animal handling, the risk of losses is lowered, contributing to more sustainable farming practices.
- **Lower Costs:** They improve the efficiency of handling processes, reducing operating costs, labour requirements, and the need for manual interventions.
- **Improve Animal Health:** Proper tools reduce stress on livestock, which not only ensures better animal welfare but also boosts production rates and overall health.

In summary, livestock handling tools are vital for promoting sustainability, as they help reduce waste, lower costs, and enhance the health of animals, thus leading to more efficient and ethical farming operations.

¹³⁵ The Future of Livestock Handling: Innovations, technology, and sustainable practices:

<https://agrimachinery.africa/technologies/the-future-of-livestock-handling-innovations-technology-and-sustainable-practices/>

ELSA (Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects) of Livestock Handling Tools

Ethical Aspects:

- **Animal Welfare:** Livestock handling tools must be designed to ensure humane treatment, with a strong focus on minimizing stress and injury to animals. Tools should help in creating a safe and comfortable environment for the animals, enhancing both their health and productivity.
- **Data Privacy:** In the case of automated or sensor-based systems used for tracking and monitoring animal health, data privacy concerns must be addressed. Farmers and stakeholders should ensure transparency about data collection and provide protection against misuse.

Legal Aspects:

- **Regulations:** Compliance with animal welfare laws is essential in the design and use of livestock handling tools. These laws include guidelines on humane treatment, animal transport, and farm worker safety. Adhering to local and international animal welfare standards ensures ethical practices and legal protection.
- **Intellectual Property:** As innovations in automation and livestock handling technologies grow, intellectual property rights play a critical role in protecting new developments while promoting fair competition and responsible innovation.

Social Aspects:

- **Public Perception:** Public concern about animal welfare is influencing the farming industry. Livestock handling tools must align with ethical farming practices to maintain consumer trust and social license. Transparent practices and proper handling procedures can help foster positive relationships between farms and the broader community.
- **Education and Training:** It is important to educate farmers and handlers on the humane and efficient use of livestock handling tools. Proper training ensures that farmers adopt best practices, enhancing animal welfare and optimizing farm operations.

Potential agrifoodTEF services and scope:

- **Animal welfare:** Tests to determine the level of animal welfare,
- **Integration with other applications:** check, verify use of test results in other in other animal welfare applications.
- **Measurement, evaluation of environmental components:** Measurements of selected components of the animal's environment (humidity, temperature, etc.) in real conditions of livestock buildings.
- **Measurement, evaluation of animal welfare control devices:** Adjustment of parameters to different types of animals, their age, etc., evaluation of the possibility of device operation during the stay of animals outside livestock buildings
- **Functionality of automatic and autonomous devices:** Measurements of the operating parameters of these devices, adjusting their parameters to specific working conditions and animal requirements or conditions, such as those resulting from the construction of livestock buildings or their additional equipment.

7 Business industry outlook and company challenges

7.1 Business industry outlook

Investment stagnation

In 2023 and 2024, investments in innovative startups and the development of solutions in the agricultural sector have stalled, despite a few exceptions. These investments are even lower than during the COVID-19 period. On the other hand, the factors that caused this investor retreat are the same for the entire market: This is economic uncertainty produced by the fact that global economy has faced significant challenges, including inflation and geopolitical tensions, which have made investors and SMEs more cautious. The other significant factor is disruption of supply chains. Ongoing disruptions in supply chains have increased costs and reduced the availability of necessary materials and technologies for agricultural innovation. The looming trade war between the USA and China only reinforces these concerns. Another important reason for the aversion to investing in the development of innovations in the agricultural sector is shift of priorities. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a heightened focus on food security and sustainability, leading to increased investments in agriculture. However, post-pandemic, priorities have shifted towards other sectors such as healthcare and the defence sector. Last but not least are regulatory challenges and policies aimed at promoting sustainability and reducing environmental impact, which have sometimes slowed down the adoption of new agricultural technologies.

It is not negligible that there are ongoing processes in the farming sector itself. The consolidation process results in a reduced number of small and medium-sized farms, which are often more innovative and willing to adopt new technologies.

Figure 11. Global agrifood investment by year.
Source: own compilation based on data from the AgriTech Report 2024¹³⁶.

On the other hand as the global population continues to rise and environmental challenges intensify, the AgriTech and FoodTech sectors are adopting innovative technologies and sustainable methods. By leveraging advanced data analytics,

¹³⁶ AgriTech Report 2024: <https://research.agfunder.com/agfunder-global-agrifoodtech-investment-report-2024-1.pdf>

biotechnology, automation, and technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), and blockchain, AgriTech and FoodTech are revolutionizing traditional agriculture and the food industry.

Although 2023 and first half of 2024 was a challenging period, investors highlighted the potential of innovation and the need for further development of technologies for agriculture and food processing. Hopes for market improvement are tied to rebuilding confidence in 2025.

Another important, if not decisive, element for European companies in the FoodTech and AgriTech sectors will be preparations for changes brought about by regulations that alter or directly impact farming and cultivation methods. The principles of the Green Deal, changing pesticide use, fertilization, and the move away from monocultures, will have a direct impact on the development and adaptation of technologies. The market is beginning to prepare for these changes, mainly by developing solutions that can contribute to reducing resource consumption and being sustainable. This may also explain why, despite the global decline in investments in modern agrifood solutions, Europe experienced a relatively small decrease of investments y/y by 14% compared to the rest of the world.

From the same reason investments in new products in farm robotics, mechanization and equipment continued its steady upward trajectory of the past five years, increasing 9% year-over-year to almost 800 million EUR.

The Years of Transition and Consolidation

Corporate Dominance is expected to surge as large corporations, seeking innovation and new growth avenues, take a more prominent role in shaping the sector, especially as traditional venture capital funds struggle with fundraising. This trend could lead to more strategic acquisitions and partnerships between startups and established companies. The Profitability Imperative marks the end of the era where growth was prioritized over profit. Investors will focus on companies that demonstrate a clear path to profitability and have a viable exit strategy. As a result, startups offering practical solutions that address immediate industry challenges and generate near-term revenue are likely to benefit. Key Growth Areas will emerge despite an overall decline in funding, particularly in Farm Robotics, Mechanization & Equipment, which, due to its connection to climate tech, is expected to see steady growth. Similarly, Bioenergy & Biomaterials will continue to attract investment due to the rising demand for sustainable alternatives. From Disruption to Transition signals a shift from disruptive innovations toward more gradual, sustainable approaches in transforming the food industry. This transition suggests a focus on solutions that can be integrated into existing systems, with an emphasis on long-term challenges like improving supply chain efficiency and reducing food waste.

As we look ahead to 2025, predictions are shaped by existing data and broader global challenges. Food Security will take centre stage, driven by climate change, geopolitical instability, and population growth. As a result, investment will focus on technologies and business models aimed at boosting production efficiency and yields, enhancing supply chain resilience and transparency, and reducing food loss and waste. Sustainability will remain a core value, with rising consumer demand for sustainable and ethically produced food. This will encourage investments in regenerative agriculture practices that improve soil health and biodiversity, as well as solutions that minimize the environmental impact of food production. Moreover, alternative proteins and innovative food technologies offering more sustainable options are set to attract continued attention. AI and Automation will see rapid integration across the food value chain. This will lead to advancements such as precision agriculture techniques that optimize resource use, robotic harvesting and automated food processing to tackle labour shortages, and personalized nutrition solutions that cater to individual health needs.

7.2 Companies challenges

Companies offering and developing solutions for the agri-food industry face many challenges. These challenges result in postponing investments in technological innovation or deliberately slowing down the development reducing the risk of failure. The main barriers identified by respondents are shown in figure 12

Figure 12. Barriers identified by responders in introducing AI and robotics in agri-food sector.
Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

The high cost of implementing new technology is natural, but in the case of the agricultural and high-tech sector, there are additional elements associated with high risk.

Knowledge and staff cost

For most of the responders biggest challenge is the high initial costs (71% of respondents). This is natural and quite obvious and refers to many different origin challenges. One of them is lack of knowledge and skills in AI and ML in technical teams. There is currently an estimated shortage of around 500,000 artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) professionals in the European Union. This shortage is the result of a growing demand for these skills in various sectors of the economy, such as healthcare, finance and manufacturing. This also results in a shortage of skilled developers in the area of products for the agricultural and food processing industry. The result is the problem of attracting a suitably qualified team through recruitment, as well as its relatively high cost of labour. Companies are also becoming aware of the lack of knowledge among existing employees and are focusing on development through further training and the acquisition of technology through cooperation with other institutions or consortia. Most of the companies operating in emerging technologies have already established such cooperation or are planning to do so in near future.

Uncertain market demand and early diffusion stage

Diffusion of innovation is the process of spreading of an innovation in a company or society or a selected group affected by a given technology. It can be seen that this process is progressing quite dynamically in the agricultural industry. However, it still faces a series of barriers. The level of acceptance is partly related to the high conservatism of the audience and the reluctance to change in the area of well-known agricultural practices. On the other hand, the pragmatism of farmers and users of these technologies demands proven solutions, whose reliable performance will be proven above all by the number of successful implementations. The uncertainty surrounding the adoption of the technology and overcoming the also significant barrier of massification means that companies still perceive investment in AI and ML technologies in their solution area as risky. Manufacturers must therefore prove to early majority customers that advanced solutions are more efficient and at the same time just as robust as classic solutions. Only then can it be said that the market has adopted the technology and that there is a demand for it, which would explain the investment in development.

A not insignificant fact is that solutions of this type are in most cases difficult to integrate with the currently used software in agriculture (FMS) or with the equipment used throughout the production cycle. This is one of the main challenges facing producers, where it appears that there must be a standardisation of the flow of information between the different parts of the agricultural technology chain. Such a solution would guarantee the delivery of a relatively simpler-to-use product and the entry of a broader mass market of consumers focusing on pragmatic use.

The standardization process that is certainly needed can be compared to the identical process that has been going on for several years in the smart home industry. Matter standard promotes interoperability between devices from different manufacturers, which could be an inspiration for Agriculture 4.0, where the integration of different technologies and data from multiple unrelated sources and products could facilitate the creation of integrated farm management systems and use in machineries.

Example of interoperability resulting in fertilisation:

1. Collection of visual data by satellite (provider A) and drone (provider B).
2. Acquisition of information about the planned crop from the FMS (provider C).
3. Processing of input data by a cloud-based system (decision making system of provider C).
4. Transmission of the abundance map of the required fertilisers to the on-board device on the tractor with the spreader (manufacturer D).
5. The device spreads the appropriate fertiliser according to the map.

Most respondents recognize the low development of the market for these types of products and the related concerns of farmers. The main challenges in this regard are indicated on figure 13.

Figure 13. Barriers among farmers identified by responders in introducing AI and robotics in agri-food sector. Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

Concerns from the agricultural community correspond with the adoption rate indicated by responders towards agricultural potential users of AI technology and full task automation.

Figure 14.. Adoption rate by farmers.
 Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

The data indicates that the average adoption rate of new solutions by farmers is ranges from 26-35%, excluding unknown responses. This suggests the market is at a critical point known as the "chasm," where transitioning from early adopters to the early majority is essential for broader acceptance. This translates to lower demand and increased investment risk. Only tangible, pragmatic results will drive increased adoption and transition to the mass market.

Regulatory challenges and concerns

Companies in the European Union face several regulatory concerns. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) imposes strict rules on data collection, processing, and storage, raising compliance issues for AI systems that require large datasets. Determining liability for AI system failures is complex, with concerns about who is responsible if an AI system causes harm or makes a critical error. The EU AI Act, set to be fully enforced by 2026, introduces a risk-based approach to AI regulation, imposing stringent requirements on high-risk AI systems used in critical infrastructure or healthcare.

There are ethical concerns about the use of AI, including issues of bias, fairness, and the potential for AI to replace human jobs. Companies must ensure their AI systems do not perpetuate discrimination or unfair practices. Balancing innovation with regulation is a significant challenge, as overly stringent regulations could stifle innovation and make it difficult to bring new AI technologies to market. The cost and complexity of compliance with various EU regulations can be burdensome for producers, potentially impacting their competitiveness.

Concerns about the transparency and explainability of AI systems arise, as regulations may require producers to provide detailed explanations of how their AI systems make decisions. Ensuring the security and robustness of AI systems is

crucial, as vulnerabilities could be exploited, leading to significant risks. The need for continuous monitoring and updating of AI systems to comply with evolving regulations adds to the operational burden for producers too. Producers must navigate the varying regulatory landscapes across different EU member states, which can complicate compliance efforts. There are concerns about the potential for regulatory fragmentation within the EU, which could create inconsistencies and challenges for producers operating in multiple countries. The need for collaboration with regulatory bodies to ensure compliance and address emerging issues is essential but can be resource-intensive. Manufacturers must also consider the environmental impact of their AI systems, as regulations may require them to minimize energy consumption and reduce carbon footprints. The integration of AI systems with existing technologies and infrastructure can be challenging, requiring significant investment and adaptation. Finally, there is a need for ongoing education and training for both producers and users to ensure they understand and comply with regulatory requirements, which can be a continuous and demanding process.

7.3 European Support for AI and Robotics

The European Commission cooperates with the member states to create robust regulatory standards and to give a financial backing to the research and development efforts. These partnership procedures aim at the promotion of AI technologies that are accountable, stable, and also inclusive; therefore, the use of these AI techniques will ensure that the whole of Europe receives benefits.

In the previous chapter, we outlined the challenges faced by technology companies developing robotic and AI technologies for the agrifood sector. This chapter highlights the European Union's role in addressing these challenges, emphasizing initiatives like the agrifoodTEF centers established under this project to support the testing and validation of innovative solutions for modern agriculture. However, these centers are not the only avenue of support. Europe offers a wide range of strategies, programs, and initiatives to aid organizations in advancing new technologies. This chapter provides a detailed overview of these efforts, including specific projects and initiatives aimed at fostering innovation and sustainability.

The European Union and its member states play a pivotal role in advancing artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics through comprehensive policies, regulatory frameworks, and funding programs. These initiatives aim to maximize the benefits of AI while maintaining high ethical standards, protecting citizens' rights, and ensuring equitable access to technology for all. By supporting innovation and fostering collaboration, the EU seeks to strengthen its technological leadership and promote sustainable development across various sectors, including agriculture.

Main European Union Initiatives:

- **Policies, Strategies and Regulatory Initiatives**

The European Union plays a pivotal role in shaping the development of artificial intelligence (AI) through a range of comprehensive policies and regulatory frameworks. These efforts are aimed at fostering responsible and sustainable AI growth, ensuring that the technology benefits society while maintaining high ethical standards. Central to these initiatives are the **European AI Strategy** and **AI Act**, which set clear guidelines focused on transparency, accountability, and fairness in AI systems. These frameworks aim to promote innovation in the digital economy while also safeguarding human rights and social values.

The EU's approach to AI regulation goes beyond technological advancement, emphasizing the responsible use of artificial intelligence in ways that respect citizens' rights. The **European Commission** plays a critical role in overseeing the proper implementation of these policies, ensuring that AI development aligns with Europe's broader goals of promoting ethical, secure, and inclusive technologies. By fostering a balanced approach that encourages innovation

while ensuring that AI respects fundamental rights, the EU aims to strengthen Europe's position in the global technological race while promoting ethical standards across all sectors of society.¹³⁷

Among the most significant documents and initiatives that shape EU policy on artificial intelligence are the following (in chronological order):

- **Statement on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems** (March 2018) - Released by the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies, this document stresses the importance of ensuring AI, robotics, and autonomous systems are developed ethically, respecting human dignity, rights, and democratic values. It calls for the establishment of international ethical principles for these technologies and highlights the need for human oversight and transparency in AI systems.
Key Points: Ethical framework for AI, human-centered approach, accountability, and transparency.¹³⁸
- **Communication on Artificial Intelligence for Europe** (April 2018) - This communication by the European Commission outlined a strategy for AI development in Europe, focusing on creating a strong ecosystem for AI, promoting research, and ensuring ethical considerations.
Key Points: European AI research and investment, alignment with ethical principles, and enhancing Europe's competitiveness.¹³⁹
- **Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence** (December 2018) - Introduced to ensure coordinated efforts between EU member states for AI development, this plan aimed at aligning national AI strategies, fostering collaboration, and pooling resources.
Key Points: National AI strategies, collaboration, and investment in AI research and innovation.¹⁴⁰
- **Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI** (April 2019) - Published by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), these guidelines outline ethical principles for developing AI that aligns with European values, focusing on transparency, accountability, and data privacy.
Key Points: Trustworthy AI, fairness, transparency, and accountability.¹⁴¹
- **White Paper on Artificial Intelligence** (February 2020) – This document proposed a European approach to AI regulation, introducing the concept of a risk-based framework for AI applications. It laid the groundwork for the AI Act.
Key Points: Risk-based regulation, balancing innovation with AI safety, and protecting fundamental rights.¹⁴²
- **Shaping Europe's Digital Future** (February 2020) - A strategic document that outlines Europe's digital transformation, with AI as a central component for driving economic growth and ensuring digital sovereignty.
Key Points: Europe's digital future, investment in AI, and safeguarding ethical AI practices.¹⁴³
- **The Digital Compass: The European Way for the Digital Decade** (March 2021) – A roadmap for Europe's digital transformation by 2030, emphasizing AI as a critical element for innovation, competitiveness, and sustainability.

¹³⁷ European approach to artificial intelligence: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-approach-artificial-intelligence>

¹³⁸ Statement on Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems: https://commission.europa.eu/research-and-innovation_en

¹³⁹ Communication on Artificial Intelligence for Europe: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/communication-artificial-intelligence-europe>

¹⁴⁰ Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/plan-ai>

¹⁴¹ Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

¹⁴² White Paper on Artificial Intelligence: https://commission.europa.eu/publications/white-paper-artificial-intelligence-european-approach-excellence-and-trust_en

¹⁴³ Shaping Europe's Digital Future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en>

Key Points: Investments in AI, digital infrastructure, and ensuring Europe’s global competitiveness.¹⁴⁴

- **Proposal for the AI Act** (April 2021) – The European Commission proposed the AI Act, the world’s first regulatory framework for AI. The Act classifies AI applications by their risk levels and introduces legal obligations to ensure safe and trustworthy AI.

Key Points: High-risk AI regulation, compliance requirements, and penalties for non-compliance.¹⁴⁵

- **AI@EC Communication** (January 2024) - The European Commission’s internal communication on AI, outlining how AI will be adopted within EU institutions. It focuses on AI skills development, ethical AI use, and governance structures. The latest communication from the EC on AI aims to summarize previous actions and outline the next steps toward developing artificial intelligence in Europe, taking into account the latest technological and political trends.

Key Points: AI strategy for internal Commission use, governance structures, and ethical AI development.¹⁴⁶

- **Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act)** - officially adopted by the European Commission in April 2021, is the world's first comprehensive legislation aimed at regulating the use of artificial intelligence. It entered into force in August 2024 and will become fully applicable on 2 August 2026. The Act seeks to establish a legal framework to foster trust in AI technologies, ensure accountability, and enhance safety, particularly in high-risk applications. Additionally, it aims to reduce administrative and financial burdens on businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Companies must prepare for various provisions with staggered implementation deadlines, reflecting the risk levels assigned to different AI systems. Stricter regulations are applied to high-risk AI applications, including general-purpose AI models, to address their potential impacts. This landmark legislation emphasizes balancing innovation with safeguarding rights and public safety.¹⁴⁷

These strategies and political initiatives are key to the sustainable development of artificial intelligence (AI) in Europe which integrates technological advancement with the social and economic values of the European Union. A chronological timeline of key European Union documents related to artificial intelligence (AI):

¹⁴⁴ The Digital Compass: The European Way for the Digital Decade: <https://eufordigital.eu/library/2030-digital-compass-the-european-way-for-the-digital-decade/>

¹⁴⁵ Proposal for the AI Act: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>

¹⁴⁶ AI@EC Communication: <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/cinea/items/815935/>

¹⁴⁷ Artificial Intelligence Act” (AI Act): <https://www.ropesgray.com/en/insights/viewpoints/102jd2c/eu-ai-act-published-in-the-official-journal-of-the-european-union-clock-starts-f>

Figure 15. Europe's Journey Towards Responsible AI Regulation.
Source: Own work, based on collected data (2024).

Some of the regulations that have been placed such as the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) ensures that safety and ethical measures are met in especially areas that are considered to be high risk. This involves data privacy, data protection, preventing discrimination, and ensuring transparency in the functioning of AI systems. This is because these regulations help build trust between the citizens and the business people making it easy for the new technologies to be embraced.

Similarly, the sustainable artificial intelligence development is also fostered by programs such as Horizon Europe and Digital Europe that finance the development of digital framework, scientific research and education in the next generation advanced technologies. Specific attention is paid to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as they are considered as important players in the European economy. This makes sure that the AI technologies are available to smaller entities which in turn puts them on equal footing with their larger competitors.

These initiatives also aim to achieve socio-economic gains including enhancing citizens' quality of life through the integration of AI in healthcare, education, and public administration. Furthermore, they help with the shift to the green economy by using AI to address climate change.

This approach does not only give Europe an edge over other regions in the technology race but also fosters the essential values of equality, responsibility and sustainable development.

7.4 Companies' outlook for 2025

Technologies under development in 2025

It is clear that the industry recognizes the pivotal role of precision farming in achieving the objectives of the European Green Deal. Specifically, the Green Deal aims to reduce the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides, with targets of cutting fertilizer use by 20% and pesticide use by 50% by 2030. These goals are expected to be achieved through the application of Variable Rate Technology (VRT), which enables the precise application of inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, and water, tailored to the specific needs of different areas within a field. This approach helps minimize waste while improving crop yields. Additionally, the industry is increasingly focused on gathering large volumes of data from both long-term local sources and real-time information, which are then used to generate detailed maps of soil health and resource availability through advanced machine learning models. Data for decision-making is collected from various sources, but IoT sensors play a crucial role, becoming a robust and reliable source of information for these applications.

Technologies that have been identified by our experts as ones that will be developed in the next year in the companies are presented on Figure 16.

Figure 16. Technologies that will be further developed by SMEs. Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

Investment trends in 2025

In 2025, the agri-food industry is expected to navigate a complex landscape shaped by new EU regulations and economic stagnation. Despite these challenges, 34% of respondents predict an increase in investments in the sector. A significant portion of these investments, 21%, will likely focus on sustainability, including biomaterials, AI, and alternative ingredients. This trend aligns with the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), which imposes a carbon price on certain imports to encourage greener practices. Additionally, the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) aims to ensure that products consumed in the EU do not contribute to deforestation, further driving investments in sustainable practices.

Digital technologies are also anticipated to attract increased investment, with 17% of respondents highlighting areas such as AI, robotics, and precision farming. These technologies can enhance efficiency and productivity, crucial in a stagnant economic environment and upcoming labour shortages. The focus on efficiency and food safety, supported by 12% of respondents, is essential for meeting regulatory requirements and consumer expectations. The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) will push companies to improve product sustainability, adding another layer of compliance. This fact also finds reference in triggering values for development (Figure 17).

However, 6% of respondents foresee a decline in investment, possibly due to economic uncertainties. Many products addressed to meet certain agro-technology needs are still currently in the early market phase, primarily adopted by innovators and early adopters. To achieve mainstream success, it needs to cross the chasm and appeal to the early majority with meeting new regulatory standards. The overall economic situation, marked by stagnation, could limit the availability of capital for new investments. Despite this, the push for sustainability and digital transformation is expected to drive significant changes in the industry.

Figure 17. The most important triggers for development of new solutions/products
Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

Based on the development directions indicated by the respondents, the following areas of work should be highlighted for the coming year.

- **Data Integration with Machine Learning Algorithms:**
 - Collecting data from IoT sensors, drones, and agricultural machines combined with machine learning algorithms enabling the creation of predictive crop models.
 - Predictive analysis for early responses to environmental changes, increasing efficiency and minimizing losses.
- **Development of Affordable and Accessible IoT Sensors:**
 - Advancements in sensor technology to increase affordable and durable sensor technologies
 - Use of communication technologies based on wide-area networks to address the issue of rural areas still lacking reliable and affordable internet access.
- **Blockchain Utilization in the Food Supply Chain:**
 - Blockchain enabling complete tracking of products from field to table, increasing transparency and consumer trust.
 - Registering data on the origin, quality, and storage methods of products, minimizing the risk of fraud and losses.
- **Autonomous Machine Systems:**
 - Agricultural machines equipped with advanced sensors and AI algorithms operating autonomously, collecting data on soil, plants, and weather conditions.
 - Examples include robots for harvesting, which can simultaneously monitor crop quality and transmit data for analysis.
- **Development of Digital Twins:**
 - Digital twins of agricultural fields allowing simulation of various scenarios, such as the impact of climate change on crops.
 - Enabling testing of resource management strategies in a virtual environment, reducing the risk of making incorrect decisions in real-world farming.

8 Conclusions and recommendations

As part of this year's technology review, based on surveys with industry experts and analysis of various sources, the directions for developing the infrastructure necessary for implementing agrifoodTEF services, as identified in the D1.5¹⁴⁸ report, were outlined. The review results were also compared to the current catalogue of services and their use cases, as detailed in the Service Request Descriptions compiled in the D1.7¹⁴⁹ report. This chapter, divided into two sections focusing on services and infrastructure, outlines the directions in which the agrifoodTEF offerings can be developed and expanded in the coming years.

¹⁴⁸ D1.5 Professionalization and Internationalization of Physical Infrastructure and Services Y2

¹⁴⁹ D1.7 Characteristics of the use of services and directions of development report Y2

8.1 Services

An analysis of the agrifoodTEF service catalogue survey results highlights a strong emphasis on services for arable farming. The surveys further indicate that precision agriculture, robotics, and AI are pivotal for the field crops sector, while the lack of similar services in food processing could limit growth, given that about 60% of respondents stressed the importance of data processing and AI. Additionally, respondents underscored the need for real-world testing conditions and highlighted the overall underrepresentation of services that could support businesses.

Figure 18 Comparison of services offered by agrifoodTEF and perspective potential of technology development in various sectors from IE survey

The chart compares the number of services currently offered by agrifoodTEF with the perceived potential for technological development in various sectors, as identified by industry experts. "Arable farming" stands out with the highest number of services (204) and aligns well with its high perceived potential (23%). In contrast, sectors like "Horticulture," "Tree crops," and "Viticulture" have significantly fewer services despite notable potential (17%, 13%, and 14%, respectively). "Livestock farming," which combines livestock and cattle, shows a moderate match between services (37) and potential (21%). "FoodTech" is identified as a promising sector (14%) but is underserved with only 5 services. Lastly, the "Other" category, which includes forestry, advisory services, and supply chain management, represents 27% of the perceived potential but is not reflected in the current offerings, highlighting an opportunity for expansion in these areas.

Figure 19. Other sectors with potential of technology development from IE survey

In response to these findings, the recommendations focus on achieving greater sectoral balance by expanding the service catalogue for underserved areas like food processing, orcharding, and horticulture. Incorporating precision irrigation, greenhouse gas monitoring, and chemical input reduction will foster sustainability. Aligning with technological trends is also crucial—broadening the reach of IoT, robotics, and Big Data beyond field crops and into animal husbandry and viticulture will address sectoral gaps. Similarly, the development of digital twins and AI-driven solutions for processing and resource management will help future-proof these sectors.

Finally, implementation support should be enhanced by ensuring access to real-world testing conditions across all sectors, a priority identified by survey respondents. The sustainability aspect must also be addressed, with services promoting eco-friendly practices, resource optimization in livestock farming, and improved crop monitoring in viticulture. Through these adjustments, agrifoodTEF can create a more comprehensive, balanced, and forward-looking portfolio of services.

The current agrifoodTEF service catalogue is strongly focused on field crops, which aligns with the trends in precision agriculture and the high technological maturity of arable farming. However, expanding services in underserved sectors such as food processing, orcharding, and livestock farming—and incorporating more AI, IoT, and Big Data technologies—could significantly improve the portfolio’s comprehensiveness and responsiveness to market needs.

An internal classification analysis shows that the proposed taxonomy of use cases (Macro × Sector × Activity × Solution) allows for **2,640 distinct theoretical combinations** (excluding generic “Other” categories). Even when considering only the three key dimensions (Macro × Sector × Activity), there are still **220 unique combinations**. This confirms the complexity and diversity of needs across the agrifood sector and underlines the importance of **modular, general-purpose service design**.

Designing scalable services around core functional clusters—such as **observation systems, mobility platforms, and harvesting automation**—enables broad applicability while maintaining clarity, usability, and cost-effectiveness. This approach prevents fragmentation and avoids the need for thousands of overly specific services that could reduce the catalogue’s transparency.

Moreover, considering that only an estimated **5–20%** of potential clients have implemented advanced digital technologies, and that **ready-to-use physical solutions remain scarce**, it is essential to extend support across all

innovation stages. Services such as training, infrastructure audits, and staged testing environments are key to addressing barriers like insufficient technical knowledge, investment uncertainty, and resistance to change. These complementary services can significantly enhance client readiness and accelerate technology adoption in the agrifood sector.

Reviewing the pilot services that have been reported so far and relating them to the survey results, the following observations can be made:

- **Data (approx. 39%):** This category dominates, which aligns with the surveys indicating data analytics and AI technologies as key drivers of digital transformation. These services support data-driven decision-making and process optimization.
- **Algorithms (approx. 26%):** While important, these could be further developed in terms of validation and integration with physical systems, addressing the need for real-world testing, which was highlighted as crucial by survey respondents.
- **Physical Systems (approx. 7%):** The low percentage of services in this category may stem from the limited availability of ready-made solutions on the market. Clients often report difficulties in integrating new technologies and uncertainty regarding return on investment, which can discourage implementation.
- **Undefined Services (approx. 17%):** These should be replaced with audits or training sessions that directly address barriers identified in the surveys, such as lack of technical knowledge, implementation costs and resistance to change. These services could assist clients in managing risk and preparing infrastructure for implementations. This category requires further definition to better meet client needs, particularly in supporting innovation processes.

Figure 20. Challenges faced by companies during the conceptual, implementation, testing, validation, and sales stages of new technology. Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

To better address the identified gaps and enhance the overall service offering, the following measures are proposed:

- **Balancing the sectoral offer:** Expand services in underserved sectors such as food processing, livestock farming, and viticulture, incorporating key technologies like AI, IoT, and automation.
- **Increasing focus on physical systems:** Concentrate on supporting customers in designing, testing, and integrating physical systems, which are crucial for demonstrating technologies in real-world conditions.
- **Education and support:** Introduce audits and training sessions as complementary services to address competency gaps and support customers in the early stages of implementation.
- **Demonstrating value:** Emphasize the specific benefits provided by the implemented services, such as increased efficiency, cost reduction, and sustainable development, to build customer trust in new technologies.

These actions can help better align services with market expectations and accelerate the adoption of new technologies in the agrifood sector.

8.2 Infrastructure

The current physical infrastructure of agrifoodTEF largely meets the technological needs related to testing and validation of solutions in the agri-food sector. It provides support for precision farming technologies, robotics and automation and

sensor systems, enabling tests in real and laboratory conditions. Resources such as test fields, robotic platforms, and systems for physicochemical analysis provide a solid base for the development of innovative technologies. Below is a graph showing the percentage rating of agrifoodTEF infrastructure in relation to the needs of survey respondents (figure 21).

Given the broad spectrum of possible technology-sector-activity combinations, the infrastructure should remain modular and reconfigurable, allowing support for a wide variety of practical use cases without the need for fully dedicated setups. Core infrastructure clusters, such as observation platforms, mobile robotic systems, and sensor fusion environments, can be adapted to multiple sectors and technologies with minimal configuration changes.

Figure 21. Relevance of agrifoodTEF Infrastructure to surveyed needs. Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

The analysis of the survey results indicates the need to supplement the infrastructure in areas related to monitoring animals in breeding, testing AI technologies in various environmental conditions and obtaining data from new environments, such as forests and orchards. In response to the question "What are the biggest challenges faced by your company or the companies you are familiar with in implementing advanced technologies in the agriculture and food-processing industries?", several answers indicate relevance to food traceability, showcasing growing interest and opportunities for technological advancements, such as fraud detection. The lack of infrastructure and access to data (7.3%) directly addresses traceability, as it requires robust systems for data collection and sharing across the supply chain. Additionally, challenges such as ensuring food safety and quality (6.5%), building awareness and trust in new technologies (9.8%), and improving collaboration among stakeholders (5.5%) also indirectly highlight the importance of traceability. These responses suggest increasing recognition of traceability's potential and its role in driving innovation in agriculture and food processing.

It is advisable to enrich existing test fields with systems simulating dynamically changing environmental conditions and to develop facilities supporting testing of innovative technologies, such as intelligent water management systems or plant protection solutions. Additionally, shared data acquisition pipelines, reusable test modules, and cross-sector

mobility or observation components can increase efficiency and lower entry barriers for underserved use cases, such as food processing or forestry.

Respondents emphasized the need to test technologies in diverse and changing environmental conditions, which is particularly important for the development of autonomous systems and AI-based solutions that must operate reliably in diverse field scenarios. As a specific example, intelligent water management systems, including irrigation, were indicated, which require infrastructure enabling precise control of water resources, e.g. through the use of lysometers or controlled sprinkler systems, allowing for the reduction of losses and optimization of water use.

Given the breadth of the agri-food sector and the diversity of technologies, any infrastructure should be flexible and adaptable to specific use cases. The modular design of test setups and reusability across related applications will increase scalability and better match the dynamic and fragmented innovation landscape of the agri-food sector.

8.3 AgrifoodTEF as a partner for cooperation

Based on responses, companies are interested in collaborating with Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) primarily to minimize costs between development and market readiness (Figure 22). This includes, but is not limited to, testing costs. Potential access to specialized infrastructure and expertise is also crucial. Another key benefit is access to diverse testing conditions through international collaboration, utilizing infrastructure and facilities located in other countries.

Figure 22. Factors influencing on agrifoodTEF services choice. Source: own compilation based on collected survey data (2024).

The elaboration of the above is reflected in the main areas of interest selected by the respondents. Main topics of interest are:

- **Testing in controlled environments by experts:** This is one of the most frequently selected themes. It often appears in conjunction with other options, suggesting that participants see great value in testing technologies in specialized settings before they are deployed more widely.

- **Services using methods for testing innovative technologies:** Readiness for testing innovative solutions is clearly a significant focus point. Participants show a appreciation to ability of testing new technologies that are under development.
- **Iteratively improve solutions based on new AI models or design changes:** This option comes up multiple times and shows how important it is for participants to be able to continually evolve and optimize the technology based on current results and changes in AI models provided.
- **Collaboration with interdisciplinary teams (engineers, agronomists, data scientists):** Collaboration with teams from different disciplines is also an important issue that participants consider crucial for creating innovative solutions.
- **Development discussions and engagement with end users:** Although mentioned sporadically, this option indicates an interest not only in the technology but also in its practical application and interaction with end users.

The internal classification of use cases confirms that individual technologies often span multiple sectors and activities, which highlights the need for modular, reconfigurable infrastructure. From the cooperation perspective, agrifoodTEF's key value lies in enabling companies to test cross-sectoral and multi-activity scenarios without the need for dedicated setups. This flexibility reduces entry barriers for SMEs, supports validation of complex or emerging solutions, and increases the chances of successful market adoption under varied real-world conditions.

